

University of the West of Scotland

**Celebrating Personal and Professional Identities:
A Case Study of Minority Ethnic Teachers in Scotland**

Khadija Mohammed

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Declaration

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Signed

Date: 28th June 2022

Personal details withheld.

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PRESENTATIONS AND PUBLICATIONS RELATED TO THIS WORK.

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Abstract

In 2015, only two per cent of teachers in Scotland identify as Minority Ethnic compared with four per cent in the general population. In 2016, this figure had declined to one per cent of the workforce (Teacher census data, 2016). These statistics raise questions about the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers. The purpose of this research was to understand minority ethnic teachers' perceptions of their personal and professional identities to better understand how they actively and consciously bring their personal identities into their teaching. The research uses a case study approach drawing on qualitative research conducted with minority ethnic teachers from the West of Scotland.

Focus groups and semi-structured interviews ascertained the views of minority ethnic teachers. The research explores the intersecting relationship between the personal and professional elements of teachers' lives, experiences, beliefs and practices and the broader social conditions in which teachers live and work. Consideration of the tensions and conflicts that exist in each of these elements show how this affects teachers' professional identities. The core research question analysed in this thesis was – 'How do Minority Ethnic teachers negotiate their personal and professional identities?' Critical race theory and constructo-interpretivism provided a useful lens to examine the teaching lives of minority ethnic teachers, with respect to the particular issues they face because of their culture, religion and language.

I argue that to address the concerns of minority ethnic teachers it is important to acknowledge the individual/institutional racism they experience; affirm the added value they bring to their work and use this to support agency. When all three aspects connect, minority ethnic teachers can build capacity and resilience to make a difference through their activism. I have identified this as the four As model in the formation of their professional identities: Acknowledgment, Affirmation, Agency and Activism.

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Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition
Minority ethnic	Highlights the fact that everyone has an ethnicity and the issues referred to minority groups in the UK context and the discrimination and barriers that they face.
Culture	Culture is defined as the lived experiences and can take many forms including cultural practices, language and religion.
Critical Race Theory (CRT)	A concept that analyses the complexity of racism and racial justice in the narratives of minority ethnic teachers. CRT draws attention to the institutional racism in schools.
Professional Identity	One's professional self-concept based on attributes beliefs, values and experiences.
Acknowledgment	In safer affinity spaces, minority ethnic teachers' racialised experiences are validated, helping them to reflect on and navigate through the racial inequity they encounter working in schools.
Affirmation	By sharing experiences, histories and healing practices, the added value minority ethnic teachers bring to their work and wider professional community is recognised.
Agency	Self-evaluation and critical reflection support minority ethnic teachers to step outside systemic expectations and allow different practices to emerge, strengthening their professional identity.
Activism	Building capacity and resilience to make a difference.

Chapter One

An Introduction to the *research thesis*

This research seeks to examine minority ethnic teachers' perceptions of their personal and professional identities to better understand how they actively and consciously bring their personal identities into their teaching. The research aim was to explore the teaching lives of minority ethnic teachers, concerning the particular issues they face that align to culture, religion and language. In doing so, research findings show factors that impact on the formation of their professional identities.

Discussion of content and purpose is dealt with in three sections. Firstly, the chapter introduces the context of the study by locating it within the current discourse. Next, it presents the growing diversity of the pupil population and finally, considers the decline in the number of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland.

Introducing the context for this study

This section introduces minority ethnic teachers' experiences within a Scottish demographic where minority ethnic teachers were found to be an underrepresented workforce in Scotland.

Since the creation of a devolved Government in Scotland, in 1999, there have been concerns over the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers (Scottish Executive, 2004). The ethnic demography of teachers in Scotland was not proportionate to the pupil population. Only 0.5% of all primary teachers were from a minority ethnic group in 2005 and 1.1% in secondary schools. The 2004 census shows that there are 3.80% of black and minority ethnic pupils in schools and that is approximately four times more than the minority ethnic teacher population (Teacher

Census Data, 2004). In 2004, the Chief Executive of the General Teaching Council of Scotland spoke at a Recruitment of Ethnic Minorities into Teaching (REMIT) symposium raising concerns about the lack of teachers from black and minority ethnic groups in primary schools in Scotland (Scottish Executive, 2004). This symposium articulated a vision for an inclusive, multicultural Scotland, which celebrated diversity asserting that:

The methods of the last century do not meet the needs of this century and the teaching profession needs to be as diverse as the population of the country.

(Scottish Executive, 2004, p.3)

This vision also questioned pedagogical practices, which met the needs of children in a multi-cultural context. Such questions suggested that schools needed to raise the bar in terms of recognising and utilising the social and cultural capital in and around the local community.

Two years later, Menter et al. (2006) carried out a systematic literature review on 'Widening Access to The Teaching Profession'. They argued that with the creation of the new Scottish Parliament and the Scottish Executive, there was a significant political emphasis on inclusion and the need to celebrate diversity. It was in this context that priority was given to seeking a teaching workforce, which would be representative of the population of Scotland. Moreover, Menter et al. (2006) suggested some possible motives behind this concern to improve the representativeness of the teaching profession.

Firstly, Scotland's Public Services have been known to adopt a more universal approach where all Scottish citizens should have full access to education, health and social services. As such, it would be important to ensure that a profession of such

importance as teaching should include people from all sections of that community. The second argument for this drive to diversify was described as an educational or professional issue whereby a correlation between levels of poor performance from minority ethnic pupils and the lack of teachers from the same group was being considered.

Mentor et. al's (2006) findings also asserted that the existence of a diverse workforce would afford opportunities for teachers to learn from their minority ethnic colleagues and present a curriculum that draws from a range of cultural and linguistic experiences and enables children to make 'cultural connections' with their teachers (p.273). This stressed that more effort was required to promote teaching as a possible profession among minority ethnic communities.

It is useful to understand that similar concerns were raised in England with the Mayor of London in 2006, commissioning a report titled 'Black Teachers in London' (Greater London Authority, 2006). This report was in response to a previous study which detailed the experiences of black pupils, and black boys in particular, in London's schools and it concluded that there was still some work to do to make schools genuinely inclusive for pupils and teachers alike (The London Development Agency, 2004). The Mayor of London clearly stated:

In order to improve achievement levels in our schools it is of paramount importance that the teaching profession, classroom staff and governing bodies better reflect the diversity of the communities they serve. It cannot be right that in some of our boroughs 48-50 per cent of the pupils are black, yet only 16-18 per cent of the teachers that teach them are of similar heritage.

(Greater London Authority 2006, p.v)

Ross (2006) asserts that minority ethnic teachers play a vital role in raising the achievement of children from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds and alerts us to the potential dangers of not allowing these roles to develop. He argues that Black teachers' commitment to teaching children often resulted in them taking on a heavy workload and this workload increased where black teachers felt they had to carry the additional burden of raising black pupils' achievement. He alludes to the 'added value'¹ that minority ethnic teachers bring when he states:

With such a range of teachers, we can aspire towards delivering an education that has the subtlety and the nuance to make each individual feel that her or his cultural set is acknowledged and valued.

(Ross, 2006, p.2).

The 'subtlety' and 'nuances' to which he refers warrant further exploration to gain a better understanding of what kind of 'added value' can be accessed by and through minority ethnic teachers' identities.

In light of the ongoing concerns about the small numbers of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland, Arshad and Mitchell (2007, p.2) also raised the important question of 'whether a predominantly homogenous teaching workforce can deliver effectively for an increasingly diverse learner population?' This further reinforces the need for teaching to be culturally relevant to the needs of pupils (Bhatti, 1999; Shain, 2005). As such, teachers now attend courses to develop their professional skills on how to

¹ I use the phrase "added value" with hesitation, as it may imply a deficit for teachers of majority ethnic background. This deficit model should be avoided, which is why, throughout this thesis, I have generally preferred to write about cultural capital (which may be distinct, yet equal to that offered by teachers of majority ethnic background).

include a range of diverse learners, but such courses often do not engage teachers in a critical examination of their own attitudes (Arshad and Mitchell, 2007).

Furthermore, in 2010, a review of teacher education in Scotland considered the skills and qualities required for teaching in the twenty-first century (The Donaldson Report, 2010). The report recognised that teachers' professional practice is 'rooted in strong values' and it provided a vision of teachers who take responsibility for their personal and professional development (p.15). Similarly, McCormack (2011) in his report on *Advancing teacher professionalism* also highlights that teachers who are empowered to work within a wider learning community could lead to better outcomes for children. The recommendations made by both reports created opportunities for positive change as they alluded to the importance of considering the personal and professional identities of teachers. They recognised the concept of empowerment as building on the social and cultural capital in and around the school community. However, both the Donaldson Report and McCormack failed to refer to minority ethnic teachers in their reports further reinforcing the question of how a homogenous teaching workforce could make cultural connections with their diverse pupils.

In 2011, Santoro et al. undertook some research with indigenous teachers in Australia and argued that indigenous teachers understand the cultural practice, values and beliefs that help shape indigenous pupils as learners and that they better understand their lives beyond schools. They (2011) suggest that indigenous teachers should mentor the non-indigenous teachers for them to connect with the pupils and ensure that their teaching is responsive to their needs.

Egalite, Kisida and Winters (2015) also undertook some research in the USA in Florida Public Schools. They found small but significant positive effects when black and white students are assigned to race-congruent teachers. It is argued that this does not suggest that only minority ethnic teachers can successfully teach minority ethnic children but that minority ethnic teachers can draw on their cultural and linguistic skills to benefit the education of *all* children. As such, there has been an

emerging consensus for the notion of diverse teachers for diverse learners and for practice, which acknowledges and utilises the cultural, religious and linguistic needs of the diverse learners. This includes the argument that being visible in school settings and leading learning, could help to challenge stereotypical representations that are held by members of the wider school community, staff, parents and children (Arshad et al, 2007). However, it has been over two decades since the devolved government was created and diversity in the teaching profession continues to be an issue.

Increasingly diverse pupil population in Scotland

Increase in diversity

Due to a range of political and economic factors, the demographics of pupil populations in Scottish schools are becoming increasingly diverse. According to the 2011 Scottish Census, the population of Scotland was estimated to be 5,295,403 - the highest ever and a 4.6% rise since 2001. The size of the minority ethnic population was just over 200,000 in 2011 or four percent of the total population of Scotland, which was double the figure in the 2001 census. Pakistanis were the largest minority ethnic group, followed by Chinese, Indians and those of 'Mixed' ethnic backgrounds. Over 70% of the total minority ethnic population were Asian: Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi, Chinese or other South Asian. Over 12% of the minority ethnic population described their ethnic group as 'Mixed'. The dispersal of asylum seekers to Glasgow since 2000 and the accession of new countries to the European Union (encouraging movement of citizens within the EU) have underpinned this increase of the minority ethnic population in Scotland and may have increased further since the last Census in 2011.

While a four percent minority ethnic population within Scotland may seem small, the minority ethnic population within Scottish schools is substantially greater. In 2011, there were 670,511 pupils in publicly funded schools. This number had fallen from 673,133 in 2010. Nearly 90% (89.9%, to be precise) of these Scottish pupils were

recorded as being White-Scottish or White-other British in 2011, which means that the other 10% constitute a minority population. The largest other ethnic backgrounds include White-Other (2.9%), Asian Pakistani (1.6%) and Mixed (one per cent).

Increase in Home Languages

Another marker of minority ethnic background can be the home language, i.e. the main language spoken in the pupil's home. As with ethnic background classifications, there is recent data (Scottish Government, 2011) on the home language of pupils. This data identified that there were approximately 24,555 pupils in Scotland using English as an additional language and that 147 different languages were spoken as the main home language, with Polish being second to English, followed by Punjabi and Urdu. These statistics confirmed an increasing diversity of cultures and languages that led me to question whether the teaching workforce reflected this increase or if minority ethnic teachers continued to be underrepresented among a diverse pupil population. This was important to an understanding of how teachers were to respond to this cultural and linguistic diversity. Yet, while diversity in the pupil population was increasing, this was not reflected in teacher populations.

The declining BME teacher population in Scotland

In 2015, only two percent of teachers in Scotland identified as black and minority ethnic, compared with four in the general population. By 2016, (see Table 1) this figure had declined to one percent of the workforce (Scottish Government, 2016). This decline was concerning especially when aligned with the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers in promoted posts, for example, in 2017, there was one minority ethnic head teacher in Scotland (BBC, 2017). While the Scottish Government is considering ways in which teaching can become more representative of Scottish society (Scottish Government, 2018) this decline in numbers of minority ethnic teachers suggested that further research was required to provide information on how to recruit and retain them.

As part of previous attempts to address the issue of teachers deciding to leave the profession (Menter et. al, 2006; Peters, Cowie and Menter, 2017) teaching unions in Scotland have called for action to address this underrepresentation. In response to this, the Scottish Government have launched a new recruitment campaign to attract black and minority ethnic people to consider teaching as a career (Scottish Government, 2018).

Table 1: Teachers by ethnicity and grade, 2016 – percentages

	Percentage of teachers at that grade		
PRIMARY	Promoted post	Teachers and Chartered Teachers	All
White - Scottish	64.3	66.0	65.7
White - Other British Isles or Irish	32.5	25.3	26.7
White - Other	1.3	2.2	2.0
Ethnic minority group	0.4	1.1	1.0
Not Disclosed	1.6	5.4	4.7
All	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Percentage of teachers at that grade		
SECONDARY	Promoted post	Teachers and Chartered Teachers	All
White - Scottish	57.7	58.8	58.5
White - Other British Isles or Irish	36.8	29.2	31.4
White - Other	1.6	4.0	3.3
Ethnic minority group	0.7	2.0	1.7
Not Disclosed	3.2	6.0	5.2
All	100.0	100.0	100.0

The promoted post includes head teachers, depute heads and principal teachers. Ethnic minority group includes: African, Caribbean or Black, Asian - Indian/British/Scottish, Asian - Pakistani/British/Scottish, Asian - Bangladeshi/British/Scottish, Asian - Chinese/British/Scottish, Asian - Other, Mixed or multiple ethnic groups, and Oth

Table 2:

Ethnic minority teachers by grade and sector as a percentage of the teacher workforce, 2016-2020 (Scottish Government) (figures taken from current census)

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Primary	1.0%	1.0%	1.1%	1.2%	1.3%
Secondary	1.6%	1.7%	1.8%	1.9%	2.1%
Special (Additional Support Needs)	1.7%	1.4%	1.9%	1.7%	1.8%

Complexities and Tensions

Whether minority ethnic teachers can bring a unique form of cultural capital with them to class is debateable. In stating that a minority ethnic teacher may have such 'added value,' we may inadvertently imply that the majority ethnic teachers have a deficit. A further point to consider is that some minority ethnic teachers may not (have ever) engage(d) with practices associated with their ethnic heritage (Santoro, 2011). To better understand how minority ethnic teachers use their cultural and linguistic skills in their teaching, Cummins (1996) discusses the process of negotiation that involves important interactions between children and their teachers, in which they discuss and explore different cultures and as such coined the phrase 'negotiation of identities' (p.16). Accordingly, Cummins suggests the need for teachers to engage in the 'sketching of a triangular set of images: an image of our

own identities as teachers; an image of the identity options we highlight for our children and finally an image of the society we hope the children will belong to' (p.16).

This tripartite view of teacher identity is not overtly acknowledged by most educators, minority ethnic or otherwise, and yet this process of negotiation becomes a useful lens through which to discuss and, indeed, interpret teacher and pupil experience. This process should acknowledge and consider situations in which the minority ethnic teacher does not actively or consciously engage with their ethnic identity in pedagogic practices. For example, why would teachers not recognise or use their cultural, linguistic and religious identities to develop a practice which is culturally relevant for all young people in a classroom.

Santoro (2013) carried out further research, which drew on data from two separate studies that investigated the experiences of culturally diverse teachers working in Australian schools. She argued that there were some tensions and complexities with how Indigenous teachers in Australia were positioned as ethnic and racialized teacher subjects making assumptions about their professional identities. Some of the teachers in Santoro's study expressed concerns that not all indigenous teachers are the same and that their experiences will have been different in many ways. They also argued that not all indigenous teachers drew on their cultural and linguistic skills to inform their teaching. This complexity makes it difficult to define the cultural capital of minority ethnic teachers within a classroom context and suggested to me that it should be acknowledged and examined further.

Background to research: my positionality

My current professional role as a teacher educator in Higher Education involves teaching on the BA Childhood Studies, undergraduate and post-graduate Primary Teaching programmes. Prior to becoming a university lecturer, I worked for ten years in various teacher posts in Primary education. As a new practitioner, I gradually

became aware of the important role that teachers can play in acknowledging and nurturing the identities of all learners. As the only Muslim teacher in the school, I felt that this work on belonging was particularly important for children from diverse cultural, religious and linguistic backgrounds.

Reflecting on my primary education in Scotland, I was not encouraged to use my first language, Punjabi, in the classroom. My teacher did not make any reference to my cultural or religious identity. I was made to feel that speaking in Punjabi was 'bad' and I was reprimanded for it. As a result, I did not develop my literacy skills in Punjabi and almost lost the ability to speak the language fluently. Baker (2006) asserts that, when a language is lost, so too, are generations of cultural identities. I did not lose my home language entirely as my parents made a conscious decision that we would communicate in Punjabi at home. However, while I was able to maintain fluency in my home language despite an unsupportive educational system, I quickly learned that the English language had much prestige and power within the classroom and beyond (Kearney, 2003). My teachers throughout Primary and Secondary struggled to pronounce my name, which was then subsequently anglicised to suit them.

My teachers did not really understand my cultural background and nor did they think this was important to learn about. Thus, I decided, at that time, that it was in my best interest to follow the majority ethnic culture of White Scottish pupils and teachers. I began to, what Cline et al (2002), suggest as 'playing white'. To play this game, as I call it, I had to try and fit in. I avoided any conversation around difference, not wishing to see my colour nor speak my first language. I learned that my cultural experiences were of little value in my teaching and the children's learning. Some decades later, my experience as a practitioner was that this important work was still often overlooked and not actively encouraged.

'An image of our own identities as teachers'

Given the central role of self-narrative to any discussion of identity, I feel it is important within this thesis to acknowledge my own narrative and the relevance of this narrative to the present research study. Researching Cummin's (1996) concept of tripartite negotiation of identities helped me to reflect on my own experiences. It aided me to understand that my personal story or self-narrative can be a powerful means through which to investigate and deconstruct social phenomena that I had experienced as a minority ethnic teacher working in a school. Cummins shows the impact of social phenomena and why it is important for all teachers to feel empowered to construct their self-narrative by focusing on one's life stories, we can shape and reshape our experiences to achieve meaning.

Reflecting on how my life history helped me to construct my own identity, I have come to realise that we all have multiple identities: I am a woman, a teacher, and a parent. I am a Scottish Muslim with a Pakistani heritage. Through sharing my story, I am able to organise my experiences and find a sense of self. In a classroom context, my stories have been useful in empowering and equipping children with the skills and knowledge required to negotiate their own cultural, religious and linguistic identities. For example, by introducing different perspectives or by simply explaining why I wear a hijab.

This continued whilst studying initial teacher education, as I sought to assimilate into the majority white, middle-class culture (Cole and Stuart, 2010). I remember my initial apprehensions about how I would be received in predominantly white schools. However, on the whole, my experiences were positive, and I felt supported by the school staff and my tutors at University. During my studies, I chose an optional module entitled 'supporting bilingual learners' in the third year of my teaching degree. Through discussions in this class, I began to think of my own cultural, linguistic and religious identity. Gradually, this awareness led me to consider how, through using my first language, I could support children who had English as an additional language.

As a minority ethnic teacher, I did this by encouraging children to value and use their cultural and linguistic skills in the classroom and recognise that I value the importance of minority ethnic culture and language, in part, because of my own experiences in primary education. Unfortunately, these had often been negative experiences.

A critical incident in my teaching career led me to question my own personal and professional identity and that of other diverse teachers. In my 6th year of teaching, a child who had newly arrived from Pakistan was placed in my class. I felt confident that I would be able to support this child because I spoke the same first language, Urdu. However, this young child refused to speak in her first language and despite my best efforts, did not seem to have a sense of belonging in the class. This led me to reflect on my own practice and come to the realisation that I too had sought to assimilate into the mainstream culture to such an extent that I was unable to engage with this child regardless of a shared ethnic background. This was perhaps, a result of my own experiences as a pupil and student teacher, but I also felt that I was being driven as a teacher to assimilate.

My classroom environment did not show value to different cultures and languages. The wall displays and resources were all in English and reflected the dominant culture. It seemed that, rather than enabling this child to understand her identity, who she was and where she came from, I was transmitting a clear message of the need to assimilate to avoid exclusion. My classroom and my teaching minimised the significance and value of this child's cultural and linguistic experiences. It took me a long time to realise that I was reinforcing a monolingual and mono-cultural value base. When I became aware that this was happening within my own classroom, I also became invested in finding the means by which to reverse this overwhelming dominance of white culture. This led me to foster truly inclusive education by valuing students' and my own minority ethnic background.

My personal experience aligned with the kinds of experiences reported by researchers who have studied minority ethnic teachers more broadly (Ladson-Billings, 2005; Santoro, 2013; Kohli, 2014). Minority ethnic teachers often have a deep knowledge of the issues that pupils currently face and effective skills in mediating diverse learning settings (Bhatti, 1999; Cummins, 2006). Minority ethnic teachers are also aware that their own professional identities, of which language and culture are important features, could be called into question by the wider systems within which they work. Yet, by continuing to assimilate into the majority culture and wanting to fit in they subsume elements of their identity (Kohli, 2014).

My changing understanding of perceptions on ethnicity and difference as a result of this critical incident outlined above deepened my understanding of the flaws in the teaching practices and I began to see myself as part of the change. Instead of being a teacher who perpetuated a problem within school and Initial Teacher Education practices, my teaching approach needed to change. I began to see my own racial background as an important factor in the way that I interacted with both colleagues and pupils. Palmer (1997) asserts

When I [the teacher] do not know myself, I cannot know who my students are....and when I can't see them clearly, I cannot teach them well.

(p.36)

How could I support a minority ethnic child to come to terms with their multiple identities, crossing the borders of their 'parallel worlds' to synthesise into one world, without crossing borders that I had experienced but had suppressed by playing white, in my own teaching world?

Curriculum for Excellence 3-18 (CfE) was introduced in 2004 in Scotland. As is well documented, in comparison to the 5-14 Curriculum (SOED, 1991), CfE is less

prescriptive and offers teachers more flexibility in how they use the guidance offered to support their teaching and the children's learning. Teachers are encouraged to focus on their pedagogical skills and the kinds of structures at work in schools. Perhaps minority ethnic teachers may be better placed to be able to draw upon their own narratives and give more importance to autobiographies within the curriculum and listen to the complex views of their pupils (Conteh et al. 2007; Shain, 2011).

Another critical incident happened in the USA when the World Trade Centre and Pentagon were attacked by Muslim Extremists. This event raised so many questions in people's minds. At that time, I taught a Primary seven class: children of around eleven and twelve years of age. The children in my class held stereotypical representations of Muslims portrayed by the media during the events that unfolded after 9/11. The media is an extremely powerful source for creating and propagating social representations and can have a direct influence on the construction of one's identity (Ahmed and Matthes, 2017). My teaching in class, where a homogenous group of children questioned and quizzed me about negative images of Muslims, was useful in helping to compare perspectives from TV, press and social media with my insights. For example, I asked the class to think about my name, Mrs Mohammed, and whether it indicated which faith I followed. There was initial silence in the classroom followed by a few of the children shouting out, "You are a Muslim!" This realisation led to an interesting dialogue about negative, stereotyping and how this can influence the way people think. Conversations about culture, religion and language offer the potential to encourage people to make informed judgments for themselves and challenge the status quo.

Returning to the tripartite cultural identity in education that Cummins (1996) proffered, the third component is the image of the society that we hope our children will form. I was educated in a society that suppressed minority ethnic culture in the classroom. I began teaching in a system that discouraged diversity. Today, I ask whether the presence of a minority ethnic teacher can make colleagues and children think differently when it comes to issues of race, ethnicity and discrimination.

Thesis outline

This thesis is divided into seven chapters:

Chapter One introduces the background to the research study and provides an overview of the issues regarding a quintessential monocultural teacher workforce in Scotland. There are concerns over the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers since Scottish devolution in 1999. Research in this area continues to show that while the population of minority ethnic pupils is increasing, the numbers of minority ethnic teachers is in decline. There is a lack of empirical research that explores why this underrepresentation continues and this provides the rationale for this study. This raises several questions and suggests that further research is needed to explore the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers.

Chapter Two examines the literature on teacher identity and culturally relevant pedagogy. Research suggests that some minority ethnic teachers choose to utilise their cultural, linguistic and religious skills in their teaching and see this as integral to their personal and professional lives, while others, do not acknowledge these skills within their professional lives. This review raised important questions and highlighted issues that required further research in providing clarity about the experiences of minority ethnic teachers which needed further investigation:

- What are minority ethnic teachers' expectations of being and becoming a teacher?
- How do minority ethnic teachers utilise their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in the classroom?
- What are the enablers as well as the barriers to minority ethnic teachers using their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in the classroom?

- How do they negotiate their personal and professional identities?

Chapter Three outlines the research design for this case study. Firstly, it discusses the philosophical underpinnings of my thesis, which are social constructionism and interpretivism. An explanation of the theoretical framework, Critical Race Theory (CRT), is discussed to show how I arrived at the research questions and how the data were analysed and the findings were produced. Secondly, it outlines the rationale for adopting a case study approach to explore the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland and their perceptions of utilising their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in their teaching. There were three main phases of data collection: Phase 1 included the first focus group of seven minority ethnic teachers to discuss their experiences of teaching. Lessons learned from this phase informed Phase 2 with a further two focus groups conducted. Finally, in Phase 3, individual semi-structured interviews were held to consider the themes arising from the focus groups and discuss in more depth the issues highlighted.

A thematic analysis was used to analyse the data. It also considers the ethical and methodological issues concerning data collection and discusses my sampling strategy on how the participants were selected for this study. Finally, as a minority ethnic, female, teacher educator and former primary teacher, I was aware that my biography would directly affect the fieldwork. Thus, I include a reflexive account of my own positionality as a minority ethnic researcher.

Chapter Four introduces the findings through the first theme; the influence of cultural factors and minority ethnic teachers desire to make a difference. It analyses the views and experiences of minority ethnic teachers in relation to research question 1, what are minority ethnic teachers' expectations of being and becoming a teacher? They discuss their reasons for choosing teaching as a career and examine the influences of culture, family and religion in their decisions around becoming a teacher.

Chapter Five continues to examine research question 1: What are minority ethnic teachers' expectations of being and becoming a teacher? The participants in this study discuss the challenges they faced from recruitment into teacher training programmes and their subsequent employment, highlighting the impact of marginality and othering in their experiences of recruitment, retention and promotion. Using one of the key tenets of critical race theory, the counter-narratives from their personal and professional lives helped to examine their professional status and the power inequities involved in the construction of minority ethnic teachers' identities.

Chapter Six examines the perspectives of minority ethnic teachers concerning their experiences of how they bring their diverse identities into their teaching. This relates to research question 2: How do minority ethnic teachers utilise their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in the classroom? Some of the participants discussed how they can modify their teaching practices to provide a culturally relevant experience to the children they teach. They also highlight the dilemmas they face in terms of agency when using their culture, language and religion to promote anti-racist education. Some participants discussed why they do not use their culture, language and religion as they see this as a barrier to their career progression.

Chapter Seven provides an overview of the analysis chapters to clarify and synthesise the themes outlined. It identifies four key aspects of supporting minority ethnic teachers' professional identity: acknowledgement, affirmation, agency and activism. Through discussion it was shown that these four aspects, when combined, were necessary to support minority ethnic teachers to construct and strengthen their professional identities and enhance the chances for minority ethnic teachers to have a positive experience of being a teacher

Chapter Seven also summarises findings, considers the limitations of the research, draws conclusions, and makes recommendations for future research, policy and

practice. This study offers new contributions to our understanding of the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in negotiating their personal and professional identities. Participants have highlighted the importance of having safe spaces for them to come together to share their experiences. For many who work in isolation, these spaces offer them: a sense of belonging, where they feel part of a community of teachers who face similar challenges; where they offer each other emotional encouragement and support; where they have a shared sense of purpose to constructively, come together to direct their professional growth and contribute to the growth of their colleagues; where they work in solidarity and engage in union activity to bring about change. In short, these spaces offer four main components: acknowledgement, affirmation, agency and activism, which can form a model for systemic change.

This study has had an impact on future policy on the recruitment, retention and promotion of minority ethnic teachers. As a result of this research, I was invited to speak at the Strategic Board of Teacher Education and share my findings. I was also invited to be a member of a Scottish Government, short-term working group on Diversity in the Teaching Profession which led to the publication of a report: Teaching in a diverse Scotland: increasing and retaining minority ethnic teachers. I have co-founded and led as, Chair, of the Scottish Association of Minority Ethnic Educators (SAMEE), a charitable organisation that supports minority ethnic teachers, parents and young people. The impact of this study has seen SAMEE being acknowledged and cited within Scotland's Race Equality Framework: The way forward (Scottish Government, 2016).

Finally, the specific recommendations from this study would be to ensure an effective process to recruit minority ethnic students into Initial Teacher Training institutes; to ensure that student teachers are race cognisant before completing their training and to this end; I was commissioned by the Scottish Council of Deans to develop a National Anti-Racist Framework for ITE. I also worked in partnership with Education Scotland to review and modify current leadership qualifications, which explore the importance of nurturing a diverse staff team. The participants' also spoke about the

importance of programmes that were relevant to their needs and experiences and as such, I have designed a bespoke Leadership and Mentoring programme for minority ethnic educators.

Chapter Two

Literature review

Introduction

This review considers the literature in three key areas. First, it explores the relationship between the personal and professional elements of teachers' identities, experiences, beliefs and practices and the broader social conditions in which teachers live and work. Then consideration of the tensions and conflicts that exist in each of these elements will illuminate their impact on a teacher's professional identity. Finally, the chapter will review research on the experiences of minority ethnic teachers regarding the formation of their professional identities and their perceptions of using their cultural, religious and linguistic identities in practice.

Chapter outline

This chapter examines research literature that underpins the experiences of minority ethnic schoolteachers. This review considers how minority ethnic teachers negotiate their cultural, religious and linguistic identities within professional identities and examines the literature on social and cultural capital as a way that minority ethnic teachers may or may not bring their identities into the classroom context. Reviewing the literature helped to examine how the cultural capital of minority ethnic teachers translated into pedagogic practice, which is culturally relevant for the young people they teach. The review suggested that minority ethnic teachers are viewed in essentially two ways: either their diverse cultural and linguistic identities are not acknowledged, or they are considered to be the 'jack of all trades' and should be there to specifically help minority ethnic children (Santoro, 2006, 2013).

Finally, literature on perceptions of their own teacher identities was explored to identify how teachers created images of themselves as professionals and what influenced the construction of identities. This review suggested that identity is a key

factor in developing a teacher's sense of purpose, commitment and job satisfaction, and so it was important to investigate the factors that influenced them both positively and negatively. The review found that problems of inequality exist regarding minority ethnic teachers' experiences in schools but there was a gap in knowledge and understanding of how this inequity impacted on the development of minority ethnic teachers' professional identity.

The literature review concluded that further research was needed to increase understanding of how minority ethnic teachers develop their role as teachers through negotiating their professional identities in schools. It was important to also examine the potential impact or influence of a white majority ethnic population. This also led to questioning how minority ethnic teachers could be supported in their career recruitment, retention and promotion. In responding to this gap, the review identifies the study aims and objectives

Understanding the relationship between personal and professional identities

Research on how teachers form their professional identities contributes to our understanding and acknowledgement of what it feels like to be a teacher in today's Scottish schools. Where many things are changing, among a diverse range of cultures that populate classrooms, it is important to pay attention to the personal aspect of teachers' professional identity and how they cope with the changes taking place (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004; Akkerman and Meijer, 2011; Hong, Greene and Lowery, 2017). These changes challenge accepted norms within the teaching profession.

An increasingly diverse pupil population may conflict with a particular teacher's personal beliefs and experiences. Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop (2004, p.109) assert:

Such a conflict can lead to friction in teachers' professional identity in cases in which the 'personal' and the 'professional' are too far removed from each other.

This kind of conflict could be present in a situation where a teacher's Roman Catholic faith is directly at odds with a pupil who decides to terminate a pregnancy or who is undergoing a gender reassignment. It could also be challenging when a teacher of a particular political view is required to teach to a curriculum that perpetuates an economic model that does not recognise the impact of poverty on learning and on the pupil's prospects for a good life. In direct relation to this study another example of conflict or friction can be experienced when a teacher who wears a hijab and feels excluded because of her beliefs.

If professional practise is rooted in strong values that seek to ensure fair education for all, this calls into question who decides on what a fair education is. It has been argued that white cultural norms are systematically prescribed and reinforced and can become problematic for minority ethnic teachers to construct their professional identity. This leads to a diminished sense of agency (Slay and Smith, 2010; Kohli, 2014). Agency, in this context, refers to the ability to make choices about one's work practice and to link these choices to personal values and beliefs (Biesta, Priestley and Robinson, 2015). Furthermore, this active shaping of their work is for achieving a good overall quality of education.

It is argued that when forming their professional identities, teachers are influenced by both how they feel about themselves and their students. Kelchterman (1993, p.449) suggests that like the personal self, the professional self evolves over time and he refers to five key areas: Self-image, self-esteem; job-motivation; task description and future perspectives. Self-image and self-esteem, according to Kelchterman (1993), consider how the teachers describe themselves through their career stories, how good or bad they perceive themselves to be as teachers, and also how others perceive them. The third and fourth areas, job-motivation and task description help to

explore how teachers define their work and the reasons why teachers remain committed to their jobs. The fifth area considers the future perspective, exploring teachers' expectations for the future development of their jobs. Therefore, this would suggest that teachers' identities are closely bound with their professional and personal values and aspirations.

However, Kelchterman's (1993) study also highlighted two recurring themes: stability in the job and vulnerability. These themes meant that teachers felt that in order to feel stable they did not challenge the status quo and were vulnerable to the judgement of colleagues. To counteract this, they became passive in their practice, which could suggest low self-image and self-esteem as a teacher. Having reviewed the literature on minority ethnic teachers' experiences in schools, it is possible to suggest that their vulnerability and marginalised positions have an impact on both their self-image and esteem. Minority ethnic teachers have reported that they feel they are being observed and judged by others (colleagues and the children they teach) as not 'real' teachers where white teachers held stereotypical images of South Asian teachers (Bhatti, 1999; Arshad et al, 2005; Mohammed, 2011).

Being perceived as the 'other' prevents most to question their image as teachers. This, too, also appears to have an impact on how motivated the teachers are in their practice, not wanting to 'act' as the jack of all trades or being pigeonholed into a specific category, such as English as an Additional Language (EAL) teacher (Santoro, 2013). The lack of recognition and promotion to senior levels also has implications for their future perspectives with many reported to leave the profession – e.g. where minority ethnic teachers have been striving to progress in their careers and not being successful (Hepburn, 2018). Therefore, Kelchterman's (1993) model of professional identity as it appears is not an appropriate fit for minority ethnic teachers. It does not capture the racialised subtleties and nuances and Kelcherman is writing from a white majority perspective.

Teachers also form their identities through the interaction between their personal experiences and the social, cultural and institutional environment in which they work. Piore and Safford (2006) assert:

It is impossible in today's world to imagine one's career without incorporating one's social context into it ...such aspects of lives as...the social stigma that may attach to one's race, religion, or gender.

(Piore and Salford, 2006 p.319)

Yet, Prasad, D'Abate and Prasad (2007) found that stigmas marginalise individuals by limiting the multifaceted nature of self, leaving them with one dimension to their identity. Moreover, Goffman (1963) defines stigmatised cultural identity where members of a group are assumed to be inferior and therefore having a blemished identity. For example, minority ethnic teachers' cultural, religious and linguistic skills may not be acknowledged and only their 'technical skills' of 'teacher' are considered (Ladson-Billings, 1995, 2005; Kohli, 2014).

Similarly, Slay and Smith (2010) have identified that there is little research on professional identities which examines issues of marginalisation and cultural identity. They examined the experiences of African American journalists in the USA, to discuss what it meant to be black and a journalist. Slay and Smith's (2010) study further develops our understandings of professional identity construction, however, there is no research in Scotland to establish the veracity of this claim and so I have found this useful as it could also be applied to examine the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in the formation of their professional identities – what does it mean to be a visible minority and a teacher in Scotland?

Slay and Smith (2010) suggest that professional roles are defined as prestigious and offer a degree of privilege and autonomy but for those who are stigmatised, little privilege is offered as 'their identities are tainted' (p.85). Moreover, they argue that it is important to consider the implications of stigma on professional identity construction as the process may be different for, or modified by, members of stigmatised groups. Pratt, Rockman and Kauffmann (2006) reported in a study of white medical students the use of performance feedback and role models in validating their professional identity. Yet, such validation can be difficult for minority ethnic teachers who may not be able to find appropriate role models because they are underrepresented in the teaching profession.

For example, Kelchterman's framework for the evolving professional self includes two areas which consider the self-image and self-esteem of teachers. Again, stressing the interrelationship between professional and personal identities. There is further evidence which shows that teaching demands significant personal investment (Day, 2002; Sachs, 2003; Shapiro, 2010; Buchanan, 2015). This investment helps teachers to situate themselves in relation to their students and to make appropriate and effective modifications in their practices and their beliefs about interacting with students.

.....the self is a crucial element in the way teachers themselves
construe the nature of the job.

(Kelchterman and Vandenberghe, 1994, p.47)

Hargreaves (2000) has presented the development of individual professionalism as passing through four historical ages —the 'preprofessional' (managerially demanding but technically simple in terms of pedagogy); the 'autonomous' (marked by a challenge to the uniform view of pedagogy, teacher individualism, and wide areas for discretionary decision taking); 'collegial' (the building of strong collaborative cultures

alongside role expansion, diffusion and intensification); and the 'post-professional' (where teachers struggle to counter centralized curricula, assessment procedures and external surveillance) (p. 153). However, not all teachers move through these stages in the order that Hargreaves presented. Indeed, this will depend upon the individual teacher and his or her experiences. For example, the suggestion that the early pre-professional stage is 'technically simple' in terms of teaching and learning is open to debate.

It can even be argued that this approach could lead to parochial knowledge. Every day practical craft knowledge may also redirect teachers' work away from the broader moral and social projects. If they view pedagogy as such then perhaps they will not be able to make the transition to autonomous learning. This raises questions on whether they will be able to challenge the status quo. Hargreaves (2000) collegial stage suggests the need to build a collaborative culture in schools, but this will only happen when teachers' individual views are respected and acknowledged. In the case of minority ethnic teachers – should they follow the technical tips to fit it into this conceptualisation of 'professionalism'? Should the post-professional outlook not be encouraged from the beginning of a teacher's career to enable new teachers to question and reflect upon practice, e.g. whether certain assessment strategies are relevant to individual children?

Sachs (2003, 2015), proposes a different framework to help understand professional identity. This framework consists of two contrasting forms: the entrepreneurial and the activist. The former emphasises efficiency, responsibility and accountability by teachers demonstrating their compliance to externally imposed policy imperatives. This type of professional identity is controlling in nature and encourages teachers to become competitive and work individually to meet standards set by others. This example of professionalism resonates with assimilatory practices where a minority ethnic teacher may subsume his/her cultural, linguistic and religious skills to fit into the culture of the school structures. Alternatively, the activist professional identity focusses on mobilising teachers in the best interests of student learning and seeks to put in place standards and processes that ensure democratic experiences are

offered (Van den Berg, 2002). This would seem to suggest a more positive outlook for all teachers. This is pertinent to my research on minority ethnic teachers with regards to negotiating their identities and considering who decides what is in the best interests of student learning.

Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop (2004) also identify four features of professional identity which may provide a useful lens to examine minority ethnic teachers' formation of their professional identities. First, they consider professional identity as an on-going process of interpretation and re-interpretation of experiences. This resonates with the idea that teacher development is a life-long process and so it encourages teachers to consider who they are at that moment but also helps them to aspire and evolve in preparation for the future. This perspective implies that professional identity is dynamic and that it does not remain fixed and stable (Britzman 2003; Arends and Phurutse 2009).

Secondly, Beijaard, Meijer and Verloop (2004) offer the notion that professional identity implies both person and context suggesting that a teacher's professional identity is not unique. There is an expectation that teachers behave and think in a professional manner by adopting professional characteristics, knowledge and attitudes that are prescribed. Yet, Beijaard, Meijer and Verloop (2004) assert that teachers will deal with these professional characteristics differently depending on the value they personally attach to them. The third feature is that professional identity consists of sub-identities depending on the context and relationships. This can include sub-identities arising from conflict during a pre-service teacher's initial teacher education training or from changes to an experienced teacher's working environment.

Moreover, Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, (2004) go on to suggest that these sub-identities need to be well balanced so that no such conflict should arise. Lastly, the feature of the agency is offered where teachers must be active in the process of professional development. Agency is defined as the means by which teachers have

the capacity to act by actively negotiating and renegotiating the conditions and the contents of their own work (Priestly, 2011). Moreover, Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop include agency as one of the four features of the professional identity framework they developed and stress that teachers are required to learn individually as well as in collaboration with other colleagues. It is further argued that this would inevitably have an impact on the teachers' commitment to their profession. This is in line with a constructionist view where learning is developed both individually as well as in collaboration with others. Moreover, professional identity is not something teachers have as something to do rather it is something they can draw on or use in order to make sense of themselves as teachers (Beijaard and Meijer, 2017 as cited in Clandinin and Husu, 2017).

The idea that teachers' personal experiences have an impact on their professional lives has been developed further. Alsup (2006: xii) coined the term 'borderland discourse', which, she argues, can enable the 'integration or negotiation of personal and professional selves.' Teachers would be involved in integrating their personal beliefs/lived histories or in Alsup's words 'personal pedagogy' with their professional expectations. This mixing and merging of the personal and professional selves or as termed as sub- identities by Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, (2004) provide opportunities for dialogue and perhaps moments to reflect on possible collisions or conflicts between and across themselves. Alsup (2006) further asserts that teachers need to find a 'space' where they can consider their identities and argues that 'often this space is in the so-called borderland between identity positions or situated discourse' (2006, p.7). I felt this would be interesting to explore through my research where minority ethnic teachers would have opportunities to construct an image of their own identities by engaging in dialogue about their past experiences.

This review of literature on professional identity construction suggests that self-concepts or views are shaped in essentially three ways: firstly, they are the result of a socialisation process where one learns about the norms associated with a particular profession. Secondly, when individuals are going through a transition in

their careers then they modify and adapt their professional identity. Finally, having identified key priorities and a sound understanding of self both life and work experiences impact on professional identity construction. Having considered these perspectives, the definition I will use in this study to describe professional identity is one's professional self-concept based on attributes, beliefs, values and experiences.

Professional Identity - Minority Ethnic Teachers'

Whilst this body of research adds information on the study of identity construction:

...conspicuous in its absences is the voice of minority professionals who often face stigma and discrimination as they enter career fields.

(Slay and Smith, 2011, p. 87)

Little research has been undertaken on professional identity construction within the context of stereotyped or complex cultural identities where:

Members of a group are assumed to be tainted or inferior, resulting in a blemished identity that prevents easy inclusion in society.

(Slay and Smith, 2011, p.86).

In order to investigate the construction of professional identity of minoritised groups, Prasad et al. (2007) advocate a 'narrative' mode which provides description and details of past histories that may offer some insight into the process. Slay and Smith

(2010) offer a model of professional identity construction for minority ethnic groups which may provide some insight into the construction of minority ethnic teachers' professional identities. They first consider how early influences of family and cultural values and professional experiences inform the possible professional self. Then, rather than using terms such as 'adapt' or 'modify' they discuss redefinition tasks including redefining professional identity; redefining the profession; redefining stigma, and redefining self.

This redefining process may offer some insight into the construction of minority ethnic teachers' professional identities and suggests questions that it would be useful for me to research such as: What does it mean to be a minority ethnic person? Is there conflict or integration between the two identities and if so, how does this influence personal and professional identity? There may be several reasons to expect the process of professional identity construction to be different for minority ethnic teachers. For example, racism and discrimination may limit opportunities essential to consider the powerful discourses that prevail around race and inequality.

Vähäsantanen et al.(2008) interviewed 24 Finnish teachers to investigate their perceptions and experiences of negotiating their professional identities in two different school structures. The two structures differed in the space they allowed for teacher agency and the management culture: one was loosely controlled by the organisational culture while the other tightly controlled teachers work practices. Both offered constraints and possibilities in helping teachers to negotiate their professional identities in terms of their abilities as active agents and their commitment to their work organisation. Vähäsantanen et al.(2008) found that where management structures were 'tightly controlled' teachers had restricted opportunities to practise agency and little time to consider their own perceptions of what was important in their work and the tasks which were meaningful. On the other hand, the loose management structure gave more freedom for the teachers to consider their personal values and interests in their work and thus increased their commitment to their work organisation (Baruch and Cohen, 2007).

Thus, with respect to professional identity, the tightly controlled work organisation appeared inappropriate to ethos where professional identity is regarded as an on-going process (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004; Sachs, 2015; Hong, Day and Greene, 2017)). Too much prescription reduces any opportunities for the teachers to interpret and reinterpret their experiences and sits in opposition to the notion that teacher development never stops. The teachers selected for interview in Vähäsantanen et al.'s study (2008) varied in age, subjects taught, length of service and work history overall which would indicate that diverse teaching experiences and different value bases should be explored further.

Moreover, the formation of professional identity implies the recognition that all teachers differ in the way they operate within their practice depending on the values they personally attach to the different aspects of their role and the situations within which they are placed. However, it is not clear how this applied to the two separate institutes used in the study by Vähäsantanen et al. (2008). It could be that the teachers from the tightly controlled institute may be young teachers and as Hargreaves (2000) would suggest they are at their pre-professional age whereby they place importance to the technical aspect of the job and deliver accordingly. The more experienced teachers may be operating autonomously, challenging a uniform view of pedagogy. There was one aspect which proved to be problematic for the institute with the loosely structured organisation. The interviews revealed that teachers tended not to share their experiences and knowledge, therefore creating poor communities of practice within the organisation.

Another study steered a multiliteracies project which aimed to investigate the ways in which teachers' own cultural and linguistic experiences can provide a basis for understanding the knowledge their students bring with them to school (Cummins and Early, 2011). Giampapa and Sandhu (2011) provide a short vignette that described a two-year case study around identity texts. At first, the teachers involved explored their own linguistic and cultural experiences which aimed to inform their teaching.

They then shared their experiences with the students in their classrooms to foster a whole class discussion. This helped to raise students' awareness of the value of different languages and cultural experiences. Parminder, a Sikh Class Teacher, encouraged her students to work collaboratively with their peers and parents to create dual-language stories and carefully selected the pairings in terms of their literacy abilities in their first language and English. Each student was involved in creating visual texts which represented the words they wanted to use. The students gained so much from this experience and the project was extended to creating dual language texts. Giampapa and Sandhu (2011) cite Parminder's ideas as transformative pedagogy which was

...fuelled by her own multiple identities and the politics around her self-positioning as a Black woman and a member of a cultural and religious minority group.

(p.86)

Giampapa and Sandhu (2011) argued that a central part of Parminder's teacher identity was to empower her students to feel valued. Indeed, this is another positive example of responsive teaching and learning.

The review of literature so far has considered examples of the integral nature of teachers' personal and professional identities. In the majority of the studies considered, the teachers were comfortable and willing to tailor their teaching styles in response to their students' needs. However, there is little research on the professional identity construction of people from diverse ethnic backgrounds. Accordingly, minority ethnic teachers, perhaps because of their own experiences of schooling, do not regard their cultural and linguistic identities as capital or as having value. Despite this lack of research, there is a body of work on race which examines how race and ethnicity influence the career experiences of minorities. Thus, it could be that they have constructed a professional identity that remains quite different from

their personal identity. In line with the idea of improvisation as a means of transformative pedagogy, it felt like it would be useful to investigate minority ethnic teachers' perceptions within the context of their personal and professional experiences.

Critical race theory

There is a need to challenge and change the structures of power relations that influence the organisation of schooling, most often, are defined by the dominant group as essential (Arshad, Wrigley and Pratt. 2012). However, a search for studies exploring this topic in Scotland revealed a gap in the literature on minority ethnic teachers experiences of identity, power and agency. Given the ways that power is used subtly to disadvantage minority ethnic groups, teachers need to reflect on their professional roles and responsibilities concerning equality and fairness and develop their capacities to create change as necessary, at the institutional and classroom level, to promote equity and diversity (Kohli, 2014; Matias and Grosland, 2016). For example, power can be explored through the theme of white privilege, which obscures the actions or decisions taken by policymakers, and can be described as happening without the knowledge of whites (Gillborn, 2008).

Critical Race Theorists (hooks, 1994; Ladson-Billings, 1995; Leonardo, 2002, 2004; Gillborn, 2008;) argue this is in line with critical race theory (CRT) as it offers a systematic and insightful framework for understanding and opposing race equity in education. Its defining element is in its understanding of 'racism'. CRT argues that society views racism as an ordinary fact of daily life and that the assumptions of White superiority are so ingrained in political, legal and educational structures that they fail to recognise the inequalities (Delgado, 1995).

Anti-racism efforts have gained momentum and visibility over the years, however, as Gillborn (2008, p.14) has argued, in 'The absence of a clear conceptual map' work carried in the name of anti-racism is often, 'a meaningless slogan that is evacuated

from all critical content' (Gillborn, (2008, p.14). There is a need for critical scholarship that will address racialised inequalities in practice, and it is within this context that critical race theory (CRT) may help to lead the way ahead. CRT is an approach that began in US law schools but has spread to education, social sciences and other areas (Ladson-Billings, 2010). CRT offers a systematic and insightful framework for understanding and opposing race inequity in education. Its defining element is in its understanding of 'racism'.

Critical race theorists use the term 'racism' to look at both the obvious acts of race hatred and the more subtle ways that power disadvantages minority ethnic groups (Gillborn, 2008; Ladson-Billings, 2010). In other words, it is not only acts of violence against minority ethnic individuals that constitute race hatred, but also subtle covert acts of discrimination – for example, giving preference to a particular style of speech and decorum of a majoritised and privileged community or utilising the social capital of the dominant group (Yosso, 2005; Warmington, 2012).

CRT scholars have been criticised for taking a dismissive stance on the achievements to date, of the civil rights movement in the USA. However, Crenshaw et. al. (1995, p.xiv) are quick to acknowledge that while their 'inspiration and sense of direction' is rooted within the civil rights movement, the focus of CRT lies in the interpretation of racism. CRT's critique of civil rights law is that it deals well with overt racism but that it can do little with 'business-as-usual' forms of racism that minority ethnic people face every day (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001, p.xvi)

CRT's radical approach reflects the long history of the antiracist struggle and it seeks to examine institutional racism more broadly. CRT scholars hold critical perspectives that aim to shed light on the racist inequities that exist beneath the rhetoric of policy debates. CRT Scholars consider racism to be a central feature of contemporary society but argue that this notion of 'race' has been misunderstood. Delgado and Stefancic assert:

The 'social construction' thesis holds that race and races are products of social thought and relations. Not objective, inherent, or fixed, they correspond to no biological or generic reality; rather, races are categories that society invents, manipulates, or retires when convenient.

(Delgado and Stefancic, 2001, p.7)

The notion that race has no biological meaning chimes with perspectives held within the social sciences (Mason, 2000). Gillborn (2008) argues that race is not fixed and that it is continually shifting and constructed through peoples lived experiences and the critics of CRT need to engage with this notion of 'social race' (p.28).

There have been some critical responses against CRT from more orthodox Marxist writers that feel it deflects attention away from class but Crenshaw (1989 cited in Gillborn, 2008) views race and class as being inextricably linked. Additionally, she asserts that being a minority or being poor, controls one's opportunities in life and these two forms of oppression also intersect with other forms of oppression such as gender and culture. CRT scholars have re-defined racism as the structural conventions and customs that uphold and sustain oppressive group relationships, status, income and educational attainment rather than the acts of individuals (Taylor, 2009).

CRT scholars have a number of conceptual and methodological tools which they refer to as 'basic insights': critical white studies; narrative storytelling, and interest convergence (Delgado & Stefancic, 2000). It is important to consider each of these concepts as they link directly with the research enquiry reported in this thesis in terms of existing power relations.

Critical white studies

Terminology can be problematic when exploring Critical white studies. To avoid any misrepresentation, it is important to state clear definitions at the outset. Leonardo (2002) provides us with a definition of 'whiteness' and 'white people':

Whiteness is a racial discourse, whereas the category 'white people' represents a socially constructed identity, usually based on skin colour.

(Leonardo. 2002, p.31).

Much has been written on whiteness across the disciplines and CRT in education is evolving. For example, Tate and Ladson-Billings (1995) published their paper "Towards a critical race theory in Education" and since then articles and conference presentations have addressed issues such as class, immigration and the racial achievement gap (Delgado, 1995; Gillborn, 2008; Taylor, Gillborn and Ladson-Billings, 2008).

Whiteness theory is intended to make white cultural and political assumptions and privileges visible so that white people do not assume that their position as normal (Leonardo, 2002; Gloria-Ladson Billings, 2010; Sleeter, 2016) It is important to note that whiteness is recognisably different from mainstream multiculturalism. Arguably, multiculturalism usually seeks to foster an appreciation of cultures other than the dominant culture and encourages integration and assimilation; in its more radical forms, multiculturalism also involves problematizing the assumptions of the dominant culture but does not extend to concentrate on how white power operates to foster and maintain white privilege (Leonardo, 2002; Yosso, 2005; Gillborn, 2008).

Whiteness theory focuses specifically on whiteness as a political and cultural *position* — a position and an identity that, to a considerable extent, is gained at the expense of people of ‘colour’ (Bell, 1992). This racial discourse around whiteness is not an assault on white people but rather an attack on the socially constructed and reinforced power of white identity and interests (Ladson-Billings & Tate, 1995).

Gillborn (2009) states that whiteness is not necessarily reinforced by ‘white people’ any more than ‘heterosexual people are *necessarily* homophobic, or men are *necessarily* sexist’ (p.54). He further asserts that white people can help to deconstruct this notion of whiteness, but that such ‘race traitors’ are rare. Tatum (1992) also refers to white allies, colleagues who support their black colleagues in raising equity issues and asserts that such allies also need allies to support each other in their fight against cultural and institutional racism. This suggests that more research is needed to offer those allies evidence on which to make their case and this study can go some way towards offering such evidence.

Drawing from the work of Roediger (1991) and Frankenberg (1993), Leonardo (2000) highlights some of the key characteristics of whiteness. He makes reference to ‘[a]n unwillingness to name the contours of racism,’ where the inequity in education, employment and wealth is not attributed to the acts of whiteness, but rather other factors are alluded to (p.32). The concept of ‘Othering’ is another key feature of whiteness where white becomes the norm from which other racial groups stand apart. Moreover, the “minimisation of racist legacy” as another key characteristic where the struggles of the past should remain firmly in the past and not feature in historic, economic and cultural factors is also discussed (Leonardo, 2000, 2013).

Any study of whiteness must include a rigorous examination of white supremacy. The two processes are related – the conditions of white supremacy make white privilege possible (Leonardo and Zembylas, 2013). Racial privilege is the notion that white subjects accrue advantages by virtue of being constructed as whites, and Peggy McIntosh (1992) states:

I have come to see white privilege as an invisible package of unearned assets that I can count on cashing in each day, but about which I was 'meant' to remain oblivious.

(McIntosh, 1992, p.291)

This has clear parallels to the notion of cultural capital as put forward by Bourdieu (1985), with whiteness being the ultimate form of cultural capital and one that, unlike language or etiquette (etc.) cannot be learned or acquired. Scheurich (1997) as cited in Leonardo (2009) also provides an interesting analogy that sums up race privilege. He described being white as akin to walking down the street with money being put into your pocket without your knowledge. This, by virtue of race, white people enjoy advantages in their daily life that they are not consciously aware of and are often, in fact, oblivious to this privilege.

Leonardo (2004) argues that this 'theme of privilege obscures the subject of domination, or the agents of action, because the situation is described as happening without the knowledge of whites' (p.38). In relation to this research, whiteness theory is particularly important for teachers when constructing an image of their own identities. It may be problematic for minority ethnic teachers to construct their professional identity when white cultural norms are systematically enforced in the schools (usually without any recognition that there are white norms). A teacher who can deconstruct his or her own whiteness is arguably better positioned to understand

why prevailing pedagogical and curricular patterns might not work for children than one who is not conscious of whiteness. A commitment to multiculturalism, without recognising white culture domination, may well get in the way of white teachers' good intentions vis-a-vis minority ethnic students and their fellow BME colleagues.

Storytelling, narrative, autobiography and parable

CRT scholars make use of fictional characters to debate issues and provide examples of the problems faced by the world. Taylor (2009) asserts that 'whites', unknowingly benefit politically, economically and educationally. He refers to their ignorance of the racist past and their lack of exposure to the viewpoints of minoritised people. The purpose of the narrative serves to redirect the views of the majority and to expose what was there all along. Debates, conversations and imagined episodes, can help challenge underlying assumptions and myths, shifting the debate towards a sense of reality that reflects the experiences of the minority (Gillborn, 2008). Ladson-Billings (2006, p.xi) argues that these narratives are not simply entertainment but that they are referenced to depict the truth:

CRT scholars are not making up stories – they are constructing narratives out of the historical, socio-cultural and political realities of the world and those of people of color [sic].

However, Farber and Sherry (1997) criticise the use of storytelling and argue for standards already established in legal scholarship. Scholarship in this context refers to the narratives that are reliant on case studies and the standards determining the validity of the stories. They argue that stories in themselves teach little unless supported by an analysis and commentary. Delgado (2009) responds to Farber and Sherry by suggesting that they are thinking of stories that are limited to just a personal account of the author's experience and that most CRT's narratives, do

indeed, include statistics, and analysis to ensure rigour and that the stand-alone narratives referred to by Farber and Sherry are rare.

If teachers are sketching images of their own identities, then it is important to consider narratives shaped around their lived experiences. Hosltein and Gubrium (2000) refer to the place of self-narrative in the process of identity formation. They argue that our lives only achieve meaning as stories, life histories, self-narratives or autobiographies. Through telling stories, we are able to organise our experiences and provide children with the opportunity to listen to the stories and in turn, this process teaches them how to tell stories.

Bell's (1980) theory of interest convergence refers to the phenomenon of Whites allowing Black people to progress whilst also promoting their own interests. Taylor (2009) asserts that Whites will only encourage racial equality or advances if they promote their self-interest. This concept is rooted in Marxist theory, where the relationship between the social classes was based upon exploitation and conflict. Two main social classes were distinguished: the Bourgeoisie and the proletariat where class membership depended upon ownership (Bourgeoisie) or non-ownership (Proletariat) of the means of production. The two social classes depended upon each other as a source of employment or as a source of profit.

This distinction is also played out in the relationship between white and minority ethnic people, where the dominant white group has the power and privilege to use their Black colleagues' cultural assets to benefit themselves too. However, Warmington (2012) warns of the danger where such collaborations further white colleagues perceive that they will have a direct advantage if they continue to exclude and oppress minority ethnic colleagues. This is evident in many workforces, particularly in education, where Black leaders are severely underrepresented (Scottish Government, 2017).

Critical race theory and education

There is little agreement on how race impacts teaching and learning and Taylor (2009) asserts:

We are hobbled by the paradox of a largely white teaching staff whose practices, consciously or not, contribute to the racial achievement gap yet who are unable to see what they are doing.

(Taylor, 2009, p.9)

In her paper, *American Scholar*, Gloria Ladson-Billings (1998) also poses the question ‘...what is Critical Race Theory and what’s it doing in a nice field like education?’ To me, CRT facilitates a process of racial analysis that can be used to deepen our understanding of the barriers for minority ethnic teachers in performing their professional identities without being disadvantaged. The narrative and storytelling serve as a pedagogical tool that enables teachers to explore their own identities.

In an ethnographic study of teachers of African and American students who were from both majority ethnic and minority ethnic groups, Ladson-Billings (1995) observed a white teacher working with African American boys. This teacher noticed that the participants held a great deal of social power and expressed that this power may be utilised in a negative way to influence their peers. The teacher took advantage of this by transforming some of the social power into academic power – she focussed on issues, which were relevant and meaningful to the boys, such as using lyrics of rap songs. She paid a detail of attention to the skills the boys brought to the setting. The teacher also encouraged the students to talk openly about their own cultural practices and share narratives of their lived experiences. This opened a

way for the students to discuss the racism they experience and bring to the fore discussions around social injustice. It is not clear why this teacher held preconceived ideas that African American boys will abuse power in a negative way but Taylor (2009) asserts that this may be the normal assumption that 'white privilege' affords. In this sense, although there was evidence of culturally relevant teaching taking place, it could be argued that it is important for teachers to deconstruct their own identities and assumptions before they can truly begin to understand their students' cultures.

Another teacher in Ladson-Billings's (1995) study was an African American woman who had experience in working in both public and private schools, having entered the teaching profession after bringing up her own family. Bringing some of their life experiences into the classroom, she was able to support her students in learning about poetry. As the mother of a teenage son, she was familiar with the type of rap music that young African American youth listen to and used this in her classroom. She encouraged her students to bring in lyrics and they decided together which ones would be more suitable to use. The students were allowed opportunities to perform these rap songs and the lyrics were used to teach the technical and figurative aspects of poetry. The students were reported to have exceeded in their academic success and as such the teacher's practice was recognised as a good example of how academic achievement and cultural competence can be combined.

Ladson-Billings (1995) argued that although at first, she could not see any patterns in the teaching practices of the participants in her study – some operated on rigid, more structured activities while others were quite flexible yet, information obtained from interviews and subsequent discussions groups, revealed information that went beyond just simply looking at teaching strategies. Rather, it was the 'philosophical and ideological underpinnings of their practice' and how they structured the social relations inside and outside of the classroom that helped to develop cultural connections (1995, p.162). It can be argued that these teachers were not dependent on state curriculum frameworks and textbooks but were open to a more critical analysis of the content. This also resonates with Cummins's (1996, 2000) identity

options, an image of our own identities as teachers; an image of the identity options we highlight for our children and finally an image of the society we hope the children will belong to. For example, how the teachers viewed themselves as teachers and how they thought about their students, parents and other members of the community.

However, it would not be appropriate to make generalisations about student success based on the teachers' adoption of a culturally relevant pedagogy. Ladson-Billings (1995) selected teachers who were identified by the African American parents to be exceptional teachers because they showed respect to their pupils and were perceived to be teachers that understood the need for 'students to operate in the dual worlds of their home community and the white community' (p.162). These teachers were also recommended by the school Principal using criteria based on test scores, discipline referrals and attendance. Yet, all of these criteria could be affected by several reasons, elements of familiarity and favouritism or if the group of students in that particular year group were cognitively more advanced than the other groups. Thus, it is difficult to claim the specific impact of culturally relevant pedagogy.

Ladson-Billings acknowledges that this kind of study is required to be replicated again and again to find out more about the classroom practices of successful teachers for African Americans and other students. She argued that more research was needed to consider the impact of teacher identity on teaching, and the possible impact of teaching intercultural education on teacher identity. This call for more research has thus been important in helping to clarify the need for a study which examines teachers' personal and professional identities.

Accordingly, Leeman and Radstake (2010) offer an interesting analysis about teaching in Dutch classrooms which aspired towards promoting social justice. Intercultural education was the Netherlands' response to dealing with new immigrants. Set in the context of a strict political climate on immigration and the issue of multiculturalism, the focus over the last few years was to assimilate immigrant pupils into the mainstream culture. Leeman and Radstake (2010) carried out research among eleven secondary school teachers to find out the intercultural dilemmas they experienced in their mixed classrooms and how their responses helped to assess their professionalism. The teachers selected were required to have at least five years' experience of working in ethnically heterogeneous classes as they would more likely have more experience with intercultural dilemmas. Of the eleven teachers, two were from minority ethnic groups, one Moroccan and one of Moluccan origin. The teachers of Dutch origin tended to be restricted by the structure of the school and although they displayed an active interest in supporting diversity, they tended to make generalisations and not see the students as individuals.

The findings suggested that teachers were concerned about the balance between commonality and diversity in their classrooms and they did see the differences but emphasised the similarities more. The teacher of Moroccan origin expressed his concern that the Moroccan children did not trust their Dutch teachers. All participants interviewed were described as pupil-orientated teachers who upheld the standards of their profession. In terms of developing their own professional identities, the teachers did what seemed to have made some movement in thinking about how they should support the minority ethnic children in their care. However, as Hargreaves (2000) would advocate, they are required to move from the autonomous professional stage to the collegial stage by building strong collaborative cultures among their colleagues and community.

This was interesting in Putnam's (2000) bridging social capital theory. Putnam suggests that reciprocity should be promoted and would perhaps go some way to encourage both teachers and students to engage in the kind of important interactions

advocated by Cummins (1996) in which they explore different cultures. Consideration of CRT is therefore necessary as there was evidence according to the Moroccan students to suggest that they do not have a sense of belonging. The teachers faced the 'business-as-usual' forms of racism, for example, and so challenged the coercive relations of power by empowering the Moroccan students to question the status quo.

Indeed, Slay and Smith's (2011) redefinition model could perhaps offer some insight as they suggest that redefining stigma could have positive connotations. For example, in their study, black journalists began to redefine stigma in positive terms by reporting on 'Black' stories as the White reporters refused to cover such stories. This gave the black reporters a voice and a sense of empowerment. In Leeman and Radstake study (2010) the Moroccan and Moluccan teachers could enact their careers in ways that would counteract existing stereotypes and see their racial and cultural identity as offering a unique perspective to their practice. The Moroccan and Moluccan teachers could perhaps find ways to achieve a balance between their ethnic identities and teacher identities.

Moreover, this issue of empowerment was explained in Shain's (2003) ethnographic study of Asian school girls where teacher-student relations were instrumental in influencing their attitudes towards education. The girls felt that the minority ethnic teachers were more sympathetic to their needs because of shared ethnicity. Participants had also commented that minority ethnic teachers could provide positive role models and could help challenge some of the stereotypical views held by the white teachers regarding arranged marriages. One particular student went on to assert that 'Asian' teachers who dressed in a traditional manner enabled Asian students to 'feel like more yourself'. (2003, p.116). A few of the girls, on the other hand, referred to minority ethnic teachers as 'not real teachers' and commented that they are 'the only the ones who teach Urdu that's it' (2003, p.94). Again, this highlighted a need for more research to better understand the complexities associated with minority ethnic teachers' identities.

There were also positive points to note about the presence of minority ethnic teachers and their ability to tune in to the students. In line with Ladson-Billings's (1995, 2014, 2016) concept of culturally relevant pedagogy, when 'Asian' teachers engage in the process of sketching their own identities they may be better placed to empower and equip the students with the skills required to negotiate their own cultural, religious and linguistic identities (Shain, 2003). Some of the minority ethnic teachers in Shain's (2003) study were characterised by their failure to teach and control the class. This may suggest that they are not considered to be up to the job and that some of the girls did not see them as positive role models. Perhaps something could be gleaned from Kelchterman's stages of the evolving professional in terms of finding out about how the teachers describe themselves through their career stories and how good or bad they consider themselves to be and also how others perceive them to be.

The self-image and self-esteem of the Asian teachers in Shain's study were found to be affected by the school structures and the value or lack of status given to them as members of staff. CRT research has re-defined racism in terms of structural conventions and customs that uphold and sustain oppressive group relationships and status may provide some important insights and offer solutions in the context of assumed white superiority that are so ingrained in educational structures that teachers fail to recognise the inequalities. (Delgado, 1995, Rollock, 2011).

Indeed, Pearce (2005) investigates these assumptions of white superiority further and tell the story of her journey as a white teacher beginning to understand how her own racial background influenced the way she perceived the Muslim children in her class and the way she taught them. Over time she began to question the national curriculum and the problems it created for the children. The school structures were also an issue and conveyed messages to the children about what was accepted. Concerned by this experience, Pearce began to record reflections in a diary over a five-year-period. Reflecting on this diary helped her to realise, at times, that her

interactions with the children did not often include their cultural experiences. Over time, Pearce became more aware of her white background and the barriers that came with it.

Pearce's reflections affirmed views held by CRT scholars that whiteness is a social construct which influences the way white people see the world. As Gillborn (2008) asserts, the Whiteness theory is intended to make White cultural and political assumptions and privileges visible so that White people do not assume that their own position is normal. In this sense, Pearce could be described as going through Helms's (1990) six-stage model of white racial identity development. Her diary reflections helped to move her from a stage where she rarely describes herself as white to a stage where she began to see how much her life and the lives of minority ethnics have been affected by racism in society.

Pearce began to feel uncomfortable and showed a desire to 'do' something about the racism, she was increasingly aware of and move on to the reintegration stage as she began to question and turn the gaze to herself and develop her understanding of race and racism so that she became more racially aware. Taking this position, Pearce was able to challenge her own implicit biases. This had led her to make the initial assumptions affirmed earlier about the lives of the minority ethnic pupils she was teaching (Pearce, 2014). Although this is only one teacher's journey in understanding her own racial identity and how it affects the way she interacts with the children. It showed how using diaries was a useful way of researching one's own practice. In turn, this can lead to individual empowerment but of course, such methods are not able to be generalised on a wider level.

In another study that analysed the nature and content of knowledge that enabled black professors to promote learning for black students, Mitchell (2010) considered a cultural aesthetic of improvisation. To illustrate this concept, he makes reference to popular culture and blues music and asserts '...art reflects the experiences of the artist' (2010, p.624). The examples he provides are of the Blues singer "Bo Diddley"

and of the African American streetball player “Rayfer”. Mitchell argues that they display the rich experiences of ‘black folks’ in America. Mitchell (2010) states that:

The numerous allusions to popular culture (jazz, hip-hop, Streetball, etc.) and specifically the blues... are an attempt to highlight elements of improvisation as an aesthetic in everyday discourses rooted in the experiences of the Black community.

(Mitchell, 2010, p.77)

Coker (1964) also advocates this concept of improvisation as an aesthetic and asserts that:

Improvisation is a meaningful concept for teaching because it inherently highlights the ability of learners to abstract from one set of examples to broader questions.

(1964, p.2)

So for example, understanding the ways African American’s lives have been affected by racism and then the discourse which followed allowed the students to explore the forces behind it. This aligned with Mitchell (2010) who reported on observations of a Black professor teaching a group of first-year law students about criminal law. This work was planned on the basis that the students would most likely be of the belief that the law is neutral and race, gender, religion and such like, remain impartial to the legal system. Yet, he saw this view as problematic and wanted to challenge their thinking by using the questions ‘driving while Black’. He stated that this was a term introduced to refer to the high number of Black people being stopped and searched by the police.

The observed black professor spoke about his intentions to use issues of race to unpick the notion of neutrality and had no idea that the African American students in his class had experienced racial profiling. He planned to use articles and other texts to challenge the idea of neutrality, but he also commented that their very presence and their willingness to discuss their own experiences helped to illustrate the ideas in ways that he perhaps could not have planned. This suggested that there was an element of 'intuition' present and in turn that the professor 'improvised' during the class, as his preparation did not involve him in 'negotiating' his identity with that of his African American students in advance of his teaching. However, an important question to consider is: What would he have done if the students were not willing or comfortable enough to share their experiences?

This very notion of intuitively knowing and improvising enhances the teaching and learning process then perhaps, minority ethnic teachers would be well placed to recognise and utilise such moments because of their own lived experiences. Mitchell (2010) went on to highlight the Black professor's ability to improvise and use the lived experiences of his students to enhance the learning for all students. The Black professor was also able to capitalise on the experiences of his African American students and to articulate his European American students a more nuanced understanding of the inequities that exist within legal systems. This argument would be considered to be in line with a CRT scholar's perspective of white supremacy - as the students were likely to be unaware of the privileges that being White affords them as they go about their lives every day. The European American students would also be able to acknowledge that the minority ethnic students bring with them an understanding of the majority culture that is important for the learning of all students. These conversations were not easy to have as it was almost three years after this research in 2013, when an international social movement called Black Lives Matter (BLM) was formed in the United States. This movement was dedicated to fighting institutional racism and anti-Black violence, especially in the form of police brutality. The name Black Lives Matter signals condemnation of the unjust killings of Black people by police (Black people are far

more likely to be killed by police in the United States than white people) and the demand that society value the lives and humanity of Black people as much as it values the lives and humanity of white people.

The findings of Mitchell's research highlighted three main points that were aligned with my research interests. Firstly, that the concept of 'improvisation' was identified as helpful to enhance the learning for African American students which I thought might be aligned with my interest in examining teachers' use of everyday examples to explore wider questions on culture, race and identity. Secondly, that improvisation is grounded in their collective histories and their ontological experiences of being black in America and so may resonate with my research in a different Scottish context. Lastly, that tuning into ideas linked to these improvisations will form the core of good practice and so I wondered whether this good practice was evident in Scotland.

Mitchell (2010) acknowledges that this good practise is not new (Gay, 2000; Shulman, 2004; Ladson-Billings, 2014) and that it will enhance learning for all students however, Mitchell's study considered the learning experiences and opportunities of the African American students on having Black professors. Mitchell's data was drawn from observations, focus groups and follow-up interviews of Black professors who were interested in working with Black students. Although this observation demonstrates an example of culturally responsive practice, the selection process could be critiqued as it raises the question of whether Mitchell would arrive at the same conclusions if he had observed Black professors who did not necessarily show a particular interest in working with African American students. They may have worked hard from an assimilationist perspective and could have regarded their role as simply to deliver the content of their subject knowledge. Nonetheless this suggested to me that a study to examine minority ethnic teachers' perceptions about their personal and professional selves would be useful in helping to better understand the extent to which they feel that their cultural and linguistic skills contribute to their professional identities as teachers.

Minority ethnic teachers' - perceptions of using their cultural, religious and linguistic identities in their practices in other parts of the world

Australia has a diverse student population and has similar issues of underrepresentation as Scotland, with regards to teacher ethnicity. Santoro and Reid (2006) carried out a four- year study to understand the experiences of indigenous teachers. The study also highlights the under-representation of indigenous teachers and teachers of ethnic backgrounds. They examined the career paths of indigenous teachers in Australia to reach an understanding of their lived experiences and identify trends in recruiting and retaining indigenous teachers in the profession. They found that the school and the wider community view the indigenous teacher as 'all things to all people' (Santoro and Reid, 2006, p.287) with responsibility for connecting with indigenous young people and their families and supporting their white colleagues, and this has resulted in many of them leaving the profession. It may be problematic for minority ethnic teachers to construct their professional identity when white cultural norms are systematically enforced in the schools (usually without any recognition that they are white norms).

Critical Race Theory and Professional Identity

As stated earlier in the review, Kelchterman's (1993) suggestion that the professional self evolves over time and the five stages he advocates can perhaps shed some light on this issue. Considering their identity options and exploring their own lived experiences may help minority ethnic teachers to define the kind of teachers they want to become. This process would also allow them to consider their role within the school and raises questions of how they will highlight the identity options for the students in their care and that of their colleagues or if a strong self-image could enhance self-esteem and perhaps give them the courage to begin to challenge the structures that impact on teacher identity.

If we are to encourage minority ethnic teachers to sketch an image of their own identities as teachers, then there needs to be an exploration of how teachers construct their professional identities. What shapes them into the kind of teacher they are or perhaps the kind of teacher they want to become? Having considered the above theoretical contributions it appears that the power of narrative storytelling, in trying to explore the teaching lives of minority ethnic teachers is effective. Connelly and Clandinnin (1999) discuss the power of teacher narrative to express identity within what they call 'a changing professional knowledge landscape' (p.120). The stories teachers tell can help them to express their multiple identities (Beauchamp and Thomas, 2009). This is why I decided to use this as part of a constructo -interpretive framework, based on the personal and professional self-narrative to interrogate the influences of ethnicity, culture, education, professional status and power inequities in the construction of minority ethnic teacher identity.

The theoretical perspectives provide a conceptual framework within which to discuss the minority ethnic teacher in the classroom, which is a topic that seems to be infrequently confronted in Scotland. Despite the controversial nature, this topic deserves attention, but too often is reduced to anti-racist platitudes and/or a failure to engage meaningfully in important discussions that need to be developed. The absence of this discussion makes it unsurprising that the 2011 review of Initial Teacher Education in Scotland mentions the word "ethnic" only three times in 116 pages (Donaldson, 2011, p.23) – remarking upon the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers but not recommending any substantive measures to increase their numbers.

Further, Gillborn (2008, p. 14) argues that anti-racism has been 'reduced to a meaningless slogan' due to its failure to address the inequities of the powerful forces that operate at a societal level. Gillborn calls for an interrogation of our conceptual history and theoretical frameworks and leads one to question the dominant systems that remain in education and so maintain the rhetoric of educational policymakers

Alternatively, looking through the lens of critical race theory, this illustrates well that by virtue of their race, the white hegemonic mainstream enjoys advantages in their daily life and highlights that they are oblivious to this privilege. Santoro and Reid (2006) refer to a statement made by an indigenous teacher:

...If there's anything Aboriginal that's been planned you have to do it and the expectations from all the other staff is that you **will** do it just because you're Aboriginal.

(Reid, 2006, p.293)

This appears to suggest that the white teachers in the schools remain oblivious to the cultural and linguistic needs of their students and that it is somebody else's job to make these links. A teacher who can deconstruct his or her own whiteness is far better positioned to see why prevailing pedagogical and curricular patterns might not work for children. Ladson-Billings (2005) argues that minority ethnic teachers will be able to function as role models and inform the whole school community in supporting diversity.

Santoro and Reid's (2006) study also highlighted that teachers from diverse cultural backgrounds can contribute effectively to all students through establishing cross-cultural links. However, they do raise concerns with regards to how the indigenous teachers feel they are viewed in the wider educational community. Are they just there to fill in the gaps? They also found that some indigenous teachers felt that they did not know enough about their own culture and so would not be in a position to share this with their pupils or colleagues.

This lack of knowledge could point to two issues. Firstly, where minority ethnic students are not allowed to have their diverse identities acknowledged, nurtured and

celebrated and are encouraged to assimilate into the majority culture, they will be less likely to enter discussions about their ethnicity and culture. Secondly, as Kohli (2014) has pointed out, these types of experiences can lead to internalised racism. Kohli (2014) undertook research where she gathered the views of minority ethnic student teachers on their experiences of racism. In-depth interviews and focus groups revealed that, where their experiences of racism were left unchecked by their teachers and unacknowledged, they began a process of 'internalised racism':

A concept that explains when people of colour consciously or unconsciously accept a racial hierarchy.... Having internalised racism has many consequences for young people of color. It can impact their self-esteem...their perception of their family or community or their performance in school.

(Kohli, 2014, p.3)

Hence, this could lead to minority ethnic students, unknowingly, replicating the racial hierarchies and choose not to engage in any activity that is out with the majority culture.

Moreover, Basit and Santoro (2011) alert us to the concerns regarding minority ethnic teachers being hailed as 'cultural experts' (p.48). This halo places extra demands on the teachers in terms of being viewed as role models, who will support and guide their colleagues in all things to do with ethnicity. The Australian indigenous teachers who were interviewed commented on feeling burdened and demotivated and consequently, their commitment beginning to diminish because they felt that they were unable to plan for their career development.

With regards to Kelchterman's framework, the indigenous teachers' professional identity might fail to evolve as their self-esteem might be affected by their lack of

motivation due to the extra burden placed upon them as cultural experts. On the other hand, the British NQTs interviewed seemed to have a more positive outlook and were keen to be used as 'cultural experts' as they felt valued through their contributions. However, the early career minority ethnic teachers may be driven by the desire to please colleagues and feel that it is their role to fill the gaps regarding the needs of the minority ethnic children. It is argued that given time, they may feel the pressure of this responsibility and so respond differently. Challenging the power relations is also a difficult notion for NQTs and if the message is being conveyed that it is their responsibility to deal with all things that are 'ethnic' then they may not question it.

Santoro and Reid (2006) go further to suggest that indigenous students are failing in the school system because of the underrepresentation of indigenous teachers and that it is difficult for the white hegemonic mainstream to engage in any real interactions with their indigenous students. Teachers from ethnic minorities should enjoy the same status as their white colleagues. However, research has shown that these teachers continue to experience structural inequality and to overcome this they are constantly striving to work hard and enhance their qualifications (Bhatti, 1999; Shain, 2003; Valenta, 2009).

Santoro and Reid's study (2006) also argued that the burden of being a cultural expert could become too much to bear and so therefore, minority ethnic teachers find it easier to assimilate and not make use of their cultural assets. The very people who can support the whole school community in acknowledging diversity will not be prepared to enter into a negotiation of their own and their pupils' cultural and linguistic identities. (Cummins and Early, 2011; Flintoff and Dowling, 2017). Consequently, minority ethnic teachers find themselves representing their respective communities (Santoro, 2016). This further suggests the need to examine their views on how this success and responsibility might be achieved. The idea of representing their communities requires examination to better understand the perspectives of minority ethnic children and their views on their learning experiences when being taught by minority ethnic teachers.

Similarly, Bhatti (1999) also refers to the fact that teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds face more problems than their majority ethnic colleagues. She studied the perspectives of the few Asian teachers who taught in the school and they, too, felt undervalued and not regarded as 'proper' teachers. It is important to consider the organisation of the school and how it values all members of staff. When minority ethnic colleagues are not perceived as having something valuable to offer, might this be reflected in the interactions between staff?

In 2005, a Scottish Executive study on the experiences of minority ethnic pupils of schools in Scotland (MEPESS) found that 'white' teachers were more likely not to notice the difference in terms of ethnicity, culture, language and religion as they err on treating all children the same expecting minority ethnic pupils to assimilate (Arshad et al, 2005). However, a few minority ethnic teachers were interviewed, and they commented on the importance of acknowledging the difference, particularly in terms of culture, language and religion. Treating everyone the same may be considered positive and things would be better if differences were irrelevant. However, it is important that the acknowledgement and examination of differences can lead to better life chances for the pupils (Gaine, 2005; Flintoff and Dowling, 2017) I argue that it is equally important to take this approach when considering minority ethnic teachers. We need to notice ethnicity and diversity rather than pretend they are not there or are assimilated into the mainstream culture. To ignore these issues and hope everything will be all right is a rather naïve view.

Valenta's (2009) research on bilingual teachers' (mother-tongue teachers for those students who did not have Norwegian as first language) experiences in Norway found that to achieve a higher status, some bilingual teachers were being encouraged to further their qualifications into mainstream subject teaching. However, Valenta (2009) found that this is leading to some bilingual teachers entering the mainstream with the new qualifications, but they are then choosing to ignore their linguistic and cultural expertise, as they feel that these skills are not

valued (Valenta, 2009). This process, which can be viewed as compelling the teachers to assimilate into the majority culture could lead to negative consequences on their sense of belonging as minority ethnic teachers.

Indeed, Valenta's (2009) concern was that if bilingual teachers continued to experience structural inequality, then they might take up the offer of furthering their qualifications in order to seek access into the mainstream teaching jobs. This would have a double effect; firstly, there would be fewer teachers teaching these specialised subjects than are fundamentally required in order to develop the children's cultural and linguistic identities; secondly, the teachers who move on to mainstream teaching could find themselves subsuming to the majority culture to attain to a higher status. This helps to identify another gap in the literature – there is little research on minority ethnic teachers striving to achieve a higher status and secure promoted posts: in Scotland, there is only one minority ethnic Head Teacher (BBC, 2016) and this raised a question about the recruitment, retention and promotion of minority ethnic teachers.

Minority ethnic children's views on being taught by minority ethnic teachers

Cummins (2000) states that young children need to understand how their identities are shaped and they need time to explore what they think, what they see and how they behave, as a result of their own experiences. Indeed, this exploration will give rise to many contradictions and through this process they are able to reshape aspects of themselves (Kearney, 2003). Moreover, schools need to create an environment that will support this process. Again, there is little research on minority ethnic children's perceptions of their teachers. In Scotland, a longitudinal study gathered data capturing the experiences of minority ethnic children's experiences of schools in Scotland (SEED, 2005). In England, some ethnographic studies were undertaken. Bhatti (1999) explored Asian children at home and at school focusing on how a child interacts with his peers, teachers and parents and Shain (2005) researched the identity and schooling of Asian girls. Both studies highlight that

children from minority ethnic communities negotiate their way through their primary years between home and school and it is through these interactions that they begin to make sense of their world.

In the MEPESS Study (2005), some of the minority ethnic pupils commented on the fact that there were very few minority ethnic teachers. The gist of their conversations was:

I think it would be nice to have teachers who are more mixed; they might understand you better.

(Arshad et. al., 2005, p.77)

This sends out a powerful message that minority ethnic children feel that it is important for them to have a sense of belonging and that the presence of minority ethnic teachers should go some way towards achieving that. In Bhatti's (1999, p.179) research the pupils described their Asian teachers as being 'caring and helpful' but the most frequent words they used to describe their teachers was 'good' and 'bad'. The teachers who held stereotypical views with regards to minority ethnic children were classed as 'bad'. The pupils also made comments with regards to the negative treatment of minority ethnic teachers by some white colleagues. Bhatti's research also raised an important question of whether they would even consider teaching as a profession if this is the way they would be treated. Much work is required to promote teaching as a good and fair profession to enter and we can only do this if young children can see more teachers from the ethnic minorities in their schools enjoying the same equal status as their White colleagues.

Moreover, Shain's (2003) ethnographic study of Asian school girls found that some of the girls expressed a need for 'Asian' teachers but when, according to the girls who participated in this study, the Asian teachers failed to meet their expectations,

the girls accused them of letting go of their ethnic roots. They were said to be taking sides with their White monolingual colleagues. It is also interesting to note that some of the girls expressed little desire to see more Asian teachers in their school. Two students challenged the competence levels of the Asian teachers and went further to say that they only teach subjects like Urdu. The implication that they are not up to the job not only reinforces the marginal status of minority ethnic teachers but also the status of the subjects that they teach. Indeed, this raises a question about which language gets preference, the European languages, French, Spanish and German? Is it certain bilingualism more valued than Urdu? This arguably highlights the potential impact of assimilationist policies whereby minority ethnic teachers feel they have to subsume their cultural and linguistic identities and 'bought' into the majority culture.

It would be interesting however, to trace, and reflect on majority ethnic teachers' own experiences of education to discover if they were educated and trained in the United Kingdom? If so, were their cultural and linguistic identities recognised and valued in their schooling and training within initial teacher education (ITE). This could mean that ITE institutes could be considered as inadvertently encouraging assimilation into the dominant culture and that white teacher educators remain oblivious to the assumptions being made regarding their relationships and communications with minority ethnic student teachers (Bartolo et.al, 2009). The circle continues unbroken in encouraging assimilation into the majority culture.

Initial teacher education and minority ethnic students

Indeed, it then becomes necessary to consider how all Initial Teacher Education (ITE) institutions prepare student teachers to develop their evolving professional identities. These institutions are mainly populated with White teacher educators and White, middle-class, monolingual female students who will have the responsibility of

teaching in schools serving children who are culturally, linguistically and racially different from themselves (Beijaard and Meijer, 2017).

According to Lander (2011) research on white student teachers who were preparing to teach in a secondary school in a diverse society draws on critical race theory as a theoretical framework to analyse how the students' ethnicity influenced their perceptions on issues related to race. The main strands linked to the theoretical framework and relating to teacher education included findings that confirmed that white student teachers do not see themselves as racialised and are unaware of the privilege they hold because of their ethnicity. This was small-scale research which employed a constructionist epistemology to examine how white student teachers engaged with issues of race equality given their own background and experiences.

Lander (2011) conducted eight unstructured interviews with postgraduate students, who were preparing to teach in secondary schools. As a minority ethnic teacher educator, her own personal concerns on the potential to influence the interpretations of the findings were examined. For ethical reasons in order to avoid the issue of power relations (from a methodological stand), she chose to work with students for whom she had no responsibility. Findings revealed that they required some form of a checklist of 'differences' and one student commented 'we need to know about their culture, their language etc.' (Lander, 2011, p.356). This approach tends to reinforce the 'them and us' culture which can lead to many children 'playing white' – not wanting to appear different and thus assimilating into the majority culture. This was compounded as students showed, as Lander describes, 'dysconscious racism' where children are not seen as a minority and become invisible (p.358). Students' inability to act in challenging racism was also found on placement. This resonates with Cummins's (2006) framework on coercive relations of power where the macro-levels of interaction in terms of educational structures are outlined. Research participants were not able to challenge the institutional racism in school and therefore coercive relations of power remained or were reinforced.

Aveling (2007) adopts a quantitative approach to explore some of the issues touched on by Lander (2011). Data for this paper was taken from 257 students teachers' responses to an examination that was held at the end of their second trimester to assess their understanding of social justice. A productive pedagogy framework was used because the focus was quite specific on what quality teaching might look like. This framework is concerned with education for social justice and provides a lens through which educators can see their teaching practices. The findings were grouped according to whether students demonstrated 'clear understanding', 'some understanding', or 'limited or no understanding' of the issues and concepts of social justice.

Aveling (2007) found a range of responses and recognised that examinations cannot adequately demonstrate the range of student learning, but suggested that:

What examinations can do is point the way to re-conceptualise our teaching to create more effective and meaningful learning...

(Aveling, 2007, p.3)

Although Aveling's approach included offering feedback on the students' understanding of some of the questions, it was not possible to comment on any specific issues arising from individual exam scripts. Also, statistical information on percentage pass rates fails to illustrate the students' perceptions and attitudes. Aveling concludes that the White teachers in her study were ill-prepared to respond to the needs of minority ethnic young people.

Aveling's and Lander's studies considered the majority ethnic student teachers' view about diversity and social justice. Both reveal that white students do not seem fully prepared to deal with the needs of children from diverse cultural and linguistic

backgrounds. Nor do they seem confident to challenge the status quo when faced with issues around social justice and equity (Aveling, 2007; Lander, 2011). If students are being left frustrated and unable to deal with issues of race equality this raised a question for me about the content of ITE courses and also emphasised a need to move beyond the technical skills-based standards under which they seem to operate. Santoro (2009) also asserts a need for pre-service teachers to consider their personal identities before they can begin to understand their students. Santoro explored how eight, monolingual pre-service teachers from the dominant culture constructed their own identities. These were informed in terms of their social class, their ethnicity and their ability to interact with students who came from diverse socio-economic and cultural backgrounds. Santoro acknowledges that it would be inappropriate to make generalisations about all pre-service students.

However, the data gathered from focus group interviews revealed some interesting points which warrant further discussion. Not only did the pre-service teachers show a basic understanding of their students' cultural backgrounds they also had little understanding of their own identities and how these are shaped by their ethnicities. This would suggest that teacher educators require to engage students effectively in understanding self through identity construction and learning about the multiple repertoires to one's identity and how this is intimately linked to their professional selves (Beauchamp and Thomas, 2009).

In a study of the experiences of British Asian and Black overseas student teachers in South-East England research was funded by the Teacher Training Agency (TTA) in South-East England. This research arose out of concern from a group of teacher educators about schools showing characteristics of racism and how this affected student teachers from British Asian Black and other minority ethnic groups (Cole and Stuart, 2005). Concerns were rooted in their work as teacher educators and in particular in the supervision of school placements. Their observations suggested that their minority ethnic student teachers face racist, cultural and linguistic barriers that make their educational experience problematic resulting in students failing or dropping out of teacher training programmes.

British, Asian, Black and Overseas students who were undertaking a one-year postgraduate course leading to Qualified Teacher Status were chosen from three different teacher training institutes, A, B and C. Accessing the target group was reported to be problematic for several reasons. Institutes A and B followed data protection law and provided a list showing the numbers enrolled by ethnic group – this raised the issue that not all students indicate their ethnicity on registration forms because they do not wish to identify themselves in this way. Some were already out on placements and were under pressure with work. One black student from Institute C was interviewed and said that ‘his British identity was more important than his colour’ (Cole and Stuart, 2005, p.355).

Semi-structured interviews revealed three key distinguishing factors: the types of programmes the students were following. In England there are many routes into teaching:

- The country of origin and education
- The cultural differences between the student teachers’ own schooling (and/or teacher education)
- Practices with their school placements.

The students from Institute C felt racism had not been an issue for them and one student from Institute B reported that they experienced some racism in the form of name-calling and that where there were overt racist remarks, staff dealt strictly with the individual concerned. Students from Institute B reported that covert racism existed everywhere and three of the interviewees stated

...you hear them say things as you pass, or making animal noises, but nothing is done about it.

(Cole and Stuart, p.357)

Unexpectedly the students from Institute C did not report any issues but this could be a direct result of assimilation or, as Cline et al (2002) would argue, a result of children growing up 'playing white' and not acknowledging the differences. Some of the students were disappointed that the schools did not see them as being able to offer 'benefits' to the school in terms of developing the school curriculum. There could be two possible explanations for this. The schools perhaps did not 'see' the cultural and linguistic skills of the minority ethnic student teachers and perhaps focused more on the technical aspects of teacher professionalism as outlined by Hargreaves's (2000) pre-professional stage. On the other hand, perhaps the schools had little experience of minority ethnic people and were unsure or even afraid of recognising the differences for fear of being perceived as politically incorrect. Cole and Stuart (2005) argued that the student teachers' responses reveal the embedded nature of Whiteness within Initial Teacher Education institutes and their colour-blind practices.

Lander (2011) asserts that:

..it is not until we question the neutral white position promoted by ITE policy and practice that we will begin to make a real difference to how student teachers perceive themselves in relation to their BME pupils and their positions as educators in a multiracial society.

(p.362).

This shows that for teacher educators to consider how they position themselves in terms of ethnicity, culture and social class. This point is further reinforced by Bartolo et. al, (2009) who present two 'diversity challenges' for teacher educators. Firstly, to encourage teacher educators to acknowledge the cultural, linguistic and religious skills the students bring with them and secondly for teacher educators to help their student teachers to work competently in diverse schools by examining their own attitudes and reflecting on their cultural experiences.

Summary

The review of this literature has highlighted several issues regarding the importance of having a teaching workforce that reflects the community at large. Ladson-Billings (2005) asserts that increasing the diverse representation of minority ethnic teachers will not simply be able to 'fix' things for the minority ethnic pupils but that the focus should be on

...creating a more diverse teaching workforce...to ensure all students, including white students, experience a more accurate picture of what it means to live and work in a multicultural and democratic society.

(Ladson-Billings, 2005,p.231)

The literature has highlighted case studies which consider the positive impact of majority ethnic teachers using culturally responsive pedagogical practices (Ladson-Billings, 1995; Shain, 2003; Leeman and Radstake, 2006; Mitchell, 2010). Overall the literature examined the minority ethnic teachers' own perceptions of utilising their cultural and linguistic skills as well as being recognised as professional teachers in their own right. These studies examined were at secondary and tertiary levels of education with little at the primary level. This highlighted important issues which need further investigation. We have found that some minority ethnic teachers disengage their personal identity from their professional identity because they feel they will be disadvantaged otherwise. It can be argued that there are three different orientations.

First, there are minority ethnic teachers who are clearly interested in engaging with issues around race and diversity and will tailor their practice accordingly. Secondly, there are minority ethnic teachers who may well be interested but are put off because they feel that they are left to deal with all issues regarding race and

diversity and/or feel that their cultural and linguistic skills are of no value, so they choose or are compelled to assimilate into the majority culture.

Thirdly, there are minority ethnic teachers who state that wrong assumptions and expectations were held about their cultural experiences and felt that although they can be identified as a minority ethnic group, they perhaps, as a result of their lived experiences, do not have an awareness of the culture themselves and so teach in line with the majority culture (Shain, 2003; Santoro and Reid, 2006; Santoro, 2016; Flintoff and Dowling, 2017).

The minority ethnic children's perceptions of minority ethnic teachers also fell into three categories: some spoke about the benefits of having minority ethnic teachers and how their presence gave them status; others argued that there are those who are present but follow the 'party line' and do not draw links with their cultural and linguistic backgrounds at all, and there were those who did not consider ethnic minority teachers to be 'proper' teachers. This raises four questions which warrant further exploration:

- What are minority ethnic teachers' expectations of being and becoming a teacher?
- How do minority ethnic teachers use their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in the classroom?
- What are the enablers as well as the barriers to minority ethnic teachers utilising their cultural, religious and linguistic skills in the classroom?
- How do minority ethnic teachers negotiate their professional identity

Chapter Three

Research design

This chapter will consider the ontological and epistemological perspectives that have underpinned and informed the development of my research design and my analysis of research findings. It will also consider the methodological questions in terms of how the research was conducted and methods used or why some methods were rejected. It also explains how the data was analysed and finally, addresses ethical considerations.

Ontological perspective

Ontology is concerned with the truth and seeks to question 'what is the nature of reality?' (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005, p.33). Guba (1990, p.17) describes a paradigm as 'a basic set of beliefs that guide action' and similarly, Denzin and Lincoln (2005) describe this by relating it to the way it frames the research and how it influences the way we think about the topic. Kumar (2014) suggests that the two main paradigms that have influenced research are the objective (positivist, quantitative) paradigm and the subjective (interpretivist, qualitative) paradigm. Objectivism is the belief that reality exists independently of social actors and their perceptions and that generalisations help to seek solutions for society as a whole (Kumar, 2014).

Constructionism views reality as subjective and internal to the social actors. Ideas are generated and constructed by and through human interaction, where 'reality is socially constructed' (Merten, 1998, p.11). People interact with each other to construct and reconstruct new understandings of the social world. This includes a range of multiple realities that are impacted by, for example, culture or history (Denscombe, 2010). This means that it may be useful to examine the role perspectives, perceptions and experiences of minority ethnic teachers play in

constructing their reality. As reality is socially constructed by people interacting with each other, this ontological position calls into question assumptions about the world by taking a critical view of common-sense understandings (Burr, 2003).

Constructionist research seeks to understand those interactions between people and how social realities are constructed, and as such, was part of my thinking about how knowledge might be claimed in this study.

Constructivism ontology also views social actors as the builders of their external realities but the focus is more on the individual as the main agent in constructing their reality. An individual's ideas and feelings are an important part of the knowledge process, too (Creswell, 2003). This study sought to understand minority ethnic teachers' lives and analyse how the teachers' ethnicity, culture and language place them within school-related issues. It interviewed minority ethnic teachers to gather alternative views that, according to participants in this study, helped them to construct and reconstruct their worldview. In this sense, they were able to adjust and expand their current view and so, could be regarded as social actors in constructing their own realities. Thus, a constructivist ontology offered a good fit for this study.

Minority ethnic teachers discussing their lived experiences and the perceptions they held about their own teaching whilst trying to consider the wider social context within which they worked also involved challenging stereotypical representations and discrimination that they face in developing their professional identities as teachers. Thus, it would appear that both the constructivist and constructionist ontological perspectives view reality as constructed and constantly reconstructed through external and internal processes respectively.

...constructivism is primarily an individualistic understanding of the constructionist position...social constructivism emphasises the hold our culture has on us: it shapes the way we see things (even the way we feel things!) and gives us quite a definite view of the world.

(Crotty, 1998, p.58)

Each gains existence and form through the construction of the other. Ackermann (2001) asserts 'knowledge is not merely a commodity to be transmitted, encoded, retained and re-applied, but a personal experience to be constructed.' (p.8). This informed my decision that both constructionist and constructivist assumptions could be applied to this study.

Epistemology

Epistemology is a philosophy that seeks to investigate how we understand reality. It considers the truthfulness and validity of this knowledge and how can it be applied to social phenomena, for example, a study that adopts a close and personal approach to the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers. Each of the epistemological paradigms has a place in social enquiry – the positivist approach, typically, sees the world objectively where behaviours are controlled and measured scientifically and are devoid of the researcher's epistemological stance. Whereas the interpretivists (Merten, 1998; Opie, 2004; Denscombe, 2010) believe that knowledge is everywhere and is socially constructed and that all knowledge is valuable and valid. This leads to multiple interpretations which can consider the researcher's epistemological position. Crotty (2003) argues that these differences are unjustifiable and misleading as such, distinctions suggest that quantitative methods are associated with research which is objective in nature and that qualitative methods focus on constructivist, interpretive research.

This is consistent with Brymen (1998) who argues that all research is interpretive in that it can only offer an interpretation – so, although quantitative data is typically associated with a positivist approach there is no reason why an interpretive study could not utilise statistics when researching about people. The key distinction in how

the data is analysed which links to the epistemological position of the researcher (Thomas, 2013).

In a study about the professional identities of minority ethnic teachers, a positivist epistemology could focus on statistics and employ a questionnaire with ranking scales to measure their attitudes and perceptions of how their cultural and linguistic skills are utilised. This would tend to treat knowledge as objective, verifiable and replicable. However, whilst this may be a useful starting point, I decided against a positivist approach as it would not offer the kind of in-depth understanding of the more subtle nuances of what is available through human interaction. Thus, I sought an approach that could gather data through meeting minority ethnic teachers and providing them with the opportunity and space to share their experiences of teaching in schools.

Interpretivism is offered as an alternative epistemology that sees the social world as 'constructed and interpreted by people – rather than something that exists objectively' (Denscombe, 2010, p. 121). In this sense, the reality is shaped by people and knowledge is being co-constructed using the different forms of capital within a social network of people. An interpretive epistemology could be applied to explore minority ethnic teachers' perspectives on constructing their professional identities and so offered a reasonable epistemology for this study, as it could tap into the space where minority ethnic teachers are constructing and negotiating knowledge. The focus of this study is not merely about seeking minority ethnic teachers' views to offer explanations of why things happen, it is about exploring how they are able to make sense, relate to and understand each other's experiences to challenge the inequalities they experience in the profession.

Thus, taking an interpretative epistemological stance could be used to enhance understanding of how minority ethnic teachers construct a professional identity and whether this is different to their personal identity. As it was the perceptions, feelings and opinions of the minority ethnic teachers that were important in this study, I

adopted a qualitative case study approach. Creswell (1998) described qualitative research as an approach to enquiry that 'builds a complex, holistic picture' (p.15). This was relevant to my study as it was important that the methodology needed to attempt to create an account of these experiences that reflected the context in which minority ethnic teachers teach. A qualitative methodology does this by allowing the topic of the research to be explored in depth.

The constructionist perspectives appear to run parallel with studies exploring the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in that the literature showed a focus on the individual, as someone who was learning about themselves and their identities, but who was also part of a social group, seeking to challenge stereotypical views and acting together to shape their version of reality (Ladson-Billings, 1995; Gaine, 2005; Kearney, 2003, Lander, 2011). In this sense, both constructionist and constructivist ontological assumptions could usefully be applied in this study. Consequently, any knowledge claims made in this study would be from a constructionist, constructivist, and interpretive stance. Gormally and Coburn (2013) have coined the term 'constructo-interpretivist' epistemology to represent this fusion of paradigms.

The overarching strategy adopted is referred to as the methodological approach and the methods refer to the specific tools that are used to collect and analyse data (Cohen et. al., 2000). Sikes and Goodson (2003) offer a cautionary statement to researchers that it would be entirely misleading to suggest that only one particular methodology will suit. There are different ways to view the world and make sense of social phenomena. Consequently, I needed to consider different theoretical and philosophical positions in order to determine the best fit for this study. It is important to note, however, that since different methods and processes yield different results, many varied and valid interpretations could be made.

Therefore, as a researcher, I needed to provide a clear rationale to justify my chosen methodology and the processes I would follow to ensure academic rigour.

Deciding on the research methodology

It is important that the methodology selected is a good match for the focus of the study. I needed to be convinced that the methodology taken is best suited to understand the experiences of minority ethnic teachers (Grix, 2004). Methodology acknowledges different ways of seeing the world and the different understandings about how knowledge is acquired: what is already there? How does this knowledge interrelate and what does this tell me about the gaps in the literature that are missing? Edwards (2001) offers a cautionary statement about qualitative research in that it is not to be viewed as a soft option. She asserts:

...all qualitative research will involve the researcher in 'getting to grips' with the complexities of the social world ...

(2001, p.117).

Kumar (2005, p.20) emphasises the importance of conceptualising a research design, one which involves 'systematic, controlled, valid and rigorous exploration and descriptions of what is known'. Therefore, identifying gaps in knowledge, verifying what is already known and considering past limitations is essential and what is more, the importance associated to what you find rests on how you found it.

Denzin and Lincoln (2011) offer two approaches to find answers to the research questions set: a structured approach and an unstructured approach. Quantitative research is classified as a structured approach which provides a measure of how people think, feel or behave in a certain way and uses statistical analysis to determine the results. A quantitative approach focusses on gathering facts that are measured and compared with other evidence offering causal explanations, generalisability and the ability to deduce relationships between variables (Punch,

2009). The emphasis here is to ensure clarity of procedure to allow other researchers to replicate and thus validate the study.

In contrast, Creswell (2013) classifies the unstructured approach as qualitative research. This is an in-depth exploration of what people think, feel or do and, crucially, why. Where a researcher wants to know why people behave as they do and what barriers there may be to their changing that behaviour, qualitative research would be used to explore those issues. Qualitative research often rests on constructivist interpretivist paradigms where the concern is given to the perceptions of the participants and as such, examines emerging themes and patterns through analysis of the data collected enabling the researcher to narrate and make sense of the experiences of participants (Silverman, 2011). The methods that are applied within this approach are those that are open-ended, including ethnography, case study, life histories and interviewing as they encourage in-depth and detailed information to be gathered. Research of this nature contributes to new understandings and theorising as it illustrates how things are or come to be in the current context (Robson, 2002).

Moreover, Creswell and Poth (2018) build on evolving definitions of qualitative research by Denzin and Lincoln (2000, 2005, 2011) which refer to approaches that are interpretive, naturalistic and ones that try to make sense of meanings. Essentially, they acknowledge that earlier definitions refer to the impact qualitative research has on making a difference in the world. The definition they embrace still includes some of the key elements proffered by Denzin and Lincoln (2011) but has a focus on research design and approaches to inquiry and as such, submit this definition:

‘Qualitative research begins with assumptions and the use of interpretive/theoretical frameworks that inform the study of research problems addressing the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human

problem. To study this problem, qualitative researchers use an emerging qualitative approach to inquiry, the collection of data in a natural setting sensitive to the people and places under study, and data analysis that is both inductive and educative and establishes pattern or themes. The final written report or presentation includes the voices of participants, the reflexivity of the researcher, a complex description and interpretation of the problem, and its contribution to the literature or a call for change.

(Creswell, 2013, p.44)

A qualitative methodology suited my study because I wanted to explore the experiences of minority ethnic teachers to learn from their lived experiences and perspectives, giving voice to any concerns they shared about constructing their professional identities within a dominant culture. I wanted to reflect minority ethnic teachers' views as closely as possible as they often find themselves invisible in policy and practice (Kohli, 2014). However, I also recognised, as Creswell (2013) highlights, the reflexivity of the researcher, that I could draw on my position as a minority ethnic teacher and researcher.

The rigour of qualitative research is held to question in terms of reliability and replicability, and this is often due to the small-scale nature of the research (Sumner, 2006). However, qualitative research is well suited to critical perspectives such as feminism and critical race theory as they aim to challenge the powerful discourses and assumptions that are entrenched in political and structural institutions. For example, Kohli's (2014) research applied a critical race theory lens to examine the professional experiences of teachers of colour in urban schools in America revealing the hostile racial climates that persist.

The tenets of CRT not only demand, that research validates the racialised realities of participants but also benefit them by co-constructing meaning with them. Kohli

refers to 'reciprocal vulnerability' where she shares her position as a minority ethnic researcher who has experienced racism. Moreover, she argues that this helped the participants to develop trust around vulnerable issues of marginalisation and oppression and states:

...while there may be some limitations to being connected to the phenomenon being studied, it seemed to serve as a strength during data collection.

(Kohli, 2014, p.373)

Similarly, using a feminist framework, Ali (2015) explains the methodical challenge she faced during a study on women's experiences of empowerment and change in Northern Pakistan. She argued that she was able to draw balance from both engaging with her identity as a Pakistani woman and researcher to gain an in-depth understanding of the intimate experiences of the participants and this helped the interpretation of empowerment from their narratives.

Choosing a Qualitative Methodology for my study

Creswell and Poth (2018) state that your choice of methodology is likely to reflect the researcher's biographical position and the knowledge and training acquired through education. I considered three methodologies to assist in deciding which was best suited to this study: Ethnography, Phenomenology and Case Study. This section explains each of these and outlines my reasons for rejecting or accepting them for my study.

Ethnography

As this study sought to examine how minority ethnic teachers construct their identities and how they negotiate these identities within the context of their personal and professional lived experiences, an ethnographic approach was considered.

Walford (2008) asserts that ethnography is a strategy which is 'well-suited' to learning and teaching issues. There is special attention given to the way the people being studied see their world. This is key to the aims of this study as some of the minority ethnic teachers may view the social world differently from their majority ethnic colleagues. To understand the values and meanings of any individual or group of people, it is necessary to take account of their 'cultural context' (p.7). Importance is given to how minority ethnic teachers self-identify and how the teachers being studied understand things, the meanings they attach to happenings and the way they perceive reality.

I considered an ethnographic approach to the study as it would require me to spend time in the field, allowing me to share in the lives of the minority ethnic teachers rather than observe from a position of detachment. This extended time would facilitate my following a trajectory in which explanations would emerge from what was being observed. Indeed, making connections with the social and cultural situations within the school could lead to a more holistic picture and thus avoid generalisations arising from isolated incidents (Flick, 2009).

Denscombe (2005) asserts that the ethnographer does not merely describe the account but rather co-constructs it, implying that the ethnographer's own experiences will inevitably have some impact on the final account. This not only resonates with a constructionist epistemological stance but has a more positive perspective on my position as it acknowledges that my own experiences will affect my interpretation of the data:

...there is a difference between an open mind and empty head. To analyse data, we need to use accumulated knowledge, not dispense with it. The issue is not whether to use existing knowledge, but how...The danger lies not in having assumptions but in not being aware of them...

(Dey, 1993, p.63)

Studies reviewed in the published literature adopted an ethnographic approach and they reported rich in-depth data exploring the perceptions and experiences of minority ethnic teachers (Bhatti, 1999; Shain, 2003; Ladson-Billings, 2005; Santoro and Reid, 2006). Yet despite this, the following reasons prevented me from adopting this approach: the red tape in getting access to school sites from the local authorities and work constraints did not allow me to spend time out in the field. As a full-time academic teaching across a range of programmes finding time to spend in schools would be difficult. Consideration of the sample size was also problematic as there are only a small percentage of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland and in different geographical locations and they often find themselves isolated in number. This would mean that an ethnographic approach to this study may have just focussed on one minority ethnic teacher present in the school. Yet, I hoped to explore a number of minority ethnic teachers' experiences to offer multiple insights into how they begin to negotiate their professional identities.

Phenomenology

Phenomenology is an approach that seeks to understand people's perceptions of a particular situation or event (Denscombe, 2010). It offers participants an opportunity to interpret their subjective experiences and how they make sense of it (MacKay, 2004). The researcher, too, has an opportunity to explore multiple perceptions and understandings of the same situation of what something is like as an experience from an insider perspective (Olson, 2011).

This seemed to be an approach that I could consider for my study. However, similar to an ethnographic approach, the experiences of minority ethnic teachers require to be examined over a long period of time (Creswell 2003). Moreover, the emphasis of phenomenology is more on describing the experiences than to investigate the external reality in which the phenomenon occurs. So, essentially, adopting an approach that seeks to exclude this reality and ‘...approach things without predispositions based on events in the past’ (Denscombe, 2010, p. 99) would not be suited for this study.

I wanted to understand the perceptions, perspectives and understandings of minority ethnic teachers’ professional lives. Minority ethnic teachers are underrepresented in the workforce and quintessentially, the teacher workforce in Scotland is predominately, white and female (Arshad and Mitchell, 2005). The literature review had suggested that minority ethnic teachers’ experience structural inequalities including racial discrimination and so, perhaps do not consider teaching as a profession as they lack role models and they are often not considered to be ‘real’ teachers by fellow colleagues and pupils (Arshad. et.al, 2005; Shain, 2005). It was important, therefore, to consider both the current and historical context within which they experience this inequality.

Qualitative Case Study Design

Punch (1998) defines a case study as:

...one case (or perhaps a number of small cases) will be studied in detail, using whatever methods seem appropriate. While there may be a variety of specific purposes and research questions, the general objective is to develop as full an understanding of that case as possible.

(Punch, 1998, p.150).

The case study methodology is commonly used in qualitative research where Stake (2000) argues that the decision to adopt this approach should relate to the phenomenon being studied '... as opposed to a methodological choice, owing to its focus on a 'case'. (p.435). Like ethnography and phenomenology, some case studies require the researcher to participate in the setting over an extended period in order to get a better understanding of the case at hand. However, Stake (2000) argues that a case study approach can also be considered where the researcher is unable to spend time in the field but still seeks to gather rich data for analysis.

Yin (2014) suggests that the choice depends on your research questions:

'The more your questions seek to explain some present circumstance (e.g. 'how' and 'why' some social phenomenon works), the more that case study research will be relevant.'

(p.4)

This suggested that a case study approach may be a useful methodology for my study as it sought to examine the case of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland.

Yin (2014) suggest that the researcher needs to define the limits of the 'case', for example, a case study of minority ethnic teachers will explore their lived experiences within school structures. The case study will not only look at the minority ethnic teacher but also at the teacher's relationships with his or her colleagues, pupils and parents. It is because of these parameters that case studies are sometimes referred to as 'bounded systems' (Edward, 2001, p.126). The 'system' is seen as a 'set of interrelated elements that form an organised whole' (Johnson and Christensen,

2008, p.406). This suggests that the researcher would be interested in looking at the system (case) to explore how different aspects of the settings and practices in school interrelate and begin to investigate 'What is going on here?' (Edwards (2001, p126).

As the review of literature highlighted the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers, both locally and nationally and the challenges and barriers they face in their day-to-day teaching lives, it was important to consider 'what is going on with minority ethnic teachers in Schools in Scotland?' This also suggested a case study as having potential for this study.

Both Stake (2000) and Denscombe (2007) discuss the level of depth that a case study can offer where the aim is to 'illuminate the general by looking at the particular' (Denscombe, 2007 p.31). This provided an opportunity to focus on the specific issues that minority ethnic teachers were raising to begin to understand the wider context within which they worked. This is in line with Stake who offers guidance on how one might "demonstrate the *particularity* of the 'case':

- “1. The nature of the case
2. The case's historical background.
3. The physical setting
4. Other context (e.g., economic, political and legal)
5. Other cases through which this case is recognised
6. Those informants through whom the case can be known.”

(Stake, 2000, p.439)

This again suggested possibilities in linking minority ethnic teachers' experiences by describing in detail the ways in which the above may be useful. Bassey (1999) identifies three major categories of case studies: theory-seeking and theory-testing case studies, evaluative case studies and storytelling and picture drawing case

studies. Yin (2014) calls a theory-seeking case study an exploratory study, which this is, as it seeks to explore the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers. Stake (2000) describes case studies as being intrinsic which helps us to understand a particular case; Instrumental, which is learning about what is happening beyond this case and lastly, a Collective case study which examines more than one case to better understand a complex phenomenon. As the aim of the study was to obtain an in-depth understanding of the case then it required not just descriptions of the experiences but rather to offer some reflections and analysis supported by theory. An intrinsic case study can lead to another large research project. This research study is both intrinsic and exploratory as I hope to gain an insight into the circumstances that have affected the case of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland.

In summary, there are key strengths of a case study approach. Tobin et al. (1989) discuss ecological validity: where the findings reflect what is happening in 'real' life and where the issue in question is sensitive, a case study is a safe approach to use. In short, a case study shares many ethnographic characteristics (Denscombe, 2007). As the review of the literature highlights, much research conducted with minority ethnic professionals and young people used a case study approach. Arshad et al (2005) used a case study approach with focus groups to explore BME pupils' experiences of school in Scotland (MEPESS) while Shain (2007) conducted a case study of young Asian students in schools and again in 2010, used the same approach to obtain an in-depth understanding of minority ethnic youth in their community. The case studies produced rich data which captured the collective and individual perspectives and so I considered that this added value to better understanding the case of minority ethnic teachers.

There are, however, limitations to a case study approach. The in-depth nature of one or a few cases means that generalisations cannot be made (Gilbert, 2008). Furthermore, the 'particularity' of a case study also means that replicability would also be a limitation (Stake, 2000). For example, there can be multiple valid answers to the same questions and diverse positions will be noted. In addition to this, I am a

minority ethnic teacher and researcher, and I may bring some bias to this study: my level of interest in this 'case'; the way I chose to record and analyse the data.

Theoretical Framework

To explore how minority ethnic teachers 'negotiate' their personal and professional identities without feeling disadvantaged, I needed to develop a theoretical framework to inform my discussion of data. Theories of Teacher Professional identity and Critical Race Theory (CRT) have been used to inform the research design.

Professional Identity

As discussed in Chapter one, the concept of professional identity is used in different ways in teaching. In some studies, professional identity is related to the teachers' sense of self (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004; Alsup, 2006; Beauchamp, 2009). These researchers have argued that teachers' images of self, determine the way teachers teach, the way they develop as teachers and their attitude towards educational reform. In other studies of professional identity, the emphasis was placed on teachers' roles, where reflection and self-evaluation were considered important to the development of professional identity (Goodson & Cole, 1994; Cooper and Olsen, 1996). Experience and events that take place in the personal lives of teachers also impact the performance of their professional roles (Sachs, 2005; Beauchamp, 2009). Moreover, it is suggested that teachers' identities are not only constructed from the professional and personal in, for example, classroom management and pupil relationships but they are also constructed through their interactions with peers and the school's cultural and institutional environment (Hong, Day and Greene, 2017).

In 2015, there were concerns raised around the underrepresentation of BME teachers in Scotland, especially in senior roles (BBC, 2017). Similarly, in England, a news report concluded that a further 68,000 teachers from Black and Minority ethnic groups were required to be recruited to reflect England's pupil population (BBC

News, 2017). Arguably, the low number of minority ethnic teachers in schools and promoted posts also impact the development of possible selves and professional identity and again highlights a need for a study that would examine this phenomenon.

Critical Race Theory

I use Critical Race Theory (CRT) to critique the powerful discourses that prevail around race and inequality. CRT provides a lens through which to investigate the contexts within which these issues are played out and to consider the implications for practice. Critical race theorists argue that society views racism as an ordinary fact of daily life and that the assumptions of White superiority are so ingrained in political, legal and educational structures that they fail to recognise the inequalities (Delgado, 1995).

Kohli's (2014) research explored Black and Minority Ethnic student teachers' experiences of racism when they were growing up. She argues that these past experiences become internalised and if the student teachers are not given the opportunity to acknowledge and unpack these experiences. The question that arises is how does this place the students to support the children they teach and to challenge racial discrimination. Kohli (2014) adopts a critical race theory framework to analyse the findings.

Furthermore, Kohli (2014) asserts that:

CRT scholars of education have developed the following five tenets to guide research: (a) centrality of race and racism; (b) challenge to the dominant perspective; (c) commitment to social justice; (d) value of experiential knowledge; e) interdisciplinary (Solórzano and Bernal 2001). Collectively,

these tenets offer scholars the historical, legal and social analytical evidence to foreground race and racism within educational inequality.

(Kohli, 2014, p.4)

By placing the experiences of minority ethnic teachers at the forefront, CRT offers me, a minority ethnic researcher, the lens with which to examine and theorise about the complexities of the professional lives of minority ethnic teachers who took part in my study. Whilst CRT intersects with other aspects of identity and experience such as gender, disability and sexuality etc., it places minority ethnic teachers' racialized experiences at the very core of the discussions (Yosso, 2005). Moreover, CRT guides researchers to move beyond seeing participants as data sources but to listen to the counter-narratives of people who have complex lived experiences (Solorzano and Yosso (2010)). Essentially, it validates and recognises their experiences as evidence within the research study.

Therefore, Slay and Smith's (2010) model of professional identity construction considers minority ethnic teachers' values, beliefs and attitudes and how early influences, such as family together with their professional experiences of being 'othered' and regarded as outsiders have influenced their professional identity. Slay and Smith's model also moves into exploring redefinition tasks which include redefining self, stigma and work. However, I argue that before this process of redefining can take place it is important to consider the tenets of CRT to support minority ethnic teachers in understanding the impact of race and racism. There seemed to be a growing realisation that minority ethnic teachers do not simply adapt to existing cultures or standpoints, but that teacher identity is negotiated by responding to challenges they face in their day-to-day experiences of teaching. These range from being 'the outsider' and having to work twice as hard as their white colleagues. They are also often pigeon-holed and regarded as the teacher who will do all things about culture and diversity and that promotion is never easy. Thus, negotiation is critical to redefining identity. Critical race theory will be applied to

examine the impact of factors influencing professional identity development for minority ethnic teachers. Minority ethnic teachers counter-narratives of their experiences in schools and the wider education system will be important to capture to help us understand the issues around under-representation, remaining and progressing in the profession.

Theoretical Framework

The Main study – choosing methods

As this study was driven by a constructo-interpretive epistemology (Coburn, 2014), and my chosen methodology, I considered different methods of collecting data, to acquire different kinds of information from the participants. It was important to consider which methods would be useful in seeking to answer my research questions.

Diaries

The use of a diary provides a means of generating large amounts of data with minimal amount of effort by the researcher (Robson, 2002). I considered asking minority ethnic teachers to keep a diary to reflect on any incidents and conversations that they took part in with colleagues and children. As with any research tool, the advantages were required to be weighed against the disadvantages to help decide on diary use in this study. An advantage is that keeping a diary is a well-understood process which can be manageable and unobtrusive. This would enable the participants to take time out of their busy day to reflect upon a key incident and help develop their thinking on their professional and personal identities.

Pearce (2005) kept a diary to research practice and record developing thinking on race and difference. The benefits of being able to reflect on diary entries, repeatedly, and on each subsequent reading, were used to identify patterns in her and the pupil's behaviour. Clandinin and Connelly (2000) highlight that events which may appear unimportant when viewed in isolation may achieve more significance when considered against previous events already recorded. This process of rereading can also enable participants to create a degree of distance from their thoughts and allow them to develop a more critical analysis of their own thoughts and actions (Brown and Jones, 2001). I considered giving the teachers a structure

to their writing but was aware that simplifying and structuring the task could produce data which would be prone to bias or leading in a very prescriptive way.

However structured diary use also risks, misreporting or increases the chance of misreporting or entering incidents about changes in behaviours and thoughts into the diary to please the researcher and show the diarist in a good light. The risk of misreporting could be increased because of assumptions made by participants about my own ethnicity and positionality. In other words, participant teachers may feel that they need to record things that they think I may be looking for. Troyna (1998) suggests that concerns have been raised that there may be too much emphasis on the personal experience which may lead to social and political issues being ignored and that the emphasis may be on individual empowerment. The purpose of this study is to try and create knowledge which will not only empower the participants but also generate knowledge of relevance to a wider audience of minority ethnic people as well as the majority ethnic teachers, policymakers and teacher educators and so I rejected this tool for data collection.

Observation

Robson (2002) states that the use of the diary as the sole data collection method is questionable in terms of reliability and validity and that combining a diary method with direct observation can give confidence about the data gathered. Thus, I considered using observation to see how the minority ethnic teachers 'perform' their personal and/or professional identities in the classroom. Indeed, I also wished to be able to see whether their cultural and linguistic skills were acknowledged and utilised within the wider school. However, the extent to which an observer affects the situation being observed remains one of the major disadvantages of this method (Robson, 2002). As a minority ethnic teacher, I am continuously aware of ensuring reflexivity and was concerned about asking questions of minority ethnic teachers for fear of leading their responses.

I considered direct observations as I would not be asking for participants' views, feelings or attitudes but rather watching and listening to what they are saying and what their experience is like. Cohen et al. (2011) reminded me of the need to consider how I would reflect on and come to know what the behaviour would have been like if I had not observed it or whether one takes on a detached role or involved role. Again, considering my own position within the research, the degree of detachment could be questionable. To avoid seeing things that I wanted to see or perhaps reading too much into what I saw. Too much time observing would compromise my role and raise ethical concerns.

Interviews

Schostak (2006) warns that interviews are not simple tools which allow them to gather information from the research participants. Rather as an interview, this method is much about seeing a world – mine, yours, ours, theirs – as about hearing accounts, opinions, arguments, reasons, declarations... (p.1). It allows the researcher to acquire multiple perspectives, 'like having many lives by proxy' (Schostak, 2006, p.1). The process should focus on the knowledge being generated by both the researcher and the participant, rather than the data being captured (Walford, 2001). The interview provided a means of listening and to provide the participants with hope that by listening to their views, something might be learnt and more importantly, how much something might be changed. The research participants are viewed as helping to construct the reality with the researcher, and because there will be different contexts with different perspectives, the research questions cannot be fully established in advance of this process. (Robson, 2002).

Focus Group Interviews

A variety of different interview structures were considered, from focus groups through to un/structured and semi-structured individual interviews. Conducting focus group interviews allowed me to focus on the respondents shared experiences and

the interactions that occur between the group members (Olsen, 2011). Hayes, points out that:

If group members regard their views somewhat contrary to prevailing opinion within the group, they might be inclined to keep quiet, or moderate their views somewhat

(Hayes, 2000, p.15).

Although all the respondents in this study were from minority ethnic backgrounds they had different experiences in terms of the culture in their settings, their own lived experiences. Some of the participants spoke about the racism they experienced and some remained quiet. Once they heard from others, they too started to contribute by sharing their experiences and perspectives (Olsen, 2011). It was important to have the right environment to allow the participants to feel comfortable and relaxed. In terms of accessibility, minority ethnic teachers often work in isolation where they find themselves as the only minority ethnic teacher in the school. Thus, it was easier and more convenient for the participants to meet in a local school, within their catchment area, after the school day was over. Initially, I was concerned about the need for privacy but appropriate rooms were offered to conduct the focus groups privately and free from distractions. This ensured safer and braver spaces for the participants to feel comfortable and at ease (Opie, 2013).

My constructo-interpretivist epistemological stance required me to take a constructionist and interpretive view on construction of new knowledge. Each focus group invited a group of eight minority ethnic teachers to explore their views about teaching and discuss their experiences of working in schools and the relationships they have with their colleagues and the children. The focus group interviews preceded the one-to-one interviews and allowed me to pursue the individual conversations based on a more socially constructed knowledge base rather than my own preconceived ideas.

Unstructured/semi-structured Interviews

Unstructured interviews are generally used to provide scope for sufficient knowledge to be created in order to move on to the next stage of the research design. As Olsen (2011) states, in unstructured interviews, the interviewer will not have any questions to ask the interviewee but instead tries to elicit information by introducing some general areas for discussion. It is argued that by providing these topics for discussion, some kind of structure is introduced to the interview.

Consideration was given to semi-structured interviews, which encourage the respondents to answer as necessary to specific questions, with the possibility of exploring more in-depth views with prompts and probes. This was a popular tool used in much of the reviewed literature and linked well with my constructivist-interpretivist epistemological stance because it encouraged collaboration with the interviewee and discussion of the ideas and views that arose from the focus groups to reach a new shared understanding (Shain, 2003; Cole and Stuart, 2005; Ladson-Billings, 2005).

This method of gathering data can allow for a more flexible style of interview, whereby the conversation is led by the interviewee to share his/her experiences rather than by prompts constructed by the researcher, which could present with my own assumptions and experiences. This was also in line with my theoretical framework as storytelling and narrative are one of the main tenets of critical race theory (Farber and Sherry, 2009). The discussions were more collaborative in nature, and I replaced the word 'interview' with conversations as this would be desirable from a critical race theory perspective, which argues that narrative in participant stories, serves to redirect the views of the majority and to expose what was there all along (Delgado, 2005). Conversations and imagined episodes can help challenge underlying assumptions and myths, shifting the debate towards a sense of reality that reflects the experiences of the minority. Therefore, the research tool I used was semi-structured, 'individual conversations' (Forsey, 2008).

Forsey (2008) questions the traditional views held around research interviews, seeks to interrogate the 'taken-for-granted status' of this tool and argues that the rigorous examination of the interview to communicate should be applied. He suggests that emphasis needs to be given to how the researcher will convey the interview data to the reading audience, in other, words the focus shifts beyond just simply the relationship between interviewer and interviewee. This bodes well when one considers the specifics of validity and generalizability (Kvale, 1996). Qualitative interviews are often described as 'intimate conversations' (Robson, 2002, p.278) or perhaps as Holstein and Gubrium (1995) state 'an unfolding, interpersonal drama with an unfolding plot' (p.16). I argue that the semi-structured conversations aimed to link the personal stories of the minority ethnic teachers to issues of collaborative and coercive power structures I was seeking to describe and analyse.

The next section will describe the process of gaining ethics approval, how the data was generated using the data collection tools, how it was analysed, and the themes that arose from coding and exploring the data.

Ethical considerations

There are many research methodology texts that caution researchers about taking care when interviewing marginalised groups. Parker (2015) asserts that interviewing minority and marginalised people, for example, the unemployed; those whose first language is a minority language; refugees and asylum seekers; is becoming an educational concern and sets out some guidance when interviewing them. These concerns are around protecting minority groups from being exploited and stress that researchers need to be culturally sensitive. This point is also reinforced by Pearce (2020) who argues that educational research has ignored marginalised groups by not addressing their needs and where research has been conducted it has been culturally insensitive and the appropriate tools were not used.

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2017) assert that the interviewer will need to show consideration to the type of interview selected for data collection. As a minority ethnic researcher, I have been marginalised in terms of my race and ethnicity, in the same way as my research participants. I agree with Pearce (2020), that methodology texts are written from the perspective of the ethnic majority and that considerations are made for the less powerful in terms of how issues should be explored with great sensitivity. I was aware that some of the information being shared could trigger internalised trauma for some of the participants and so I provided contact details for minority ethnic agencies that could offer support if required.

It was important for me to consider my own position in relation to the study as my ethnicity and life experiences had the potential of influencing my interactions with participants; which in turn and raise concerns around the credibility of the study, the validity of findings. Lessons can be learned from the work of Bhatti (1999), Shain (2005) and more recently, Lander (2011), who are minority ethnic teacher educators and researchers, all marginalised in their Academies. All three authors argue that research conducted with marginalised groups should be driven by the intent to benefit the groups and not further exploit them (Pearce, 2020). This is a key feature of critical educational research where the notion of simply coming to a shared understanding is not enough, but it is necessary to be able to bring about change as a result of the research. As Cohen et al. (2011) assert critical educational research 'seeks to emancipate the disempowered, to redress inequality and to promote individual freedom within a democratic society' (p.31).

An issue for consideration prior to collecting the data was the extent to which the participants would be involved in the study after their interviews were completed. The literature and research methods identified narrative and in-depth interviews as appropriate, as the respondents will have space to 'self-disclose' and retell their life stories and share their voices (Arshad et al., 2005; Shain, 2005; Lander, 2011; Bhopal and Rhamie, 2013). Being heard and listened to is paramount in bringing about change so it is the responsibility of the researcher to avoid being judgemental

and so create opportunities for the participants to validate and reflect upon comments made and to have the right to withdraw certain information.

To comply with the University of West of Scotland's robust ethical approval processes, I completed an ethics application which was approved. Participant information included an introductory information sheet and consent form that was distributed prior to a briefing meeting. Before the focus group conversations started, I briefed the participants about the study. In addition to providing information on what I would do with the data they provided, the briefing included an explanation of how ethical issues would be managed and how participant anonymity would be protected and maintained through the use of pseudonyms. They were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study and how to do this.

Keeping the data confidential and anonymous was also an ethical consideration, particularly, when there are such few minority ethnic teachers in Scotland. Each participant was given a pseudonym to avoid identification. One of the focus groups comprised of 6 teachers that taught in the same school, but I provide no geographic marker to show where the school is situated within Scotland as it would not take much to identify this school. As shown in the literature review, minority ethnic teachers' often work in isolation – this school is in a unique position to have a number of minority ethnic teachers working together.

To avoid the risk of anyone being recognised, first names were used and then during transcription, the names were changed. All documents containing written notes were secured in a locked drawer in my office at the university. All transcribed data was stored in a password-protected pen drive.

Data Collection

As discussed in the review of the literature, there are only a small percentage of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland, around 1%. Therefore, the selection of a non-random, convenience sample (Seale, 1998; Robson, 2002) meant that it was largely drawn from minority ethnic teachers who I knew and could be easily contacted. I also took advantage of the snowball strategy to encourage more teachers to come forward. In this sense, the sample was opportunistic and not representative of the entire population of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland (Bell, 1999; Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2001).

For both the pilot study and the main study, the fieldwork was conducted using the same data collection methods, namely focus groups and semi-structured interviews. Interviews require to be planned carefully, in particular focus groups where the researcher should consider the role of the interviewer and the interviewee. (Olsen, 2011). So, it was important for me to reflect on the lessons I have learned from conducting the first focus group conversation. In the first phase, I held three focus groups and in total, twenty minority ethnic teachers took part. There was a mix of male and female teachers with teaching experience ranging from 1 to 25 years. The minority ethnic teachers self-identified as either British Asian, Pakistani or Indian. 16 out of the 20 teachers stated that they were of Muslim faith, 1 identified as Christian, 2 as Hindu and 1 as Sikh.

Phase 1 – Focus Groups

Focus Group 1 Participant	Age	Gender	Ethnicity	Religion	No. of years teaching experience
Abu-Zahr	52	Male	British Asian	Muslim	15
Leyla	49	Female	African- Caribbean	Christian	12
Khurram	46	Male	British Asian	Muslim	12
Safia	38	Female	Pakistani	Muslim	7
Pooja	25	Female	British Asian	Hindu	3
Dina	44	Female	African- Caribbean	Christian	8
Focus Group 2 Participant	Age	Gender	Ethnicity	Religion	No. of years teaching experience
Kashif	35	Male	British Asian	Muslim	10
Yusuf	55	Male	Pakistani	Muslim	25
Naila	37	Female	British Asian	Muslim	13
Mumta	60	Female	Indian	Hindu	20
Kasim	50	Male	Pakistani	Muslim	17
Aneesah	42	Female	British Asian	Muslim	15
Nusrat	51	Female	British Asian	Muslim	19

Waheed	24	Male	British Asian	Muslim	2
Adnan	65	Male	British Asian	Muslim	30
Focus Group 3 Participant	Age	Gender	Ethnicity	Religion	No. of years teaching experience
Shaista	40	Female	British Asian	Muslim	16
Ayesha	36	Female	British Asian	Muslim	10
Nafeesah	34	Female	British Asian	Muslim	11
Zainab	34	Female	British Asian	Muslim	12
Wahid	26	Male	British Asian	Muslim	1
Karol	24	Female	British Asian	Sikh	3
Samera	36	Female	British Asian	Muslim	Probationer
Farhana	50	Female	British Asian	Muslim	27

Phase 1 – Focus Groups

For phase 1 of the data collection, I conducted focus groups using some question prompts. I used a deductive approach, whereby the research questions were informed from the gaps in the literature review). I then used the research questions to write some question prompts for the focus group schedule to explore four key areas: why they chose teaching as a career; what they bring to their teaching, their

interactions with minority ethnic pupils and their identity as minority ethnic teachers in schools. To recruit minority ethnic teachers for the first focus group, I contacted Khashif, a secondary school teacher, who helped arrange for a few other colleagues he worked alongside, to attend. This snowballing strategy was effective in locating and encouraging teachers to take part (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017). When it came to deciding on the venue, I had learned from the pilot study, that it was easier for the teachers to gather in either the school where they worked or one nearby within their local authority.

The focus group interviews with participants lasted between 45 minutes to one hour. I wanted to ensure that the participants had my undivided attention and did not wish to be writing notes whilst trying to maintain eye contact (Olsen, 2011). It was important to show value to what they were discussing as we learned from the literature review that the perspectives and lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers are often overlooked in policy and practice. To this end, I used a digital recorder to capture the focus group discussion and written consent from the participants was obtained prior to the focus groups starting. I used the prompts to encourage a conversational approach which gave participants an opportunity to feel relaxed and openly discuss their views.

Unspoken Words: non-verbal cues

It is important to consider both the verbal and non-verbal data. The facial expressions and the body language were also very revealing. Participants shared each other's experiences and perception of their work lives, their relationships with fellow colleagues and the pupils they teach. They quickly gained each other's trust and spoke with confidence about the perceived racism and inequality within the school structure. Mustafa was candid in both the focus group and the subsequent individual conversation. Yusuf's language illustrated a lack of interest as he shrugged his shoulders and shook his head to show his indifference. As the conversation continued, it became apparent that Yusuf's lack of interest was grounded in the decades of inequality he had faced as a teacher with little to no

support from his colleagues. His dismay was understandable when he said '*We have been having these conversations for years upon years...what's the point, nothing changes!*' (Yusuf)

Such non-verbal cues were observed during the focus groups and interviews and were added to the transcripts to give depth. According to Sturges and Hanrahan (2004) these non-verbal cues offered a level of richness that the verbal data alone could not provide.

Phase 2 – Semi-Structured Interviews

For, phase 2, I invited those who attended the focus group to take part in individual conversational interviews to follow up on some of the issues discussed within the group. I adopted an inductive approach to Phase 2 as the information deduced from the focus groups allowed me to draw up the individual interview schedule (Olsen, 2011). Nine of the original participants agreed to participate (see table 3) in the semi-structured interviews (see table above in the individual conversations are highlighted below. A further four had provisionally agreed but due to busy school schedules and personal commitments were unable to meet. One participant asked me to remove her from the focus group along with any data that included her responses.

Data analysis: generating codes and emerging themes

Qualitative approaches can be nuanced and diverse and so it is important to describe the process taken to analyse the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To begin the process of transcribing, I listened to the recordings several times. This helped to gain insights into the participants' perspectives from the prompts and questions provided. The focus group interviews, and all semi-structured interviews were transcribed and the data analysed in relation to the research questions. Boyatzis (1998) outlines thematic analysis as a tool rather than a method and similarly, Ryan and Bernard (2000) consider analysing data for themes and recurring patterns as a process. This process should be transparent as it will allow for effective evaluations

of the study and comparisons to be made with other research topics or with future research carried out in this area (Attride-Stirling, 2001).

Scholars have diverse perspectives on the use of codes and coding data, from an objection (Packer, 2011), to recognising this as a valid way of analysing data to an assertion that:

Any researcher who wishes to become proficient in qualitative analysis must learn to code well and easily. The excellence of the research rests in part on the excellence of coding.

(Strauss, 1987, p.27)

This study is framed by critical race theory, which creates opportunities for marginalised communities to place their experiences of race and racism at the centre of the challenges they face. CRT offers them a:

... language to name their experiences, feel a sense of community in their experiences, and [...] find a voice to challenge Injustice.

(Kohli, 2014, p. 4)

The conversations arising from the focus groups and semi-structured interviews gave me the opportunity to apply my theoretical lens to examine carefully the words and paragraphs within the transcripts to capture the nuances and subtleties of how participants negotiate their professional identities.

As I conducted the interviews myself, during the analysis I had some prior knowledge of the data and perhaps some initial ideas on emerging themes. This, too, has an impact on how you begin to code the data (Adler and Adler, 1987; Kvale and Brinkman, 2009). The first stage was to transcribe the interviews. This was extremely time consuming, particularly because of the nature of the conversations, where some interviews took longer than one hour. However, the interpretive nature of this phase, which included listening to the recordings and reading and re-reading the transcripts, provided an opportunity to immerse myself in the data and make some initial notes on patterns emerging and possible codes (Riesman, 1993; Bird, 2005). Boyatzis (1998, p.3) describes this as 'finding a codable moment'. The reading and re-reading across a data set to find repeated patterns of meaning and giving names to these provides an opportunity to see things that can be coded together to create themes (Boyatzis, 1998).

I used Boyatzis's (1998) Thematic Analysis Framework which uses a process of open coding to categorise information and develop thematic analysis. Generating initial codes involved a line-by-line coding looking for words and phrases that were recurring across the data set. I highlighted these and noted them down, creating a list which would enable me to identify any similarities and group these to create themes. From initial coding to sorting codes into groups, the search for themes began. I used mind maps as a visual representation of codes and started to think about the relationship between the codes identified and the themes emerging.

I reduced 25 initial codes down to four themes that each of the analysis chapters discuss. When the participants discussed the reasons for becoming a teacher, they cited reasons such as a family member being a teacher or parental encouragement, I coded this as family. Some of the participants discussed wearing a hijab or having a beard and some clearly referred to their faith influencing their decisions to become a teacher, I coded these under religious beliefs. Many of the participants discussed how they did not have a minority ethnic teacher when they were at school and wanted to support all pupils, in particular minority ethnic pupils. They also discussed

the racism they experienced and did not want minority ethnic pupils to go through this. I coded this making a difference and changing attitudes.

During the focus groups and semi-structured interviews, participants discussed how they felt like outsiders and their attempts to try and fit in. They also shared some of the comments, the looks and scrutiny they would receive from colleagues at different stages of their careers. I coded these as lack of self-esteem, feeling invisible and ignored against the daily racial micro-aggressions experienced. This acknowledgment of the racism they experienced was important to shed light on.

Participants shared how they tried to build positive relationships with the young people and their families. They also discussed the different ways they try to ensure that the ethos is culturally relevant and engage in a critical approach to what they teach and how they teach. However, they also discussed some of the challenges they faced in doing so.

Finally, they discussed the challenges they faced in term of progression – phrases such as ‘I have to be whiter than white’, ‘it is not a glass ceiling... a concrete ceiling’ helped to shed light on their experiences. They also discuss some of the enablers that actively support their leadership opportunities.

These themes are:

- Acknowledgment
- Affirmation
- Agency
- Activism

These themes were also consistent with the literature in that minority ethnic teachers discussed their experiences not being recognised and that some did draw on their diverse cultural, religious and linguistic skills to inform their teaching where others did not. However, the case of minority ethnic teachers is an under researched area in Scotland and these themes were helpful in understanding how minority ethnic teachers can be better supported in developing their professional identities as teachers.

Figure 2: initial process of analysing data

Table 3: Coding the data

Codes	THEMES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ family ➤ religion ➤ aspiration ➤ making a difference ➤ changing attitudes ➤ questioning self-image ➤ lack of self esteem ➤ trying to fitting in ➤ feeling invisible ➤ Daily experiences of racial micro aggressions 	<p>Acknowledgement and Affirmation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The influence of cultural factors • Giving back • Sense of Belonging: • interpersonal racism • internalised racism • institutional racism
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Rapport/connection/family ➤ Gender ➤ Curriculum - challenging stereotypes, discrimination ➤ resources ➤ religious issues ➤ use of mother tongue ➤ cultural references 	<p>Agency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relational ties: culture/ gender/ language/ family • The hidden curriculum • culturally responsive curriculum

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ overlooked/devalued ➤ relationships with colleagues/ socialising ➤ networks ➤ lack of career progression ➤ strategising 	<p>Activism – Leadership opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barriers – fitting in as part of an assimilation process • Enablers – affiliation/allyship • Taking action

The pilot study - Lessons learned

At the start of the Focus Groups, I noticed two teachers, one from focus group 1 and the other from focus group 3 looking around before they spoke, indicating that they were not entirely comfortable. I assured them that their responses would remain confidential and anonymous and that they should feel that they are in a safe space to speak openly.

Having conducted the first focus group conversation with minority ethnic teachers, there have been lessons learned that have helped me to refine my data collection and the procedures to be followed. As Yin (2014) discusses, the initial phase in data collection is used more formatively to support in developing the questions and in offering clarification with respect to the research design (Yin, 2014).

There were three main lessons to learn: my sample, my ability to conduct a focus group interview and the choice of venue for the interviews.

Deciding on whom to interview: lessons learned.

My concerns were mainly around two aspects: first, there were such few minority ethnic teachers and secondly, the sensitivity and nature of the study may discourage them from taking part. Olsen (2011) cautions qualitative researchers to consider the question 'how much time is required for a person to acquire 'enough' experience to provide data of good quality?' (p.26). It would have been helpful to have a wide range from participants at the beginning of their career journey to more experienced participants. I did find some rich data about their journeys and showed how they, in their own ways, seemed to subsume within the majority white culture and get on with, as they saw it, the job in hand – to teach. This sample offered a particular dimension to the study: their own experience of schooling; training to be a teacher and their current experiences and could go some way in answering the research questions for this study.

However, for subsequent focus group conversations, I then recruited participants' with diverse experiences: newly qualified, minority ethnic teachers at the start of their journey; minority ethnic teachers who have been teaching for a number of years; minority ethnic teachers who were not born in Scotland but trained to be a teacher in Scotland and subsequently worked in Scottish schools. This would help me to consider all the different perspectives that have relevance to the study.

Conducting the focus group interviews: Lessons learned

I had no experience of facilitating a focus group conversation and as such, the lessons I learned were valuable. I had produced an interview schedule with five questions (see appendix) and I was aware that these questions required to be discussed over the duration of the interview. I also was mindful that the interactions between the participants in the group were of value too

I introduced the study to the participants and collected consent forms from those who had signed and brought them with them and also issued consent forms for those who did not bring signed copies to the focus group conversation. I also asked the members of the group to state their names before they speak so that it would be easier to identify who spoke when transcribing the interview (Denscombe, 2007). This was fine, initially, but then members forgot to continue this. When I asked the questions, the members seemed to take it in turn to offer their response, and I felt that this reduced the interactions between the members – it was akin to holding individual interviews within a group setting where you simply seem to be collecting data quickly. This is not the purpose of a focus group and Krueger (2009) points out the importance of including the responses from both the questions set and the questions and comments of other people in the group.

I ensured to set ground rules for the focus group so I could identify the speaker when transcribing and ensured that I used my questions to probe and encourage interaction between the members as they shared their experiences. I switched off the audio-recording device once I concluded the interview but as the participants were preparing to leave the discussions seemed to continue and I was included in some candid remarks that I felt were quite important for the project. I recorded these conversations in my field notes and sought permission to include this information as data. For the main study, I ensured to keep my audio-recording device on for a further 10 to 15 minutes after the focus group and interview was over (Olson, 2011).

The locations chosen for the conversations: lessons learned

The first focus group conversation was carried out in a school building and after school hours. Despite seeking a location, the participants requested that a school close to them was best for ease of travel. The focus group conversation took place in an open plan space within the school and although all staff had left the building, I noticed some of the participants looking a little anxious about their surroundings by looking over their shoulders from time to time. I had little control of this but as the researcher, it was my responsibility to ensure everyone felt comfortable and safe to talk. I asked if we could move to a closed room.

Researcher identity and positionality

Malterud (2001) discusses the importance of being consistent and connected from the introduction of the research study to drawing concluding marks. As a researcher, I had to be clear and consistent in all aspects of research design. Opie (2004) emphasises the place of reflection and reflexivity in ensuring a confident rigorous researcher:

I believe that it is important for all researchers to spend some time thinking how they are paradigmatically and philosophically positioned and for them to be aware of how their positioning – and the fundamental assumptions they hold – might influence their research related thinking and practice.

(Opie, 2004, p.19)

I was aware of my own lived experiences and so felt that I was being drawn into the conversation. The following account illustrates Cohen et al.'s (2005) point. Three female researchers, Porr et al. (2010), undertook a study where they wished to interview people who were suffering from depression. They designed a poster inviting individuals to call and take part. They managed to recruit some interested people, but they noticed that no men came forward. The research team were advised by a male student that they should change the poster so that people who wished to take part in the study should call him. They managed to recruit some men thus indicating that depressed men seem to prefer talking to a male interviewer. Warren (2010) highlights that factors such as gender, race, ethnicity, religion, age have an influence on the quality of the data.

Emic and Etit Perspective

Morse et al. (2002) argues that it is better when an interviewer is less familiar with the topic of study as important information may be overlooked due to increased familiarity. However, Fetterman (2008) discusses the benefits of the case where the interviewer is seen as an 'insider' and as such, could gather data that would not otherwise be available. Olsen (2011), too, emphasises this standpoint and asks, 'whether the researcher would like to study from the perspective of an 'insider' (emic) or an 'outsider' (etic)?' (p.15). As a minority ethnic female, former schoolteacher and researcher, I have had a balance of the emic and etic perspective using a triple lens. I too, have been part of educational spaces where I have experienced a racially minoritised status. I have the lived experience and shared the same cultural background as many of the participants. I am located within this research and as

such, the participants have often included me when sharing their perspectives by using pronouns such as 'us', 'we' 'our' and, I, therefore, argue that the data gathered was from an emic perspective. However, my etic perspective is the outsider perspective. The fact that I am an academic positions me as the outsider operating from a different level, as I have academically researched this area. So in my role as a researcher and academic, I share culture, and I share meaning making. The participants have the lens of an expert by experience - current lived experience. I also have this lens, but it is a past one so in some sense, I do not know because I have this balance of the emic and etic. My emic perspective positions me to bring my practitioner lens and my lived experience and when I come into the etic perspective, I am the researcher and academic and I bring to it a very particular lens. It is not a constant position it is more an iterative process, and I have been conscious of my positionality because at no point did I want not to take for granted that I was the expert as this was not my epistemological view of life nor my philosophical perspective. My view was just the opposite because I have the lived experience, I needed to understand more and wanted to create change. As such, my positionality changes depending on which way that lens is used. I have been satisfied that throughout I have been reflective and have been reflexive and more over talk about sharing of vulnerability.

It is difficult to capture experiences of inequality and internalised racism, and sensitivity is essential when interviewing the participants. As Kohli emphasises, 'it takes trust and vulnerability to share something so personal' (2014, p.373). Furthermore, she refers to '*reciprocal vulnerability*' as a method:

Where the researcher shares personal experiences with oppression to establish collective and mutual trust...when the researcher can engage interviews as dialogues that involve openness and vulnerability from both sides.

I adopted this position when conducting my research, as I wanted to extend my understanding of minority ethnic teachers experiences. My positionality offered me the capacity to do this. I have a particular epistemological understanding, and I wanted to create new knowledge using the constructs of feminism, intersectionality, lived experience and not only that, I used paradigms that were constructo-interpretivist which helped me to understand and make meaning of the lived experiences. I believed this helped participants to be candid and comfortable during conversations and it served as a strength during the focus groups. Consequently, participants seemed more willing to discuss their experiences with me than they perhaps would with a white teacher/researcher. My evidence to illustrate this point comes from participants who respond, 'You know what I mean'. They said this several times which suggested that they considered me to be the 'insider' and as such, the focus group and semi-structured interviews became conversations between people who had experienced inequality.

Addressing vulnerability in pursuit of non-maleficence.

Corbin and Morse (2003) discuss the importance of supporting the participants in the event that they become distressed due to the nature of the topic. Two teachers were visibly upset. Kajol, during the focus group became quite upset but she then managed this by simply choosing not to talk about the aspects that distressed her. Leyla was distressed during the semi-structured interview; therefore, I was careful to begin with the key issues arising from the focus group she had attended and informed her that I had some additional questions to ask that may be difficult for her to discuss and that she could refrain from saying anything if she so wished. This was a helpful approach as it served two different objectives – first, it placed the participant in control of what was going to be discussed and second, it served to help prepare the participant emotionally to discuss sensitive issues (Dickson-Swift et al., 2009).

I am co-founder and chairperson of an organisation called SAMEE (Scottish Association of Minority Ethnic Educators) which provides support to minority ethnic teachers. Although only two teachers appeared to be visibly upset, the remainder could have felt anxious but managed to hide their emotions, therefore I signposted all participants to SAMEE. I do not feel there were any power relations because of my unique emic and etic perspectives: I was an insider who could be trusted, the participants knew about reciprocal vulnerability, and they could see that this study could further their voice and give them epistemic justice.

Chapter 4

Becoming a teacher – acknowledgment in a largely homogenous workforce

This chapter analyses the views and experiences of minority ethnic teachers in relation to research question 1: What are minority ethnic teachers' expectations of being and becoming a teacher? Participants were asked in the focus group 'why teaching?' I followed this up through the semi-structured interviews, asking participants to extend or build upon their reasons for their career choice. Data analysis showed a common theme illustrating influences on their decisions. The themed influences included: family, ethnicity, language and religion in the decisions of the participants in being and becoming a teacher. There was also a strong sense of contributing to society – giving back to their communities by sharing one's knowledge.

The analysis also revealed some divergence particularly in wanting to help children to learn in that the participant's own experience of inequality and marginalisation led them to choose teaching as a career. Introducing the participants, in line with the CRT framework, I used a counter-storytelling tool, to construct their narratives to help analyse both commonalities and expose the differences in the majority narrative when it came to ME teachers (Gayels, et al. 2015). The chapter is in three parts. It begins by exploring cultural factors which were discussed by the teachers, followed by the influence of religion on their decision to become teachers, and the importance of giving back to their students and society.

The influence of cultural factors

According to Wenting (2019), the motivations for people choosing teaching as a profession are often multi-dimensional, contextualised and individualised. The participants in my study spoke clearly about cultural factors, such as their family,

ethnicity and language influencing their decisions to become teachers. This section will consider these influences as narrated by the participants. The first question I asked participants was why they chose to teach as a career.

The case of Leyla

Leyla is an African-Caribbean, peripatetic, secondary school teacher in Glasgow who teaches Art. She has found it difficult to secure a permanent post and so does supply teaching across schools in Glasgow. She speaks about the influence her parents had on her choosing teaching as a career:

Both my parents were teachers in my home country. I, too, decided to follow in their steps as I like bringing the best out of people...even if I am not the best myself...When I moved to the UK, my teaching qualification was not accepted and my cultural upbringing encouraged me to work hard and pursue teaching and to embrace the challenges that came my way. I decided that, if I can be a teacher there, then I can be a teacher here, too. I decided to retrain.

(Leyla)

Here, Leyla, explains that she chose teaching so that she too, could follow in her parent's steps and pursue a career in the teaching profession. This aligned with a study conducted in New Zealand (Lovett, 2007) with first-career teachers who came from a teaching family, where one or both parents were teachers. The participants in that study, who were largely white and female, reported clearly that their decision was influenced by a family member who they regarded as an important role model. That study revealed that being around teachers allowed participants to acquire first-hand knowledge about the teaching profession and the life of a teacher and as such this became almost a pre-determined path like in the case of Leyla.

Leyla refers to her '*cultural upbringing*' motivating her to keep going despite the challenges. It is perhaps worth noting that in a study (Lovett, 2009) which examined the interplay among cultural factors in an ethnically diverse Asian American sample, which included teachers who identified as Pakeha, Maori and Pasifika, it was found that there was a tendency to live up to parental expectations and an interest in traditional occupations. Such occupational stereotypes continue to exist and portray Asian Americans as more competent in physical, biological, and medical sciences and less competent in verbal, persuasive, and social occupations (Huang, 2021). These stereotypes are problematic as they contribute to the occupational segregation found within the Asian American community. In this study figures from the U.S. Census Bureau (2011) data indicate that Asian Americans are traditionally overrepresented in science and technology fields and underrepresented in humanity and social service fields. This is also the case in Scotland, where the Scottish Census (2011) indicates that South Asians are more likely to choose careers in medicine, computing and engineering.

Shen et al. (2014) asked 229 Asian American students from universities nationwide to complete a demographic questionnaire and to rate 70 different occupations on the degree to which each was considered stereotypical. Results indicated that living up to parental expectations and internalized stereotyping partially mediated the associations between parental pressure and the three occupational outcomes mentioned above (medicine, computing and engineering).

This offers an explanation as to why Leyla is ready to '*embrace the challenges*'. Perhaps as a migrant, she is seeking social status and to be accepted as an equal to her peers. Both Leyla and her parents were educated in a different system, and this could suggest a lack in the 'appropriate' capital, knowledge or access to the social networks that could help Leyla to consider her options. Clearly, Leyla's cultural and linguistic capital was not of value in Scotland. Her ability to teach and assess children in her home country appears to be devalued with the General Teaching

Council (GTCS) acting in a fashion that could be described as discriminating. However, her self-determination and her sense of resilience and purpose meant that to overcome the setbacks she had experienced, she complied with the gatekeeping and retrained as a teacher with a teaching qualification that was accepted in Scotland.

Moreover, Flores and Niklasson (2014) state that family influence can enhance individuals' confidence by recognising their potential suitability for teaching. Perhaps Leyla's confidence is evident when she says that she likes '*bringing the best out of people*'. I interpreted this to mean that she has a genuine desire to work with people so that they can have a positive impact on wider society. This altruistic reason is commonly cited as a reason for becoming a teacher (Cross and Ndofirepi, 2015). Studies from across the world concur that the main reasons for choosing a teaching career fall into three dimensions: altruistic, intrinsic and extrinsic (Jimenez, 2019). Altruistic reasons view teaching as a socially valuable and important job, as can be noted from Leyla's response, '...related to improving society, for example, a desire to make a social contribution and to help young people reach their potential' (Struyven, Jacobs and Dochy, 2013 p.1009). Intrinsic motives refer to internal factors which suggest that one has an instinctive passion about teaching and genuinely enjoy working with children, which suggests some overlap with altruistic reasons. The extrinsic reasons cover aspects of the job which are seen as benefits – good salaries, good conditions of service and security of employment and the social status of teaching as a respected profession.

Interestingly, it would seem that Leyla is motivated by both altruistic and intrinsic reasons which informed her decision to retrain in the UK. Leyla was a qualified teacher in her home country but when she moved to Scotland her qualification was not recognised by the General Teaching Council in Scotland (GTCS). Despite the fact that ME teachers represent only 1.4% of the teacher workforce and that an expert steering group was set by the Scottish Government in response to this underrepresentation (Scottish Government, 2018), the GTCS, a body made up of a majority of white professionals, in this instance continues to act as a gatekeeper to

the profession by deciding who can and cannot register as a teacher in Scotland. Leyla's comment on '*bringing out the best in people*' whilst not believing or considering to be the best herself created an interesting juxtaposition. Here, Leyla is showing self-doubt because her qualification is not being recognised. When I probed further and asked why she did not consider herself to be the '*best*', she remarked:

I was constantly told that I looked different and talked differently...I have a strong African-Caribbean accent. They also asked if the children can understand me...

(Leyla)

These comments about being 'different' both visually and orally further reinforce her self-doubt and rejection, firstly, when her teaching qualification was not recognised and secondly, when she faced rejection on a regular basis by being told that she looked and sounded different. These experiences, resulting from lack of recognition of and value for what Leyla brings contribute to a low self-image. – When asked to explain who she was referring to as '*they*', she said '*my fellow teacher colleagues*'. In this sense, Leyla is constructed as the 'other' who is different from the mainstream teaching population. The fact that her qualification is not recognised in Scotland also reinforces this feeling of rejection she has experienced: you are good enough to be a teacher in your home country but not in Scotland. This was more concerning in colleagues making reference to her accent and skin colour and their raising questions about her capability to teach, doubting that '*... the children can understand me*'. Such questions raised around her capability to teach perhaps also stem from the rigid regulations that are set by the General Teaching Council in Scotland (GTCS) which, it could be argued, legitimise the questioning of capability of those who have not trained in the UK, although, it should be noted, those who are trained across Europe do not have these rules applied to them. (GTCS, 2018).

Whilst there may be reasons that might support the case for this for example, understanding the Scottish system and the structures within schools in Scotland. However, as referenced earlier, we live in an ethnically diverse Scotland, and it is important that our teaching workforce must reflect this diversity. So, why is it that it is continuously difficult for teachers who have qualified in their home countries to achieve registration without retraining. Perhaps an alternative route, such as an induction year could be one such way to support the recruitment of teachers from diverse ethnic backgrounds.

So, in Leyla's case, such negative comments around her cultural capital and her qualifications being rejected reinforce the point that BME teachers are marked out to be different and that their very presence invites such comments. Puwar (2004) argues that when people of colour enter spaces where they are not the 'somatic norm', not belonging to the majority White, their mere presence is questioned. Marked out to be different, they are 'space invaders' (p.11). From a critical race theory lens, institutional racism has become so embedded that these persuasive acts of 'othering' go unchecked and unnoticed as they are 'normalised' and as such, Leyla's white colleagues felt quite comfortable in making such discriminative comments (Wilkins and Lall, 2011) positioning her as the racialized outsider of the Scottish teaching profession based on physical markers and speech (Virdee,2014).

According to Bourdieu, capital refers to an accumulation of knowledge, skills, abilities and resources possessed and inherited by privileged groups in society (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977). Bourdieu asserts that:

Cultural capital (i.e., education, language), social capital (i.e., social networks, connections) and economic capital (i.e., money and other material possessions) can be acquired two ways, from one's family and/or through formal schooling.

(Yosso, 2012, p.9)

Yet, surprisingly, Leyla's cultural capital – her education and her language is regarded as a deficit because her qualifications and accent lie outside the majority norm. Perhaps this raises the questions: whose culture is valued and whose knowledge counts? Culture and language is problematic within the Scottish curriculum where the emphasis is given to European languages and the importance of learning in one plus two languages (Scottish Government, 2012). There is no reference nor value placed on ME young people's first language which is not English – Urdu Punjabi, Cantonese, Afrikaans. As such this is regarded as a deficit, a problem that requires additional support from English as an Additional Language teachers.

Bourdieu's (1986) theoretical insight about how a hierarchical society reproduces itself has often been interpreted as a way to explain why the academic and social outcomes of BME communities are significantly lower than the outcomes of Whites. There is an assumption that BME communities lack the necessary knowledge, social skills and abilities and cultural capital required for social mobility (Hooks, 1990; Solorzano and Delgado, 2001). Garcia and Guerra's (2004) research acknowledges this deficit thinking and argues that it permeates society and influences teachers' beliefs. Using CRT helps to challenge the traditional interpretations of cultural capital presented by Bourdieu (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977) as they do not go far enough to explain the juncture between class and race.

Bourdieu focuses primarily on class to explain inequalities that exist whereas CRT states racial injustice as a starting point. As such, it provides a lens that shifts the focus away from the deficit view of black and minority ethnic communities where their cultural capital often goes unrecognised and unacknowledged. Yosso (2012) introduces an alternative concept called community cultural wealth which outlines forms of capital which shift the focus from white middle-class culture to the cultures of communities from black and minority ethnic backgrounds:

Indeed, a CRT lens can 'see' that Communities of Color nurture cultural wealth through at least 6 forms of capital such as aspirational, navigational, social, linguistic, familial, and resistant capital (see Delgado Bernal, 1997, 2001; Auerbach, 2001; Stanton-Salazar, 2001; Solórzano & Delgado Bernal, 2001; Faulstich Orellana, 2003). These various forms of capital are not mutually exclusive or static, but rather are dynamic processes that build on one another as part of community cultural wealth.

(Yosso, 2012, p.10)

Aspirational capital is the ability to have hope despite the structured inequalities that exist and these aspirations are developed within familial contexts, often through advice and encouragement from parents. Clearly, in Leyla's case, she had hope and determination to retrain as a teacher in Scotland. In terms of her linguistic capital, Leyla felt that her colleagues regarded her strong African-Caribbean accent as a negative, yet CRT presents this as a positive offering added value in being bi/multilingual where one has the ability to speak in two or more languages in their daily lives (Baker and Wright, 2017). It is well documented that bilingual people have particular cognitive strengths and a strong metalinguistic awareness as they can use this capital to engage in the skills of storytelling, drawing on various language registers and have a strong cross-cultural awareness (Conteh, 2007; Fuente et al., 2020).

Although a fluent English speaker, and thus having linguistic capital, Leyla was othered by her colleagues based on her difference which was her accent and skin colour and not belonging to the Scottish teaching profession on their level, or ability to teach students effectively. This illustrated some of the barriers that Leyla had to overcome, whilst dealing with precarious contracts, and a 'when and if needed' approach by the council and the schools. This suggests that while policy asks for more diversity, Leyla's lived experiences and evidence, highlight gatekeeping with the teaching profession on who a 'real' teacher is and who is not. The questioning of identity and place is continued by Abu Zar in the next story.

The case of Abu-Zahr

Abu Zahr is a 52-year-old, British Asian male teacher who has been teaching Science for 15 years. When I asked him why he choose teaching as a career, he initially responded:

‘There is nothing more rewarding than actually changing someone’s attitude and the success you have... there is nothing more wonderful than sharing the joy of success’

(Abu-Zahr)

For Abu-Zahr, it was about having the opportunity to change ‘*someone’s attitudes*’ and enjoying the success of it and being able to share in the positive impact this had. This resonates with Leyla’s altruistic aspirations to improve society and make a valuable contribution through her teaching. For Abhu-Zahr, teaching would be his second career as he went on to share:

In my case, the mechanical companies collapsed, and I didn’t want to go back into engineering as I would have to go abroad, and I didn’t really want to travel. This is my home. So, it was either go open a shop (like my parents) or get careers advice. My mum and dad are totally illiterate; I am the only one in my entire family who has any kind of qualification. My dad used to always say that I would be a good role model for young Asian kids ...

Here Abu Zahr explains his reasons for entering the teaching profession due to the collapse of the telecommunications trade. To pursue his career in engineering he would have to relocate but his words ‘*this is my home*’ seemed to emphasise that he was not prepared to travel outside his current place of residence leaving him with two options. He could either seek careers advice or ‘open a *shop*’ like his parents.

He also makes reference to being the only member of his family who attended university and his father encouraging him to be a '*role model*' for other BME children. This shows that his reasons for becoming a teacher were more complex than his initial statement, about the rewarding nature of teaching children and helping them to challenge attitudes and share in their success. Abu-Zahr refers to his parents as '*totally illiterate*' and the manner in which he spoke about opening a shop like his parents, appeared to be quite dismissive. However, I interpreted this as his parents not having the acceptable social and linguistic capital which he infers through having his British education and qualifications.

Furthermore, perhaps Abu-Zahr perceives the shop as 'static' – a place where his parents are 'stuck' and he has chosen not to be 'stuck' and having the opportunity to explore his options. His parents perhaps had chosen to do this as they had no other option when they arrived in the country many years ago. They very quickly learned that their cultural capital was not acknowledged nor valued. Moreover, Abu Zahr appears to take a stereotypical view of his parents being illiterate and so they have a 'shop'. There is a cultural assumption that South Asian families, traditionally, have businesses that are referred to as the 'corner shop' and so these stereotypical representations of being 'illiterate' because their spoken English is not good, are reinforced. They, clearly, were not illiterate, but again this reflects Yosso's (2012) question on whose language is valued and whose knowledge is counted.

His parents showed capacity for financial acumen to set up a business and create the circumstances for their child to be given opportunities, which they did not get, unable to guide as they did not know the system or have the requisite knowledge or skills to advise on career choices. Interestingly, Abu Zahr in his earlier comments about why he chose teaching as a career referred to '*changing attitudes*' yet, here we note that his own attitude towards his family and their business does not mirror what he says. He is negative and appears to reinforce the stereotype. Kohli (2014) refers to this as 'internalised racism' where discrimination and stereotypical misrepresentation go unchallenged and so young people internalise this and are therefore less likely to challenge it later in their lives.

There is a lack of recognition and dismissal by Abu Zhar of his parents' ability or contribution in his life or their life and employment choices. He feels he has done more to contribute to making a change in students' lives through his teaching practice. The deficit discourse illustrates how he does not see his parents as being able to support him effectively to make the right choices. Whereas in the following case study, Khurram, whose parents also became shopkeepers, discusses his relationship with them in a more positive manner.

The case of Khurram

Aspects of Khurram's experience resonated with both Leyla's and Abu-Zahr's. Khurram is a 48-year-old, British Asian, male secondary school teacher with 18 years of teaching experience. When asked about his reasons for becoming a teacher, he replied:

My dad was a headmaster but when he came to this country, his qualification wasn't worth what it was, and he ended up with a shop. My mum was a support teacher and they kind of come from that background, but strangely they never really told me that's what they did back in Pakistan until later.

(Khurram)

Khurram's father's qualification was not accepted in the UK and so perhaps this was the reason why they did not share their previous careers with Khurram. The fact that it was not recognised meant it had no value, so they '*ended up with a shop*'. This was quite typical of many South Asian families who arrived in the 1960s, when the only jobs available were the low skilled and low-paid jobs as they could not occupy the same spaces as the 'middle-class' (Lahiri, 2017), despite belonging to it when

they lived in South Asia. Like Abhu-Zahr's parents, Khurram's parents' set-up their own businesses and wanted to provide security for their families. As such, this had an impact on Khurram's aspirations for life to have a different skill set which would allow him to be more than a shopkeeper. This further reinforces that parental aspirations are key in making decisions about career choices – South Asian parents direct their children to particular careers, such as doctors, engineers, lawyers and accountants in order to avoid the struggles they had to endure long hours, no social lives and no time for family (Fouad, et. al, 2015). Perhaps this speaks to the internalised racism discussed earlier – the negative connotations associated with being a shopkeeper.

Like Abu-Zahr, teaching was a second career for Khurram. He goes on to say:

So, initially, I became a software engineer and worked as a trainer in Sky TV, and that was a job I really loved, ye know, training people. I have a lot of nieces and nephews who got me to help them with their studying and then my family and friends said to me 'oh, you'd make a great teacher' which made me start thinking, ye know, 'really?'... and the more I thought about it I thought you know, why not go ahead with it...

Interestingly, despite expressing passionately how much he enjoyed training people and helping his family learn, this response to comments such as '*oh, you'd make a great teacher*' shows surprise: '*really?*'. Questioning this expresses a level of self-doubt that he may not have overcome if his family and friends had not made the initial comment about making a great teacher. Or on the other hand, this response could be interpreted as being quite thrilled that he may have found a career but questioning if he has the skills to be a teacher, and then deciding to go with it and find out. There is an inherent recognition of what professional skills Khurram will bring to teaching.

This section has discussed family and language as two cultural factors that influenced the participants' experiences of becoming a teacher. The next section discusses how religion was suggested as influential on participant choices and to go into school teaching as a career.

The influence of Religion

The case of Yetunde

A study of student teachers carried out in Turkey revealed that the majority of students chose teaching as they were influenced by altruistic–intrinsic reasons (Balyer and Ozcam, 2014). Most of the student teachers came from deprived, lower-educated families who lived in villages and their parents sent them to universities close by as they could not afford to pay for accommodation. These students stated that they chose teaching as a career to overcome the economic difficulties their families faced. Moreover, the research found that a lot of student teachers considered teaching as a 'blessed' profession (Balyer and Ozcam, p,110). This may stem from the perception of teaching in the historical process where in the ancient civilisations of the Sumerians, Egyptians, Israelis and later in Muslim societies teaching is considered as one of the most blessed professions (Sonmez, 2010). In my study, religion was also frequently cited as an early influence on career choice.

Yetunde is a 44-year-old, African-Caribbean female teacher who had 8 years of teaching experience. She follows the religion of Christianity. When I asked her for her reasons to become a teacher, she made reference to her faith:

I am a Christian and my faith also advocates preaching and sharing knowledge and I guess, my love for teaching came from my childhood when I attended Sunday school.

(Yetunde)

Here, Yetunde makes clear reference to the advocacy nature of her faith in terms of disseminating knowledge and giving sermons and she goes further to say that her 'love for teaching' was sparked by attending Sunday school. This could suggest that she may have been influenced by her Sunday school teacher and that perhaps this positivity stemmed from the Sunday school teacher's teaching style, as such, providing a tentative link between her love for teaching and her faith. Given her initial response, I asked her why she did not train to teach in a Roman Catholic school. Yetunde laughed and replied:

It was a struggle to get to interview stage with the universities...I remember applying over a period of three years, I'm convinced they didn't look past my name and on top of that, my qualifications were not from here but from Ghana ... they would likely reject my application. I would love to teach in such school but to apply for a certificate to teach in a Roman Catholic school would just have been another battle – anyways, I guess just because I'm a Christian and have strong faith doesn't mean that I should only teach in a faith school...I am happy to teach in any school as the principles are the same – using what I know to encourage the children to think and question their place in the world?

(Yetunde)

Yetunde has highlighted in her response the challenges she faced to be accepted onto an ITE programme and refers to her name and previous qualifications being a barrier. I interpreted this to mean that she is well aware of the systemic structures that govern ITE institutions and seemed to understand why her application was rejected many times – the entry requirements emphasise UK qualifications and conscious and unconscious bias by admissions officers is likely to prevent applicants that do not meet those requirements from being selected (EIS, 2018; Scottish Government, 2018).

As stated earlier, Yetunde's qualifications from Ghana will not have been accepted by the regulatory body which acts as a gatekeeper in terms of who enters the teaching workforce in Scotland. Much has been reported on the recruitment of teachers in Scotland, and the numbers continue to highlight that teachers from minority ethnic groups selected for an ITE programme remain very low (CRER, 2018). Moreover, research demonstrates that it is not that BME individuals do not apply but that they experience barriers when they apply. This highlights the need to confront institutional and cultural barriers to diversity and to address racial discrimination (Scottish Government, 2018).

It is important to note that Yetunde makes reference to '*...another battle*', that she would have faced had she applied to gain a teaching certificate qualifying her to teach in a Roman Catholic school in Scotland. To teach in a Roman Catholic school in Scotland, student teachers are required to seek a certificate from their Priest to confirm that their faith informs their daily life (Scottish Charter for Catholic Schools, 2016). Recently, the Scottish Catholic Education Service (2020) presented a paper at Scottish Parliament in which there were fourteen recommendations to improve the recruitment of newly qualified teachers into Roman Catholic schools. However, not one recommendation discussed the lack of diversity in terms of ethnicity – rather the focus was on entry qualifications and the Catholic Teacher Certificate. This sends a clear message that BME teachers are not considered and remain invisible (Anujla-Bhullar, 2018). This further reinforces the ongoing challenge of a BME teacher's presence in both non-denominational schools and Roman Catholic Schools – the 'fitting in': Yetunde's name and the colour her of skin will serve as a racialized marker that place her outside institutional belongingness, with her very presence challenging the continued domination of institutions of whiteness (Daniel, 2019).

Despite this, Yetunde's final comment expresses her view around the principles that underpin her faith where she states, '*I am happy to teach in any school as the principles are the same – using what I know to encourage the children to think and question their place in the world?*' I interpreted this to mean that she considers that her faith will still support her teaching in a non-denominational school as it is about

drawing on common principles to explore how one exists in the world. Matemba (2020) argues that scholarship and classroom discourse in religious education is about 'gazing back and moving forward' whereby exploring histories, traditions and beliefs of religions help to engage learners in critical discussions about learning from the past to inform the future (p.155).

The case of Mumta and Shaista

Mumta is 60-years old and has been teaching for over twenty years. She is from India and follows the religion of Hinduism. When I asked her about her career choice, she, too, stated that her faith influenced her decision:

When I used to go to the Mandir (temple) as a child, I loved learning. When I started university, I ran a class at the temple for my fellow peers and knew that I was good at explaining things.

(Mumta)

Like Yetunde, Mumta also commented on attending her place of worship from a young age. The comment that followed 'I loved learning' seemed to suggest that she was referring to the learning related to Hinduism - again associating learning with faith. She also mentions taking a class at the Mandir (temple) and that perhaps in doing so, she developed a good approach to teaching by making the learning more accessible through 'explaining things' well.

Like Mumta, Shaista also spoke about how her faith influenced her decision to become a teacher. She is a 40-year-old British Asian female and has been teaching for sixteen years; she is a Muslim and follows the religion of Islam.

In my head, I'm thinking from a religious perspective – I studied Biology at university, and I wanted to share Allah's creation with young people to say, look how amazing the human body is...education is in line with Islam as it is all about seeking knowledge and teaching others...

(Shaista)

Here Shaista talks about the science degree she studied at university and draws parallels with her faith by referring to '*Allah's creation*' and studying the anatomy of the human body (in the Islamic faith, Allah refers to 'God'). Moreover, she mentions that she wanted to share this knowledge with young people and reinforces her belief that '*education is in line with Islam*' as it is about learning and teaching.

The case of Nafeesah and Yusuf

The influence of faith in choosing teaching as a career was also discussed by Yusuf and Nafeesah. Yusuf is a 55-year-old Pakistani male who has 25 years teaching experience and Nafeesah is a 34-year-old British Asian female who has been teaching for eleven years. Like Shaista, they both also discuss how teaching and learning is an important aspect of Islam:

In Islam, teaching is a fundamental part of learning anyway and helping people to improve their lives. So, I feel from that angle teaching is quite a natural profession for Muslims because you are either learning or teaching.

(Yusuf)

I wanted to be a teacher, there were lots of Asian kids in my class who struggled, and I used to help them...also as a Muslim, education is something which is very much valued ...

(Nafeesah)

Yusuf talks about teaching as a '*natural profession for Muslims*' whereby teaching and helping others is a core part of his Islamic faith. He further adds that this aspect of his faith is about '*helping people to improve their lives*'. Interestingly, Nafeesah also holds similar views in that she wished to support the '*Asian kids*' in her class '*who struggled*' and that this desire, to help, stemmed from her faith, '*as a Muslim, education is something which is valued*'. She does not say why the ME children in her class struggled nor does she explain how she 'helped' them. However, this could suggest that she is reflecting on her own experience as a child where perhaps she may not have had teachers who looked like her and can appreciate the impact that this had on her and would therefore want to support, simply by her mere presence (Kohli and Pizarro, 2016; Kohli, 2018; Daniel, 2019).

Research conducted with minority ethnic teachers found that many join teaching to fight injustice by supporting the educational experience of minority ethnic young children to enhance the transformational experiences of their communities which they felt were lacking in their own schooling (Irizarry and Donaldson, 2012, Kohli and Pizarro, 2016). Both Yusuf and Nafeesah were clear that their faith had an influence on their career choice, but they further added the desire to '*improve*' the lives of the '*Asian kids*' who '*struggled*'. The following two cases build on this theme of giving back to their communities.

Giving back to their communities

The case of Khashif and Kasim

The theme of giving back was also identified as the data was coded. As stated earlier, altruistic reasons view teaching as a socially valuable and important job which values their communities' cultural wealth rather than seeing it as a deficit

(Yosso, 2005, Little, 2020). Yosso coined the phrase 'community cultural wealth' to explain how CRT helps to shift the lens away from ME communities seen as being disadvantaged by not having English as their first language and by engaging in cultural practices that differ from the 'norm' and instead focus on the cultural knowledge and skills they bring. This form of capital draws on what ME young people bring from their communities and homes into the classroom (Little, 2020).

This can be seen in the case of Khashif, a 35- year old British Asian male who has been teaching for ten years:

Teaching was never in the forefront of my mind, but when I was growing up, I saw BME kids in my class who were not being supported well and I wanted to help them –I would say a few things in Punjabi, and they would get it... my parents encouraged me to think about this further...

(Khashif)

Kashif explains that he did not consider teaching as a career, at first, but reflecting on his own experiences of school, there were many BME children who he describes as "*not being supported well*" and that he wanted to "*help them*". He did this by speaking to and explaining things to his peers in their first language, Punjabi, and said "*they would get it*". I interpreted this to mean two things: firstly, it could suggest that he found a way to connect with his peers by their first language (Punjabi) thus giving value to it. Secondly, he wanted to help them understand what they were learning and so drew on '*Punjabi*' to help make sense of the English (Baker, 2011). This process is referred to as code switching where a bilingual person will switch from one language to another seamlessly to take advantage of the language repertoires that are available to them (Grieve and Haining, 2011; Little, 2020).

In Khashif's case, it was switching from English to Punjabi. Perhaps, this was necessary due to the lack of support that he was referring to in terms of teachers

who did not have the language to support nor the realisation that they should provide a more tailored response for the young people. This would be further increased by a lack of cultural awareness and understanding of second language acquisition as much research has shown that teachers do not understand what this means and view a first language as a deficit and problematic (Foley, Sangster and Anderston, 2013).

Similarly, Kasim who is a 46-year-old, British Asian male teacher with twelve years of teaching pointed out:

I wanted to make a difference to ethnic minorities, that was one of the reasons, I don't know why, it was just something in me, you know, Em..., my dad always made sure I listened to the news and all the rest of it, and there was injustices happening even....Bosnia and that, and I was always involved in school...sorry University, I was on BBC talking about the Bosnian issue, and it really infuriates me when they actually, ye know, cut an important part that I was talking about.

(Kasim)

Here Kasim, states that he wanted to help and '*make a difference*' for BME young people. He also says that he did not know why but that '*it was something in me*' and perhaps his next statement may help to unpack what this '*something*' in him was. He mentions that his dad ensured that he kept up to date with the news and '*...all the rest of it*'. So, I interpreted this to mean that his interest in the news helped him to recognise the injustices taking place across the world from a very young age. The support from his parents is also evident from this as he discusses the Bosnia crisis on TV. Kasim reflects upon the time he was on TV for a discussion, and a section had been edited from his interview and this attempt to 'sensor' the information being aired angered him. So, for Kasim, there appear to be early signs that he was quite active in challenging inequalities and taking on a role that would support BME

communities. Passion for activism is evident and a desire for himself and his students to question the dominant narratives.

The reasons for becoming teachers the participants in the study articulated were sound and fairly typical: '*rewarding*'; '*changing attitudes*'; '*helping people to learn*'. Their responses further indicated that their aspirations were the on the whole, similar to many who choose teaching as a career. However, there are also clear indications that there are additional aspects that need to be considered further. Both Leyla's and Yetunde's experiences highlight that their ethnicity appeared to be a barrier and that their cultural capital was seen as 'cultural poverty' (Yosso, 2005, p,69) with comments on Leyla's accent and her qualifications not being accepted. This was also true of Yetunde with her initial lack of success gaining access to an ITE programme.

The extant literature on teacher identity fails to draw on the experiences of BME teachers and this can be seen in the work of Craig (2013) who states that teachers should bring their 'best-loved self' to their teaching and this is further reinforced by Hong et al (2018, p.who argue that schools should actively recruit teachers who are both 'willing and able to bring their best intellectual and emotional commitments to work if they are to serve their students well'. So, there appears to be a bland assumption that this literature speaks to teachers who are white and from the majority ethnic and who can draw from the same intellectual and emotional experiences to inform their teaching. It is also important to consider the language used in reference to being willing and able to bring their best selves – in the case of Leyla, we can see that the willingness is there but that she is not enabled to be herself as her accent and ethnicity are not considered to be normal, not fitting into the homogeneous workforce.

One of the five tenets of critical race theory, white supremacy, helps us to understand a system of privilege that prevails (Bhopal, 2018). This allows the white privilege to manifest in subtle and more covert ways and those classified as white

benefit from it and are enabled to bring their 'best –selves' into their teaching without fear of discrimination but those classified as other are harmed by it. Moreover, Leyla's experience would perhaps suggest that she may be expected to assimilate into the majority culture, and in doing so, subsume aspects of her personal identity (Giroux, 2015). Where minority ethnic teachers are not prepared to do this, or again in Leyla's case, where she cannot change her accent, they are viewed as 'space invaders, out of place' and therefore struggle to find a sense of belonging in schools (Purwar, 2004, p.11). This then raises the following question: If the reasons why people come into teaching are quite similar then why is the experience of minority ethnic teachers so different? Why is it that minority ethnic teachers only represent 1.4% of the teacher workforce in Scotland and what is the difficulty in recruiting more minority ethnic teachers into the workforce? (Scottish Government, 2018).

Research has evidenced that a supportive environment assists individuals at different times of their professional careers because it gives them the help both emotionally and practically that enables them to survive (Guarino, Santibanez and Daley, 2006). This support, Leahy (2012) believes, is needed throughout a teacher's career to help them manage the complexities of the personal and professional life. Woods and Weasmer (2002) state that collegiality enhances job satisfaction for teachers, which sadly did not extend to Leyla.

Galchoir, Flaherty and Hinchion (2018) argue that the journey to becoming a teacher is complex and often conflicting for many. However, it has been noted earlier that the literature around teacher identity often excludes the experiences of minority ethnic Teachers and so the challenges that they face are further compounded because of their ethnicity (Slay and Smith, 2010). Sachs (2016) places importance on the individuals' understanding of how to be or how to act as a teacher but again there is no reference nor acknowledgement given to the experiences of teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds.

Summary

The participants discussed some of the reasons that influenced their decisions to become teachers. Firstly, they shared how cultural factors such as family and language encouraged them to pursue teaching. Secondly, for some of the participants, religion was also an influence as they related it to the act of teaching and learning to make a difference in children's lives. There was also a strong sense of contributing to society and giving back to their communities by sharing one's knowledge. Overall, the reasons provided by the participants in this study were fairly typical – family member who is a teacher: it is rewarding; the idea of changing attitudes and helping people to learn. Despite this, some of the participants acknowledged that their ethnicity appeared to present additional challenges to being accepted. ME teachers in this study can arguably be driven to become teachers in the same ways as their white colleagues but yet they continue to experience inequalities which are oppressive and encourage assimilation.

Minority ethnic teachers did not see themselves in the frame and this is evident in a key text recommended for ITE students and teachers alike, 'Scottish Education', which features white teachers on the front cover (Bryce et al, 2018). This is problematic as it was published after the Scottish Government working group convened to discuss the underrepresentation of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2021). As such, finding a teacher identity in a largely homogenous workforce continues to be challenging for someone who is different, and this is discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter 5

Affirmation - finding a teacher identity

Chapter four established that research participants came into teaching for reasons that would be routinely expected. This did not tell me anything new about why minority ethnic teachers come into teaching. However, they identified that despite commonality in decisions to become a teacher, all participants felt that they were persistently treated differently. Examining the theme of teacher identity, this chapter responds to this concern into two core areas to show understanding how minority ethnic teachers find a sense of belonging and then, to better understand the discriminatory challenges that participants reported as happening on a regular and routine basis.

The literature review raised concern around teachers' professional identities. This highlighted that teacher identity is a complex mix of both personal and professional selves (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004; Day and Gu, 2014), where becoming a teacher is grounded in the interaction between each teacher's beliefs, norms and values and their understanding of teaching and learning theories. The literature review also identified a lack of research on professional identity construction, among minority ethnic teachers. This suggested a need to consider the complexities of processes in identity construction among Minority Ethnic Teachers, as they begin and continue to wrestle with questions such as 'who am I as a teacher?' and 'what kind of teacher do I want to become?' (Beijaard and Meijer, 2017, p.177). This chapter examines some of the challenges participants said they had experienced while trying to construct their professional identities.

Factors impacting on sense of belonging

When asked about their experiences of becoming a teacher, participants described how they felt as 'the outsider' across their career trajectories: from their teacher

training, their probationary period as a Newly Qualified Teacher (NQT), their own self-image as teachers, and as an experienced teacher within a school. This chapter will consider each of these stages and explore the challenges BME teachers faced in becoming teachers.

Minority Ethnic teachers' ideas on the identity of the student teacher and newly qualified teacher

Given that minority ethnic teachers currently represent 1.6% of the Scottish Teaching workforce, it was not surprising to hear from a few participants about their experiences of being the only minority ethnic student teacher within their cohort, during their teacher training:

I was the only male BME student in my time and boy that went down a shock during school experience.

(Khurram)

I walked into the staff room and it was as though I had fallen out of the sky... are **you** (this was emphasised) the student teacher?" asked the Class Teacher'

(Abhu - Zahr)

I was the only BME student teacher in an all white staff room and when I arrived for my first placement experience, I suddenly thought, I don't think this is the place for me.

(Mumta)

The three participants above completed their teaching education over fifteen years ago. From Khurram's presence as a '*shock*' exemplified by the class teacher's

question to Abu-Zahr '*are you the student teacher?*' is very telling that the mere presence of BME teachers was rare. Ahmed (2007, p.156) asserts that 'space acquires the shape of the bodies that inhabit them' so where the dominant ethnicity of teachers is white in Scotland, institutional spaces are shaped by this 'skin'. Moreover, reinforcing teaching as a mono-cultural and mono-linguistic profession for white females (Arshad, 2021).

Moreover, Mumta, beginning to think '*that this is not the place for me*' is evidence that she began to question her sense of belonging and that her image as a teacher was clearly not mirrored widely. The drive to diversify the profession in Scotland has been a battle that spans over three decades and as there were very few teachers from BME communities in schools at the time Mumta was a student teacher, she felt she was in unfamiliar territory. Puwar's (2004) words where minority ethnic teachers are seen as 'space invaders', entering a space which has been occupied by predominantly, white, female teachers and so, deemed to be 'trespassers' as they are not considered to be the norm (p.8).

Moreover, Samera, who is currently a newly qualified teacher in her probationary period, talks about her experience at university fifteen years on from when Khurram, Abu-Zahr and Mumta completed their teacher education in 2005. She explains how this stage started to shape her identity as a student teacher:

... being the only Muslim female was quite difficult because I didn't really have anyone else to share my experiences with and reflecting back, I would say that I lost quite a lot of my own personal, Islamic identity whilst being at university because it was very hard to assert that...it felt very much, that I had to adopt a whole new different sort of culture and I felt that teaching was a culture rather than a part of who I was. It wasn't really a job but more a lifestyle, it was so encompassing, full on. I don't think there was any one point, during school experiences, until the last placement that I could push my own identity... it was very hard. It felt like I was going against the tide.

(Samera)

It would appear that over the past few decades' things have not changed much in terms of the number of minority ethnic students in teacher education programmes (Scottish Government, 2021). Samera completed her teacher education a year before our interview and was the only minority ethnic student teacher within her cohort. She spoke about losing her Islamic identity while she was at university and finding it difficult to assert her Islamic self in what she described as adopting culture that was not part of her existing identity. For Samera, becoming part of that culture represented a troublesome and significant lifestyle change. In trying to fit in with this teacher culture, she had subsumed aspects of her personal identity, namely her religion.

As a newly qualified teacher, Samera's commitment to teaching appeared to be a real challenge. Yet, she was prepared to give up her religious identity because she felt isolated as the only minority ethnic student in her class, who '*...didn't have anyone else to share my experiences*', which suggested a lack of appropriate support to introduce her to the new teacher culture. In this sense, Samera's experiences led to an understanding that '*teaching was a culture rather than part of who I was*' which reinforced concerns about the idea of space invaders, operating within a dominant monocultural and homogenous teacher workforce. Samera's metaphor of '*... going against the tide*' indicated that there was little or no acknowledgement of the potential contribution of her cultural and religious beliefs, and that differences were to be subsumed as less important aspects of her personal identity to adopt the dominant 'culture' of teaching'.

This presented an interesting perspective aligned with earlier research that indicated schools that often give out messages to young children about leaving their culture outside the school gates (Cummins, 2000; Arshad et al., 2004). Samera's comments

affirm that this message is also communicated to minority ethnic student teachers attending ITE institutions. In her report 'Teaching in a Diverse Scotland', Arshad (2018) makes a number of recommendations on valuing the cultural and linguistic skills of minority ethnic teachers. From Samera's experience it is interesting to note that a teacher culture is prevalent in ITE which plays a significant role in how minority ethnic teachers are positioned.

Drawing on critical race theory, it is this, not seeing, nature of whiteness, where white ITE tutors are unable to interrogate their own assumptions, to acknowledge, nurture and celebrate the diverse identities of their ME student teachers and so continue to reinforce such perspectives (Matias and Grosland, 2016). Moreover, Lander and Santoro (2017) undertook in-depth qualitative interviews investigating the experiences of Black and Minority Ethnic teacher educators working within the predominately white space of the academy, in England and Australia. They wanted to explore how their participants', race and ethnicity shaped their experiences in Teacher Education Programmes. The findings revealed that both English and Australian minority ethnic academics were positioned as 'outsiders' in the academy and reported experiencing complex and subtle forms of racism from colleagues and students. They felt at times hyper visible and at other times invisible. So where minority ethnic teacher educators are viewed as bodies out of place it is not surprising that minority ethnic student teachers feel they do not belong. Moreover, Puwar suggests that the space invader is a body that does not fit well within the institution and the very presence of an minority ethnic teacher 'jolts the worldview' and so reconfirms the whiteness of that space (Purwar, 2004, p,43).

Samera shared that in her final placement she was able to '*push her own identity*' but still found this to be challenging. This suggests that she had grown in confidence and was more comfortable to assert her identity or it could perhaps be linked to having a more supportive environment and colleagues. When probed further and asked what she meant about '*pushing her own identity*... she explained:

Just being the only one, I think not having anyone recognising or appreciating that you are slightly different or that your needs and requirements are a little bit different from other people. Not that you want any special treatment and that is not anything that I would request or ask for but I think that just identifying that I may have, you know different issues involved, so probably to that extent I would try to push...eh...yeah, I don't think people appreciate that you feel very much alone when you come from a different culture, different background.

(Samera)

Striving for her colleagues to recognise her ethnicity and culture, it is interesting when she remarks: '*I think not having anyone recognising or appreciating that you are slightly different*' makes her feel isolated. It is important to consider her choice of words – looking for some recognition and appreciation that her experiences may be different and as such requires more tailored support. What is concerning is that she states that she doesn't want any '*any special treatment*'. Furthermore, she makes reference to a '*culture of school*' which I interpreted to mean that she feels she has to assimilate and adopting this school culture' - a particular identity, one perhaps informed by a monocultural white identity where her cultural identity has no recognition. Kohli (2021) uses the counter narratives of minority teachers to challenge the normalcy of an overwhelmingly white teaching force and highlights the institutional structures that function to side-line minority ethnic teachers.

Moreover, it is suggested that teachers' professional identities are in 'a state of flux', whereby there is a strong correlation between a teacher's professional identity and retention in the career (Chong et al. 2011). Chong et al's (2011) study included 105 graduating teachers and focused on their emerging professional identities. They argued that the experiences and perceptions of student teachers' professional identity 'depend on how they view themselves as teachers before they begin teaching and whether this is challenged or 'shattered' by the context of their preparation' (p.50). The demography of the sample did not include ethnicity.

However, as the accounts of the participants in my study indicate, in the case of minority ethnic student teachers this process of becoming a teacher presents a more complex and intersectional experience.

Prior to starting a teacher education programme, student teachers have different perceptions of teaching, and they only begin to see themselves as teachers once they start their teacher education programme. However, their own school experiences have an impact on these perceived images and as such, inform their attitudes, professional beliefs and their practice in the classroom. Moreover, O'Gallchoir, O'Flaherty and Hinchion (2018) explored the experiences of seven pre-service teachers as they understood what becoming a teacher means for them. Data was gathered using autobiographical narratives and video clips of their practice on placement. Their findings suggested that pre-service teachers are initially drawn to the physical depiction of what a teacher looks like and as their placement in schools progressed there was an emerging dissonance that challenged their ongoing identity construction. The participant in this study included a 60:40 ratio of male and female pre-service teachers and there was no diversity in terms of ethnicity.

Similarly, Wahid, who was a student teacher two years ago, and Pooja, who graduated four years ago, both recalled the challenges they each faced:

I remember other students looking at me, it was hard not to. I was the only BME student in my cohort and to top it off, I also had a beard... I could almost feel, what I can only describe as, the 'suspicious stares' I received from my peers...I guess for me, it was a double whammy – Black and Muslim!

(Wahid)

Being on placement was not enjoyable – I could do nothing right. I constantly sought feedback but it was not forthcoming and so I was left not knowing how to improve my teaching. I couldn't quite put my finger on it. My tutor observed

my teaching and found it to be satisfactory but the class teacher marked me unsatisfactory for every category...I tried to challenge this at University by asking my tutor for support, I even went to the Dean only to be told that their partnership with the school was important and that they would not question the teacher's assessment of my teaching.

(Pooja)

Wahid's comment about his peers looking at him and his description of almost palpable '*suspicious stares*' reflects his feelings of what he refers to as a '*double whammy*' aligned with being both Black and Muslim. Wahid shows awareness of being in the minority because of his ethnicity and also because of his faith. Crenshaw (1989) refers to this as double discrimination and coined the term 'intersectionality' where multiple forms of inequality are compounded to create further obstacles.

Meanwhile, Pooja discusses how placement was fraught with tensions with her reference to '*I could do nothing right*', and the lack of support for developing practice. She also found herself trying to understand her experience – '*I couldn't quite put my finger on it*'. I wondered whether this could be Pooja questioning her Class Teacher's intentions, in line with Maylor's (2009) research which has shown that some teachers exhibit unintentional racism towards students from minority ethnic backgrounds. This also aligns with Bhopal and Rhamie (2013) who reported that BME student teachers have negative experiences at school where they feel isolated, receiving little support and encouragement. The participants in Bhopal and Rhamie's study (2013) also reported teachers holding stereotypical attitudes towards them and a 'sense of being treated differently from their white peers' (p.308).

Pooja also mentioned that her tutor on the ITE programme was supportive which resonates with Wilkins and Lall's (2011) research where respondents commented positively on the support received from their ITE institution. Yet, Pooja also mentioned the reluctance of the University Dean to challenge the school's report,

despite the tutor's satisfactory report, for fear of spoiling the school partnership. Combining Pooja's description of what happened with important insight from Smith and Lander (2012) into how whiteness operates to reinforce inequitable power relations in teaching in ITE and schools, suggested that issues of 'race' and anti-racism need to be addressed on ITE programmes. This is further reinforced by Arshad (2018, p.193) when she states, 'The twenty-first century teacher needs to engage with race and racism'.

Hong et al. (2018) undertook research with twenty-two pre-service teachers to explore the construction of early career teachers' identities. Six teachers were then interviewed to consider how they managed the challenges they faced within their pre-service period. The findings concluded that the construction of positive or negative professional identities was intimately linked to participants' coping mechanisms which included not only their own commitment but also the support they received from the school setting. It was interesting to note that the teachers in that study all identified as Caucasian. The challenges and tensions identified were centred on daily working conditions and routines and their development of professional skills - the experiences of minority ethnic teachers were not considered.

The participants' experiences both prior to and during their initial teacher training coupled with their personal beliefs and experiences help to inform teachers' professional identities. Friedman states that beginning teachers may experience 'praxis shock' when there is inconsistency between their expectations of what happens in schools and the realities of teaching (Friedman, 2004, as cited in Day et al. 2005, p.52). It is important then to consider the extent to which this 'praxis shock' impacts on minority ethnic teachers' identity construction. The participants in this study commented on the assimilatory practices within ITE institutions and that they felt inadequately prepared to deal with the prevailing school cultures which emphasise a socially constructed normative teacher identity (Alsup, 2006). Over two decades ago Bullough (1997) wrote:

What beginning teachers believe about teaching and learning as self-as-teacher is of vital concern to teacher education; it is the basis for meaning making and decision making...Teacher education must begin, then, by exploring the teaching self.

(p.21).

Chong et al., (2011) argue that student teachers should be encouraged to not only focus on their beliefs and abilities but also on developing their identities as teachers and their aspirations. Earlier research also states that the construction of professional identity during teacher training and the probationary period is essential as this can influence and inform student teachers if they are suited to the profession (Schempp, Sparkes & Templin, 1999). Further research highlights the mismatch between ITE practices and school realities and offers recommendations to bridge the theory-practice gap, including a shift of the focus from knowledge and skills to the process of becoming a teacher within both school placements and universities supporting the development of student teachers' identities (Danielewicz, 2001; Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004). However, as stated earlier, these studies did not make any reference to teachers' ethnicities.

My analysis thus far has revealed that ethnicity impacts the factors influencing professional identity construction for BME teachers and as such, negotiating the process differs significantly from that of their White colleagues. Minority ethnic teachers professional knowledge is shaped by their own schooling experiences where their histories, languages and culture have been devalued, they find themselves having to stand up to the dominant structures that question their place in school. I argue that minority ethnic student teachers' emerging identity is already full of conflict and tension for two main reasons: firstly, they fail to find a sense of belonging during their initial teacher education where the 'self' is not explored fully and secondly, as probationers they face further challenges where they are isolated and encouraged to assimilate into the majority culture subsuming aspects of their personal identities (Kohli, 2014).

Newly Qualified Teacher

Samera shares her experience of being an NQT.

As a NQT, you think about the needs of the school and the needs of the children before your own needs but unfortunately or fortunately, you are also a person who has needs as well so, I need to have time to pray...people really not understanding my culture and my background and accepting that I may have different needs...it feels like there is a *culture* of school (said in an exaggerated tone), there is no culture of identifying that people will have individual needs ... I don't think that I have seen that in any of the schools ...this concern for individual teachers, it's all about the school. I feel everyone is under pressure and as a NQT you appreciate that other people have got other concerns... I am definitely not their concern.

(Samera)

Samera refers to pressure at work and acknowledges that other NQT's will have their concerns too, so perhaps this could suggest that the environment is not supportive enough for all teachers but what perhaps is alarming is when Samera states indignantly, '*I am definitely not their concern*'. This acknowledges that NQTs face pressure as it is a very intense year but that perhaps she felt that it was more complex for her as she was not only an NQT but a teacher who was looking for someone to acknowledge that she was different, in terms of her ethnicity and culture and that perhaps this recognition validates her presence. Her use of '*definitely*' further emphasises a sense of being marginalised and further adds to the view already expressed, that her needs were not acknowledged. Arguably, this leads to the conclusion that, if minority ethnic teachers do not fit into this culture of school, if you are not the norm, namely white, monocultural and monolingual then you are deemed to be out of place (Puwar, 2004),

Based on the accounts of the participants in my study, I would also argue that Alsop's (2006), use of the term 'borderland discourse' to describe the stage from being student to becoming a teacher and the importance of respecting personal beliefs and commitments while embodying a teacher identity is not helpful to minority ethnic teachers. In the extant literature, the case of minority ethnic teachers and respect of personal beliefs and passions has not been explored nor have the challenges been acknowledged. Their cultural experiences are not valued and their beliefs are often questioned with suspicion (Gillborn, 2008; Kohli, 2014). The lack of diverse teachers in Scotland, where 1.4% of the workforce are from a minority ethnic background, means, that student teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds are highly unlikely to have been taught by a minority ethnic teacher and so their image of what a teacher looks like, may be an obstacle in itself for them in imagining themselves as teachers. Furthermore, we know that ITE institutions are failing to challenge the homogenous, white, female image of the teacher and this, indeed, will inevitably shatter the very image of minority ethnic student teachers (Kohli, 2009; Pearce, 2013; Anuja-Bhullar, 2018).

The Experienced Teacher

There were fourteen participants in this study that had over ten years' experience each, with at least four who have around twenty years' experience of teaching in schools in Scotland. When they were asked about their identity and whether they were able to be themselves in school, the participants noted that despite the number of years in the profession, they often feel like the 'outsider' and remarked on the influence this had on their professional identities:

I had romanticised the idea of a teacher ...I've totally lost that now completely. The experience shook me up; I realised that there is such a different culture there than the one that I had expected. I will never be good enough.

(Zainab)

I have been a peripatetic teacher for so long and have been in so many schools but more recently based in two schools. In some schools you are really not accepted...they don't want you there. The body language says it all...but sometimes, the words follow...(she quotes) "you are not one of us" ... but I know I am there... Can you believe, when I walk into a staffroom, they stop talking and stare?

(Leyla)

Zainab has been teaching for over twelve years and has described how positive she was when starting her teaching career. I asked her what she meant by '*romanticised*' followed by '*shook me up*'. She explained that she was looking forward to being in a school, having her own classroom and working alongside her colleagues to support the children. However, she went to explain that she never felt accepted nor valued by her colleagues and she felt demoralised '*I will never be good enough*'. Interestingly, she also makes reference to the culture within the school, and I understood this to be her realisation that no matter what she does to fit in or work with her colleagues, she will remain an outsider.

Similarly, Leyla, remarked '*you are really not accepted*' and saw this as a disapproval of who she was as a person '*they don't want you there*'. I asked her to clarify who she referred to as 'they', she replied with an almost surprised look 'staff, of course'. I followed this up and asked why she was surprised by my question and she responded, '*people assume that it is just the young people, but staff are very guilty of this behaviour*'. Leyla highlights the different ways in which she experiences discrimination – her reference to '*body language*' demonstrates the covert and more subtle ways that racism is played out but what is also concerning is when she said '*sometimes, the words follow*' highlighting overt acts when she was told '*you are not one of us*'. Her experience of isolation is marked by her mere presence in the school '*when I walk into a staffroom, they stop talking and stare*'. When I asked Leyla why she thought they reacted in this way, she replied:

Because you are different, you are new, you are strange...I don't know...not accepting something different...not accepting change (a long pause), they don't see me as a colleague. You are made to feel uncomfortable...maybe so, I don't stay longer...but I have been sent to do a job, and I will do it.

This further reinforces the work of Puwar, where Leyla is a 'body deemed out of place' (2004, p.8), entering a space which has otherwise been occupied by majority white teachers and so therefore would reinforce Leyla's perception '*they don't see me as a colleague*'. Leyla thought for some time. The long pause seemed to indicate deep reflection and then she said '*maybe, I don't stay longer*'. She appears to question her sense of belonging and is aware of the subtle forms of discrimination she is experiencing, which lead to feelings of discomfort. Leyla is also very aware that she is not welcome in the school, but the nature of her peripatetic role means she does not really have a choice when she remarks '*I have been sent to do a job and I will do it*'. Moreover, she describes another incident which again compounds the isolation and exclusion:

There was a school I went to and the HT actually said "I don't want you here". She then quickly said that my contract was a 0.7 and she required a 0.6 teacher. I was asked to leave and later I learned that she replaced me with two white members of staff. Both their contracts would equate to 0.7. At another school, the HT announced at a staff meeting that temporary staff will not be issued with keys. What made it even more stressful for me was that to go to the toilet, I needed keys, and I had to walk to the other end of the school to use the toilet in the staff base. Also, the locker that was allocated to me for my personal belongings did not have a key. The PT told me that the keys were missing - out of all the lockers that key was missing. So, I had to carry my bag and things with me to every classroom.

Her treatment within the school is clear – she was first discouraged to join the staff team, and this message came directly from the leadership in the school '*I don't want*

you here' and then she was denied a key that would allow her access to staff facilities. The HT could have been focussed on the contract criteria when she made this comment but from the actions that followed it became evident that what Leyla described was casual, overt or perhaps unconscious racist attitudes which not only affect ME teachers' sense of confidence and belonging but also have a profound effect on their developing professional identities and as such, their career opportunities (Coleman and Campbell-Stephens, 2010; Bhopal, 2017). These racist incidents need to be acknowledged as Bhopal reminds us how important it is to be mindful of the role of Whiteness – the trivialising or dismissal of any form of racial prejudice is a powerful tool of Whiteness that is used to maintain their hegemonic understandings and to avoid and ignore the issues that come to light (Bhopal, 2017).

Similarly, Khurram, who has been teaching for over twelve years, as an English as Additional Language (EAL) Teacher described how he is made to feel when he arrives at schools:

I get around quite a lot of different schools who may have never had Asian teachers, so the reaction is, you know that it's like "are you really a teacher?" and that's the kind of expression I get. But funnily enough, I actually have experienced this with teachers you know, who think I am just a teaching assistant, like it's such a shock when they find out "oh you are a teacher?" This could be because they have no BME teacher in their school. It has often made me think that they have a stereotype – an Asian person – you should be working in shop (he laughs).

(Khurram)

Here Khurram's response shows that he has received comments from both pupils and staff questioning his professional identity, '*are you really a teacher?*' He describes how this misrecognition for the teachers '*is such a shock*' which, perhaps reinforces the failings of a homogenous workforce which appear to have 'normalised' what a teacher should look like (Arshad et al, 2005; Pearce, 2014). It also brings to

the fore the stereotypical assumptions that socially holds regarding BME people. Khurram laughed out loud and I interpreted this to reflect how he perhaps feels about this – a sense of frustration unfolding into a helpless hysteria which essentially, may be defeatist in nature (Kohli, 2014).

Yusuf, who has been teaching for twenty-five years, also speaks about how things do not seem to be getting better but rather, are regressing:

I've been here for over 20 years, and it was good but more recently, I am seeing a change...the negative stereotyping coming back into the fold. I saw a lot of it when I first started my career and now again...that is the worrying thing.

(Yusuf)

Yusuf's concern '*I see a change...*' refers to adverse assumptions '*coming back into the fold*'. When I asked Yusuf to explain what he meant by this he simply replied '*it got better for a while*'. Yusuf's comment suggests that issues around race equality were better for a period of time but have got worse again, which is interesting to consider, particularly in light of the claims that we have entered into a post-racial era in Scotland, where there is no 'problem here' following the appointment of a Scottish Muslim Justice Minister and the SNP referendum rhetoric around 'One Scotland – Many Cultures' (Davidson et, al, 2018, p.9). From a critical race theory perspective, Yusuf's comment suggested that the negative stereotyping and inequality still existed but are presenting more covert and subtle forms. The change that Yusuf could be seeing is perhaps a move to more obvious comments made outright which have been fuelled by the current political context - growth of far-right groups and the discourse around Brexit (Armstrong, 2018; Liinpa, 2018).

A few of the participants seem to have developed strategies to help them negotiate their identities as teachers:

I am more comfortable in myself, do my job, be nice, don't need to be part of it. But this has impact on people like us at some level – moving up.

(Farhana)

Sometimes, I try to help other teachers out and is that, inherently, a bit of me trying to get acceptance? Or is it also because you don't tend to fit in because you don't drink, you don't go out to clubs and all the rest of it with them... there tends to be a lot of nepotism within teaching, it's not what you know, it's who you know.

(Khurram)

I have resilience and that helps to support me. There are certainly a lot of things that happen to us BME teachers and I've learned to take it. If it was to happen to native white teachers, they wouldn't be able to do it. I believe I am able to stand most of the pressures and stress that I face because of my ethnicity and where I come from.

(Mumta)

I have a motto. To be brilliant you have to be good in their eyes. To be good, right, you have to be ok. But never be okay because you will be judged on a different level, different point.

(Abu-Zahr)

Farhana's approach appears to be to get on with the job and be nice to others. Her comment '*I don't need to be part of it*' could suggest that she doesn't feel the need to be accepted by her white colleagues and that her focus is on doing the job. She does however, indicate that in doing so, she could potentially jeopardise her future opportunities such as promotion. In contrast, Khurram's remarks indicate that he wants to be perceived by his white colleagues as someone who is supportive, but his

question is important to note 'is it *a bit of me trying to get acceptance?*'. I interpreted this to mean that Khurram feels he needs to be acknowledged by his colleagues and goes out of his way to help in order to make up for the fact that he doesn't socialise with them out with school. However, like Farhana, he appears to be aware of an informal network which he refers to as '*nepotism...it's not what you know but who you know...*' and that, by not being in the fold, he will suffer the negative consequences. Mumta speaks of resilience and learning to '*take it*'. It appears that she draws confidence from the struggles she may already have faced because of her ethnicity.

Abu-Zahr's motto is thought-provoking, '*to be brilliant you have to be good in their eyes*' or else you may be judged by your white colleagues. This resonates with the seminal work of Dubois (1903) who states that racialized minorities have a double consciousness where they see themselves through the eyes of others. Abu-Zahr speaks about the privilege afforded to his white colleagues in measuring the worth of his work and seeking their approval. This privilege, where one looks for recognition from others seeks to discredit and undervalue the knowledge and skills of BME teachers (Rollock, 2012).

The above quotes highlight the complexities of embodying diversity when teaching in a mainly white school. Sara Ahmed's (2009) statement is apt here, reflecting:

If only we had the power we are imagined to possess, if only our proximity could be such a force. If only our arrival was their undoing (. . .). The argument is too much to sustain when your body is so exposed. (p,40).

The participants do not wish to disrupt the status quo and as such, are prepared to engage in what Leonardo and Porter (2010) argue is safe racial dialogue where whites feel comfortable but where racially minoritised groups, when silenced, experience tension and conflict – when they attempt to have genuine conversations

around race, they are faced with whiteness as a default position (Rollock, 2012). Furthermore, it can be said that the strategies adopted by the participants are what Rollock claims are 'rules of racial engagement for (possible) survival in a White World'. The participants in this study discuss maintaining a lowered tone of voice in debates on race, especially where there is a difference of opinion. They work at presenting a friendly and reasonable persona. Another tactic they use is to present an image which is friendly and approachable which gives them a degree of license.

Summary

As minority ethnic teachers, they have entered schools which are traditionally homogenous, dominant white spaces and they have observed how their presence often disorients this whiteness. Kohli (2021) call this a double take – so, whilst minority ethnic teachers exist and work in schools, their right to dwell in these spaces is questionable. So for this reason, it is important to gain a deeper understanding of identity construction for all teachers but in particular, for minority ethnic teachers. Participants referred to a 'culture' that existed in ITE and in school and that they were required to fit in or otherwise face isolation. The findings show that there are teachers, including minority ethnic teachers, who are not ready to confront the dominant racial ideologies, the overwhelming presence of whiteness in the schools and communities in which they work. It is important therefore to consider the role of ITE in helping student teachers to learn about what it means to be and become a teacher.

While teacher education programmes focus on providing new and responsive ways to engage students in their learning, much of a teachers' professional knowledge is shaped by their own experiences of attending school. For minority ethnic teachers, reflecting on their student teacher journey, they were aware that their ethnicity and culture was often ignored and devalued in discussions around the construction of teacher identity. For the teachers in this study, it has been a process of adopting and enacting a new identity while negotiating the relationship between this new identity and their previous identities.

ITE should introduce student teachers to frameworks that discuss racial and ethnic identity development for all. For white students to construct a positive white racial identity and a parallel need for both white and minority ethnic students to see and learn about examples of empowered minority ethnic teachers (Utt and Tochleck, 2016). This would improve the ways that ITE programmes are perceived (Beauchamps and Thomas, 2009; Gallchoir, 2018). As such, the inextricable link between personal and professional selves of teachers, particularly for BME teachers must be considered in understanding teacher identity (Alsup, 2006; Slay and Smith, 2010). I also suggest that their fellow minority ethnic colleagues also helped them to shape their identities through a shared history which offered an acknowledgement - an acceptance that prejudice and inequality, though at times, subtle and covert, exists. Through articulating similar experiences, they found a sense of community – an affirmation where they found encouragement and emotional support where BME teachers benefit from each other.

An important part of expanding on both personal and professional identities of minority ethnic teachers is the discourse that provokes transformation in their thinking. As such, Slay and Smith (2010) encourage a personal transformation where they become conscious that as professionals, they, too, should be afforded status and respect. They promote the kind of interaction that has the power to confront teachers' ideas about themselves and their profession, through their beliefs, actions, emotions, language and appearances. The next chapter will consider the multiple cases of minority ethnic teachers about what they do in schools and in the classroom to create the kind of transformation required for an alternative teaching culture to be realised. It will examine how minority ethnic teachers used their cultural, linguistic and religious skills in the classroom in a positive way.

Chapter 6

Finding teacher agency: making a hidden curriculum visible

'I bring my hijab...my colour...my culture into the classroom?'

Introduction

In Chapter Four, becoming a teacher, participants spoke clearly about their reasons for choosing teaching and cited they wished that they had teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds so that they could relate to them. They also had a strong desire for social justice and wanted to ensure that they could draw on their own lived experiences to challenge discrimination and saw themselves as advocates for change (Borrero et al., 2016). Most of the participants had discussed making a difference to the education of *all* pupils but particularly those who were also from a ME background. This is consistent with many research findings that due to their personal understandings of racism, minority ethnic teachers are especially committed to the education of minority ethnic children (Magaldi and Trub, 2018; Santoro and Basit, 2010). Furthermore, in Chapter Five, participants discussed the challenges they faced in finding a teacher identity where their ethnicity, culture, language and religion marked them out to be different from their majority ethnic colleagues. Some of the participants in this study were making a conscious decision to affirm their diverse identities and use this cultural wealth to build relevant positive relationships with all children but in particular minority ethnic children.

This chapter explores minority ethnic teachers' experiences of teaching and responds to the question: In what way does your identity as a minority ethnic teacher impact or make a difference to your teaching? Through the analysis of data, minority ethnic teachers share how they adopt a Culturally Responsive Pedagogy (CRP) which draws on their cultural, linguistic and religious experiences to benefit not only children from minority ethnic backgrounds but all the children they teach (Kohli,

2021). The analysis shows how minority ethnic teachers utilise their diverse identities and lived experiences to provoke and disrupt the implicit values, attitudes and beliefs children learn through the everyday experiences of a Eurocentric/western curriculum and the wider school culture. This chapter also examines the enablers and barriers to progression for minority ethnic teachers.

This chapter does this by firstly, considering the important roles that the minority ethnic teachers in this study fulfilled in relation to building positive relationships with the minority ethnic pupils they teach through relatable ties. Secondly, it explores how minority ethnic teachers use their diverse identities and discuss their personal understandings of racism and injustices to disrupt the western euro-centric curriculum in schools and act as advocates for minority ethnic students in their school settings. Kohli (2021) argues that much of a teacher's professional knowledge is shaped by the experience of attending school and for minority ethnic teachers, who have had their histories, languages and culture ignored and devalued, they have had to unlearn and resist the dominant structures that question their place in schools. The participants in this study bring into sharp focus the existence of the hidden curriculum and in applying the critical race theory framework, specifically in seeking to understand how teachers utilise these skills. Lastly, minority ethnic teachers also describe some of the limitations in their agency towards progression.

Relatable Ties: culture, gender, linguistic expertise and families

Culture and gender

Culture-specific issues are also a lived reality for minority ethnic teachers as they build positive relationships with the pupils they work with. Aneesah is a female teacher who has been teaching for fifteen years. She identifies as British Asian. She shares how she builds positive relationships with the children she teaches:

As the only minority ethnic teacher in the school, kids look at you with preconceived ideas of what you should be like. I get a real buzz out of it because my presence helps to break down barriers and build relationships. Often the conversations are around minority ethnic teachers as positive role models for minority ethnic kids ...I'm not sure because I think it goes beyond that. I think it provides opportunities to listen to someone who can relate to the kids and provides opportunities to listen and allow them to open up...I guess a role model is something in a distance thing, you can see a person but it needs to be how you interact with them on a day-to-day basis...Senior BME pupils come to me and start telling me things – I am not a pastoral care teacher but I am British born and I've got the Glasgow patter that helps them to relate to you and they do come and attach themselves to you and say “look this is happening at home – you get that”

(Aneesah)

Aneesah refers to the young people's '*preconceived ideas*' regarding her ethnicity but she sees this as a challenge and gets '*..a real buzz out of it*' suggesting that her presence helps to change the perceptions held by the young children (Basit and Santoro, 2010; Kohli, 2014). She also highlights that her presence is not simply about representation but rather reaches beyond this to include how one interacts and relates to all their pupils. Aneesah further adds '*it helps to break down barriers and build relationships*' which suggests that her presence and interactions support her white pupils in some way to disrupt perceptions around the colour of her skin through nurturing positive relationships.

In terms of relating to her black and minority ethnic pupils, she comments that '*senior BME pupils come to me and start telling me things...I'm British born and I've got the Glasgow patter that helps them to relate to you*'. For Aneesah there is clearly an assumption that because she has grown up in this country and speaks like her pupils, she is able to relate to what the pupils experience...particularly when she comments '*...attach themselves to you and say look this is happening at home – you*

get that'. To gain a clearer understanding of this relatability, I asked Aneesah, '*what do you get?*' She provided an example:

On one occasion, a 15-year-old female pupil came to me and said that she had asked her pastoral care teacher for advice on subject choices and careers. The response she received was "why are you worrying over this, you'll be getting married as soon as you leave, won't you?" She asked me to speak to her pastoral care teacher on her behalf, which I did and that did not go down well at all. My colleague complained that I should not have had any communication with her pupil.

With this incident, we can see Aneesah's cultural background being drawn to the forefront. Her attempts to communicate and dismiss the stereotypes her colleague held did not go well and was facing a complaint made against her. This is a recurring theme over the past two decades, from Bhatti's (2005) ethnographic study exploring the experiences of South Asian children at home and school to Inter-Cultural Youth Scotland's survey (2019) where black and minority ethnic pupils were asked whether they felt their teachers and staff at school understood their culture, heritage or background. Almost 70% per cent of pupils disagreed. As such, culture is important when it comes to pupils being able to relate to their teachers and this is reinforced through the pupil's words to Aneesah '*you get that*' suggests that she is in a good place to nurture and bridge such divides.

Similarly, Shaista, who identifies as a British Asian, Muslim female and has been teaching for over sixteen years, also suggests that her ethnic identity helps to support her relationship with the children:

I think my ethnicity, as a British Asian, helps in relating things to pupils' cultural experiences and sometimes for those out with their cultural experiences and I think the interactions they have with us make them open

their minds towards people from BME communities. I definitely think this helps when establishing rapport with the children.

(Shaista)

At first, it is unclear who Shaista is referring to when she refers to *'those'* *'their'* and *'them'*. However, I understood the first part of her sentence to refer to ME pupils and how she feels that her ethnic identity helps her to build relevance and bring her lived experiences to connect with her pupils. When she refers to *'those out with their cultural experiences'* I understood this to mean the majority-white children as she goes on to say *'the interactions they have with us makes them open their mind towards people from BME communities'*. Shaista perceives her ethnicity to benefit all the children that she teaches. Her mere presence in the school setting and how she interacts with them helps to challenge any preconceived negative stereotypes that the majority of white pupils may hold. This was evident in Magaldi and Trub's study (2018) study, minority ethnic teachers reported that although they could identify more with the minority ethnic children they also felt that their presence helped the majority-white children in challenging stereotypes held about diverse communities.

It is clear that the minority ethnic teachers in this study saw their roles as providing a perspective on education that was critical to the profession. As such, minority ethnic teachers were using their experiences to provide new objective voices for both staff and the young people (Slay and Smith, 2011):

"Having taught in an all-white school in Kilwinning, I wanted to go to Glasgow to show that we are not all bus conductors, doctors or waiters. I went out there in the 1980's it was dead obvious that I was different. It was to show that if you are a BME teacher, they had to evaluate your worth in making a difference to their life choices and that too was a challenge in changing perceptions. For our BME young people there was a sense of community, that you are from a BME background and they are too. While they are not looking for any special treatment you have some empathy, and you can see

their point of view. Even if you are educated here you have black heritage sometimes that gives added depth to the teaching experience – a bonding with all youngsters but have more so for BME kids. In the past, the school had various problems around prejudice - we tended to be the shepherds for minority ethnic pupils. This was not to give them lee way but to bond with them culturally and allowing them to be more open with you than they would be with another teacher.

(Adnan)

‘As teachers it is not just about teaching content, it is much wider than that and this links to ‘dawa’ (to act as an advocate). This also speaks about a lot of teachers who are just content driven but what’s teaching anymore? You have to help them with making sense of their experiences – life skills, skills for work, their identities...’

(Kashif)

‘If this is how we are treated, educated professionals, then what kind of treatment do the children receive when we are not there? I raised this point at the last departmental meeting... it did not go down to well.’

(Wahid)

Each of the quotes above discusses the different ways in which their own cultural experiences help to provide new voices which are culturally relevant. Adnan’s words ‘*Black heritage gives added depth to the teaching experience*’ in order to bond with the young people and his comment ‘...we tended to be shepherds for minority ethnic pupils’ was perhaps his way of explaining how they looked out for them by ensuring stronger bonds were established through teaching and general interactions. Abu-Zahr indicates that he can acknowledge and give voice to these day-to-day experiences by drawing on his own experiences of coming from a scheme ‘*they look at me and say you are like us*’ and ‘*breaking the mould*’. Kashif’s use of the word ‘*dawa*’ is interesting. ‘Dawa’ is an Arabic word which means to act as an advocate

and links this to life skills. He speaks about teachers who are 'content driven' and this could suggest that they are less likely to speak to the cultural experiences of the young people (Cummins and Early, 2011). Wahid takes this to another level and asks, '*what kind of treatment do the children receive when we are not there?*' He is prepared to challenge and represent their voices.

Yusuf shares the same views. He has been teaching for twenty-five years and identifies as a Male, Pakistani teacher. He raised an interesting point:

I think sometimes you need to be able to find someone you can relate to and I'm not sure if this fits into the category of role model...I remember discussing this in my training, but I was never encouraged to think about my ethnicity in becoming a teacher. I know some BME teachers who just won't go there ... but to be able to draw from your own experiences and help share and support BME kids is great.

(Yusuf)

Whilst it is important for black and minority ethnic children to see a teacher who looks like them in terms of their ethnicity, Yusuf's reflection '*I'm not sure if this fits into the category of role model... I know some BME teachers who just won't go there*' suggests that it is not enough to share the same ethnic background or look the same but that his understanding of being a role model goes beyond just visibility and representation. For Yusuf, the real impact is where he states, '*to be able to draw from your own experiences and help share and support BME kids is great*'. Again, this seems to suggest that sharing his own life experiences it will help to relate to the minority ethnic children in his setting. It is interesting to note when he said '*I was never encouraged to think about my ethnicity in becoming a teacher*' which further reinforces the discussions in Chapter Five on finding a teacher identity. While identity development in Initial Teacher Education has become an area of increasing focus for researchers, there is little research that discusses identity development which includes participants from minority ethnic backgrounds (Beauchamp and Thomas,

2009; Sachs, 2016; Hong et al., 2018). Yusuf was beginning to explore some possibilities about 'self' and how this relates to his teacher identity. This process of redefining his role where he feels he can share, help and support minority ethnic children is '*great*' perhaps raises questions about how Yusuf sees himself and how he is involved in enacting a teacher identity that requires continuous negotiation around expectations and norms.

Furthermore, O'Gallchoir, O'Flaherty and Hinchion (2018) explored the experiences of seven pre-service teachers as they understood what becoming a teacher means for them. Data was gathered using autobiographical narratives and video clips of their practice on placement. Their findings suggested that pre-service teachers are initially drawn to the physical depiction of what a teacher looks like and as their placement in schools progressed there was an emerging dissonance that challenged their ongoing identity construction. The participant in this study included a 60:40 ratio of male and female pre-service teachers and there was no diversity in terms of ethnicity.

This would also help to make sense of his comment '*BME teachers just won't go there*'. As this was not explored in their teacher education programmes, the implicit message is that it is better to assimilate and consider their ethnic identity to have no relevance in their interactions with children. However, it is also important to consider why some ME teachers would not consider it relevant. Aujla-Bhullar (2018) had ongoing conversations with minority ethnic female teachers about the challenges and responsibility of representing one's racialized identity, ethnicity, culture, and religion while finding oneself marginalized within their own school settings. Furthermore, Arshad (2018) highlights that many minority ethnic teachers feel uncomfortable drawing on their cultural and linguistic experiences for fear of the implications of being different. This is helpful in understanding why some minority teachers would rather assimilate into the majority dominant white culture prevalent in schools across Scotland.

Gender

But also, in this kind of school, a lot of Asian kids treat you like a 'baji' or an 'aunty' at home. They see a lot in their homes – female Asians at home in that role. They also think that I may be a pushover. I nip this in the bud and this shows them another side - Asian woman can be professional teachers!

(Naila)

Moreover, Naila's comment reinforces Aneesah's perspective as she discusses her identity as a teacher in terms of a positive role model who by her very presence helps to challenge stereotypes. Interestingly, Naila focuses on the stereotypes that are held by BME young people on '*female Asians at home*'. Her reference to '*in this kind of school, a lot of Asian kids treat you like a 'baji' or an 'aunty' at home*'. This seems to indicate that the school has a large population of minority ethnic young people who come from an 'Asian – Pakistani/Indian background. I, too, come from this cultural background and understand this terminology well. The term *baji*' (literally means sister in Urdu but in a general context it is used to show respect to someone who is older) or '*aunty*' which is also used to show respect rather than have any biological connection. That said, there is also an element of not taking 'female Asians' seriously as Naila adds they see a lot of females holding the role of 'baji' or 'aunty' and though they often are associated as ones to respect, their experience is often that they are role models at home and who do not work outside the home. Perhaps this is why she adds '*...they think I am a pushover. I nip this in the bud and show them another side*'. So, for Naila, she appears to be a role model to show the young people that they can perhaps aspire to be working and have a professional career.

Ghaffar and Stevenson (2019) carried out a qualitative study to examine the ways in which young Pakistani and Bangladeshi women deal with the tensions between the construction of identity and the use of stereotypes from within their communities

revealing some of the emotional difficulties they encounter in accessing the workplace. Naila's words '*Asian woman can be professional teachers!*' seems to also indicate that she wants to change the typical perceptions they hold, relying on the stereotypical representation they see within their communities as 'your typical Asian' who is a home maker (Ghaffar and Stevenson, p.50).

Khurram, a male participant who has been teaching for twelve years also discussed his gender as having an influence on the young people he worked with.

we actually break the mould, and in their mind they don't just see us (men) as being some kind of person who can be like a...like a retailer, the guy with the local Pakistani shop but as an educator, or we don't see them when they see people like us as not just the Health Service, they see us a educators trying to guide and nurture them.

(Khurram)

Here Khurram refers to the stereotype often associated with minority ethnic males from an Asian background, running small businesses or being a doctor/dentist/pharmacist. His comment '*we actually break the mould*' is perhaps commenting on how his presence in a school disrupts this perspective for the young children to '*see us as educators trying to guide and nurture them*'.

Waylen et al, (2017) carried out research to consider what factors motivated BME students to consider a career in the health services, in this case, Dentistry. They found that the most important factor was personal choice and for minority ethnic students the second most important factor was family pressure.

Religious Experiences

Minority ethnic teachers in this study reflected on their own experiences to understand the cultural practices linked to religious beliefs that might shape their pupil's experiences as learners in Scottish schools. Nusrat, a Muslim secondary school teacher draws upon her religious knowledge and how this impacts the Muslim children she teaches:

During Ramadan, I notice the children are tired and perhaps not doing so well, I get it, I understand why. It really is about relating to the children's experiences because you've been through things yourself. They see some sort of connection there, or whether it's prayer or fasting they see that I can build some sort of connection and they latch onto that. So, I let them use the classroom if they need to come in and pray or just rest during Ramadan. I also try to explain this to other teachers.

(Nusrat)

Here, Nusrat suggests that because she has been 'through' similar experiences herself, she is able to '*build some sort of connection*' based on her understandings of the students' religion. Nusrat also demonstrates how responsive she is to their needs by providing them with a space to pray in her classroom or simply rest. She also is aware that the children may not be achieving as best as they can due to the tiredness they experience as a result of the fasting. This is very much in line with advocates of culturally responsive pedagogy – ensuring that teaching and learning are structured and conducive to the lived experiences of the learners (Ladson-Billings, 1995; Yosso, 2006; Kohli, 2021). Moreover, she believes that these experiences place her well to act in an advisory capacity to her colleagues.

Similarly, Mumta is female Hindu secondary school teacher who has been teaching for over twenty years commented:

I am not Muslim, but this does not stop the Muslim pupils from approaching me and saying things like ...'you understand miss, our other teachers don't'. I also have some of the Hindu/Sikh pupils who will share what they do at home with me.

Here, Mumta suggests that despite not being Muslim, she is still approached by the 'Muslim pupils' as she identifies with the local South Asian culture and community well. Mumta appears well-positioned to draw on such knowledge to support her pupils.

Farhana is a Muslim teacher who has been teaching for 27 years. She is a Principal Teacher of Pastoral Care. She recalls an incident between a young male, BME pupil and his white, Modern Studies teacher:

...he came to me and said that his teacher remarked "you know you are not getting into my subject until you get THAT of your face!" ...the pupil had a beard in line with his Muslim faith. When this was brought to my attention, I was not happy. He was not in my group, but I could not sit back and do nothing. I could have walked in and said blah, blah, blah but I know how the system works...he would deny what he said and blame the pupil and me and it would go further...to a grievance...becomes unpleasant. It has to be done subtly. So, I went to see the teacher and said that I was worried that perhaps the young pupil may have heard wrongly and that maybe he was confused, in fact, I am sure he is, but I just thought it best to clear this up and tell him he got it wrong...

(Farhana)

Farhana raises a number of significant points. Firstly, despite not being in her group, the pupil felt able to approach her because he felt she could relate to his concern. However, in her attempt to act as an advocate, she too faced issues when trying to address the anti-Muslim racism of a colleague. This term refers to prejudice and discrimination against people who identify as Muslims (Bakali, 2016). It is closely related to the term 'Islamophobia', which dates back to the 1910s and 1920s but reached wider audiences in the UK with the 1997 Runnymede Trust report *Islamophobia: A Challenge to Us All* (Runnymede Trust, 1997). The report defined islamophobia as 'unfounded hostility towards Islam [and] unfair discrimination against Muslims individually or as part of a group'. When asked about the 'system' she referred to she simply responded '*...the school culture of course and the structures that cover up*'. Kohli (2021) argues that racism continues to be prevalent in school structures, systems and processes and that many minority ethnic teachers 'have brought new tools and insights to the individual and collectivist struggle in and out of the classroom', (p.xiv). Farhana's insight into the system helps her to navigate her way through the racism she and her pupils experience. This can often be subtle and at times blatant.

In March 2018, the largest teaching union in Scotland, the Educational Institute of Scotland (EIS) highlighted some of the ways in which Muslim staff and learners in educational spaces experience anti-Muslim prejudice. This can take many forms as outlined in the report. From verbal abuse and name-calling to racist comments presented as 'jokes'; derogatory comments and loaded questions, e.g. 'so, what did you think of the Brussels event? Sikhs, Hindus and other South Asian young people experience misrecognition when they are mistaken as Muslims because of their skin colour, hair and features etc. (Hopkins et al., 2017). Victimisation is also another way that anti-Muslim prejudice manifests when staff and young people raise any concerns about the prejudice they experience, they tend to be unfairly treated and Farhana's common about things becoming 'unpleasant' and moving to 'grievance' demonstrates this.

Faller and Lander (2018) examined the views of eight Muslim teachers of RE on fundamental British values (FBV). FBV was introduced into the new teachers' standards in England in 2012 which set out the professional duties of teachers and the minimum baseline requirements for teachers' practice and conduct (DfE 2013). The standards included the requirement to uphold the public trust by "not undermining fundamental British values" (DfE 2013, 14). The Findings demonstrate that as teachers of multicultural RE, they find it difficult to teach the curriculum as it is presented. The Muslim teachers are critical of its divisive effects on their students and on how this positions them in terms of their own multiple identities. They feel they have no choice but to assimilate.

Linguistic Expertise

Minority ethnic teachers in this study were able to use their bi/multilingual expertise which helped to build positive relationships with minority ethnic children. Participants in this study spoke to how fortunate they felt in being able to communicate with families and pupils in their first language:

I've had a young boy come straight from Jamaica. I had to explain to him in his first language the things we were doing, which I found was very useful. I think that I am able to connect with him.... Over the years, I have had a few Jamaican pupils in my class when I speak with them in Patwa, they love it. Sometimes, it is things that I notice in their writing where they may get their tenses all muddled up and I am not suggesting that they don't understand how to use the tenses but it is because of how we speak Patwa ...I am aware of this and this helps me to raise the awareness of my colleagues who do not.

(Keisha)

Similarly, Aneesah, noted:

Sometimes I speak to my kids, if it is an all-Asian class, then we talk in Urdu, last year I had a senior class and we talked in Urdu and Punjabi and we talked about other things linked to the subject but that kept them going and it kept their passion for the subject going. You could not do that with an all-white class or mixed race class in front of me, you just couldn't do that. There is a deep connection.

As a bilingual teacher, Keisha can show how she uses her mother tongue to support the Jamaican pupils in her class. She draws on her knowledge of the language structure in Patwa. They both also comment on the value of doing this ...Keisha saying 'they love it' and Aneesah 'kept their passion going'. This ability to codeswitch or more formally known as translanguaging allows children to mix words and expressions from their first language and second language (in this case, English) to support their learning and the development of positive identities (Garcia-Mateus and Palmer, 2017; Cummins, 2013). Clearly, this serves as an advantage to the school in supporting multilingual pupils. Research suggests that identity matters for school success and that language and identity are powerfully intertwined. Garcia-Mateus and Palmer (2017) carried out a close discourse analysis of children's interactions in a two-way bilingual classroom. They found that when teachers embraced translanguaging pedagogy it improved the metalinguistic awareness and bilingual identities of the children.

However, at the same time, opposing messages are heard and internalized in several ways. It is interesting to note when Aneesah commented that she '*could not do this with 'an all-white class or mixed-race class...you just couldn't.*' Perhaps this reveals some of the challenges she faces – she is comfortable to speak in Urdu but only when Urdu speaking pupils are present. She appears to have some concern ...'you just couldn't' in which she may be suggesting that this will not be welcomed by her white monolingual pupils and/or fellow colleagues. When asked if she

received comments from other teachers or children she responded *'no, I didn't but it's the way they look at you when they hear you speak that says it all'*.

There could be two main reasons for Aneesah's concerns, firstly, there is a lack of awareness around the importance of promoting the first language in the development of a second language. This was shown in the study carried out by Turnbull (2018) to investigate the opinions of pre-service teachers regarding the use of the first language in acquiring a second language. The results of this study suggested that, although the pre-service teacher participants were accepting of the first language use at times, their acceptance was limited, implying a lack of a complete understanding overall.

Secondly, Aneesah's reservations about speaking in Urdu suggest she feared a potential backlash from her colleagues – a form of subtle yet significant oppression that Aneesah has internalised in which she has 'learned' that Urdu is not one of the languages that carry value in comparison to French, Spanish or other European languages (Sanchez et al., 2017). The absence of any encouragement or appreciation of her ability to effectively communicate and connect with the children in her class is a powerful message of covert racism. CRT helps us to understand these looks as microaggressions. Racial microaggressions are every day, routine, verbal and behavioural degradations, intentional or unintentional, that involve hostile, derogatory or negative conduct involving a failure to acknowledge racial insults (Sue et al., 2019).

Families – home-school liaison

In this study, the teachers' knowledge of their student's backgrounds meant that they were well-positioned to foster home-school relationships. Most of the teachers felt that they made an important contribution to bridging the gap between school and home and encouraging reluctant minority ethnic parents to attend parent-teacher meetings. Naila remarked:

I remember clearly that my Asian parents felt so much more relaxed when they saw me. One parent told me that she had previously not attended any parent teacher meeting because she could not communicate with the class teachers. I can talk to parents in Urdu, and it just makes things much clearer to them.

Similarly, Pooja observed:

I think that some of the parents feel that they can approach me to discuss some sensitive cultural issues - I remember once it was about a school Christmas dance and she did not want her daughter to dance with a boy.

As shown in the comments above, it is clear that minority ethnic teachers' skills are not confined to their linguistic expertise but include religious/cultural skills. With Aneesah's comment '*Asian parents felt so much more relaxed...I can talk to parents in Urdu*' and Pooja's words '*discuss some sensitive cultural issues...Christmas dance*' shows the benefit to schools of having teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds who have the ability to welcome and support minority ethnic parents in terms of being able to communicate in their first language and a foster sense of belonging which helps them to feel relaxed and be able to approach the teachers. There is much research that indicates minority ethnic parents lack confidence in the school system which fails to acknowledge and meet the linguistic needs of their children. Over four decades ago the Community Relations Commission (1976) undertook a piece of research on the education of south Asian girls and made the following statement:

The children of Asian parents born or brought up in Britain are a generation caught between two cultures. They live in a culture of their parents at home, are taught a different one at school. (p.21).

This was a key finding in Little's (2020) research where a survey of 212 heritage language families was conducted to explore their attitudes towards maintaining and supporting heritage languages. The parents struggled to feel valued by the school staff because of the language and cultural barriers and as a result, they had little to do with their children's schools.

Many of the examples presented in this chapter thus far reflect how the participants; cultural and ethnic backgrounds helped them to connect to both the children they taught and their families. They also discussed how this made them more likely to act as advocates of change for them so that they did not experience the same challenges they faced when they were growing up in Scotland. It would appear that the participants took an emic perspective in which they understood minority ethnic children from inside their culture and family (Olsen, 2011; Kohli, 2014). Zafar captures the sentiment well by saying '*I know what it is like, we have been there. So, that's the legacy you know, you're the legacy.*'

There have been several issues within the curriculum field that affect education leading to calls for curriculum reform. The hidden curriculum is one such issue where unspoken or implicit values, behaviours, processes, and norms are promoted and enforced in educational settings (Alsubaie, 2015). The term hidden curriculum was first used in curriculum discourse in the late 1960s. In 1983, Greene made reference to the concept and argued that the hidden curriculum has both a normal and moral element. Normal in that it is multifaceted with both formal and informal aspects that come together to form the curriculum itself and the moral aspect includes the need for educators to make the hidden curriculum explicit (Greene, 1983). Moreover, in

the early 1970's to the 1990s, these unspoken values were understood as what schooling does to people and terms such as the 'the by-product of schooling' 'unstudied curriculum'; the 'implicit curriculum'; the 'covert curriculum'; the 'silent curriculum' and the 'invisible curriculum' were used to express the implicit values in curriculum discourse (Portelli, 1993, p.344). Alsubaie provides a helpful definition:

The hidden curriculum is an implicit curriculum that expresses and represents attitudes, knowledge, and behaviours, which are conveyed or communicated without aware intent; it is conveyed indirectly by words and actions that are parts of the life of everyone in a society. To address this issue, we should understand that the hidden curriculum plays a positive or negative role in the education system in school; therefore, teachers have to be aware of it and how it appears in the school. (Alsubaie, 2015, p125).

From Alsubaie's definition, the normality that Greene (1983) first referred to is clear as school curriculum can be defined as the praxis and rituals that occur within the bricks and mortar of our schools – in the everyday. In trying to understand the positive and negative aspects of the hidden curriculum, teachers need to realise that curriculum is multiform in nature with both formal and informal elements that come together to form a symbiotic relationship. The positive space is where teachers can challenge the status quo and interrogate the structural inequalities that are inherent within the education system. Teachers also should be aware of the negative influences of the hidden curriculum that often leads to the marginalisation of young children from minority ethnic backgrounds (Magaldi and Trub, 2018). Furthermore, it inadequately prepares them for the future has a direct negative impact on minority ethnic pupils' experiences, sense of belonging and attainment (Gillborn, 2018).

From a critical race theory perspective, Harlep (2010) argues that curriculum continues to be structured around mainstream white, middle-class values 'this hidden curriculum services white students and it disservices students of colour' (p.

21). Moreover, he argues that the not seeing nature of whiteness leads to a colour-blind approach to the curriculum which leads ultimately to a Eurocentric and western curriculum (Moncrieffe, 2020; Liyanage, 2020). Similarly, Moncrieffe, questions that if the majority of teaching staff in schools are White-British, then could this mean that they will be more inclined to maintain the 'cultural reproduction' of White-British history in schools and classrooms through their privileged 'white' perspectives (2020, p.8).

Minority ethnic teachers using their cultural, linguistic and religious identities: a culturally responsive pedagogy

This section will now discuss how minority ethnic teachers make use of their diverse identities in their teaching of curricula with a vision for equity and change.

Khashif is a thirty-four-year-old male teacher who has been teaching for over ten years. His ethnic identity is British Asian, and he is a Muslim. He currently teaches in a school where there is a large percentage of minority ethnic children attending. When asked in what way his identity as a minority ethnic teacher impacts or makes a difference in his teaching, he replied:

I have a passion for my subject first and foremost (long pause)...I guess me being a teacher provides a different experience for a lot of kids, I always make reference to things/events that BME kids can relate to and this is something that comes easy to me as I, too, have experienced it ...when I think back to when I was at high school and if I had a minority ethnic teacher, I will always wonder what kind of impact it would have had on me? Perhaps it would have shown me that we are 'normal' kind of people and someone I could have aspired to be. It may have helped me to connect better with what I am learning...it was always a struggle.

(Khashif)

Kashif, at first, seems to draw on the fact that it is his passion for his subject that has an impact on his teaching. There is a long pause and he then comments that perhaps being a minority ethnic teacher brings a '*different experience*' for many children, and he does this by drawing on '*things/events*' that minority ethnic children can relate to. He also adds that this '*comes easy*' as he has experienced what it is like not to have a minority ethnic teacher and the consequent struggle to connect with what he was learning. His subsequent comment on being seen as 'normal' further highlights the importance of having teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds in schools so that minority ethnic children are able to see teachers who look like them.

It is this validation that many researchers over the past few decades have highlighted (Ladson-Billings, 1995; Bhatti, 1999; Cummins, 2005; Arshad et al., 2005; Kohli, 2014). This connection with learning is discussed earlier in the literature review as Culturally Responsive Pedagogy (CRP) where cognisance is given to the culture, language and heritage of learners lived experiences (Cummins, 2005; Lander, 2011). Khashif does not go into any detail on how he does this but in line with CRP, this includes setting an appropriate cultural context and utilising resources that are familiar to minority ethnic children.

Magaldi and Trub (2018) undertook a qualitative research study in the US involving over one hundred teachers from diverse ethnicities: Trinidadian, Jamaican, African, Haitian, and Dominican. Like this study, focus groups were used to stimulate a general conversation about their experiences of being a teacher. Magaldi and Trub findings revealed that minority ethnic teachers 'bridge the cultural divide that has long existed between white teachers and minority ethnic children (2018, p.314). Furthermore, Kohli (2021) argues that minority ethnic teachers academically and

social-emotionally engage minority ethnic students and serve as 'cultural brokers with the community' (p.11).

Abu- Zhar is a male, British Asian teacher who has been teaching for over fifteen years as a Science teacher. He draws on his knowledge as a Muslim scientist to ensure that the children learn about world scientists who have contributed to science:

.... I tell them about the great Muslim scientists..., like for example, where algebra came from, where alkalis came from... we know that Peter Higgs won the Nobel prize for Higgs boson, you know the particle responsible for giving all other particles mass but Abdus Salam influenced him, you know, I'm enjoying that as well because being a scientist I know this stuff but also being Muslim, I am aware of the many scientists from across the world who played key roles but the texts always just emphasise the western scholars...just take Abdus Salam, he laid the groundwork for Higgs yet he was just one of many Muslim scientists whose names are never mentioned in the books that children read.' When I do acid and alkali's, I tell them exactly where the word Alkali comes from, for example, right now I am doing the atom and that's Professor Jim Al-Khalili. I could have had Professor Brian Cox, but on video, I've got Professor Jim Al-Khalili talking about quantum mechanics.

Abu-Zahr clearly states that as a Muslim he is aware of the many Muslim scholars who have contributed to the field of science. He also recognises texts read by the children as part of their science curriculum '*emphasise the western scholars*' and exclude scientists who laid the foundations of some ground-breaking concepts. Moreover, he shares with the children that the scientist who won the Nobel Prize for discovering the Higgs boson, otherwise known as the God particle, because it is said to be what caused the Big Bang that created our universe many years ago, was Peter Higgs. However, he also highlights that the scientist behind this discovery was

in fact a Muslim named Abdus Salam. When asked if this is part of the existing curriculum in the school, he responded:

...are you serious? This stuff was not in the resources we used when I was at school and it is still not included. We are supposed to teach what is in the text...colleagues always ask why I do this, and the Head of Department often ticks me off and tells me to stick to the planned curriculum and not to digress but we owe it to our children. They should know the truth of our history!!

(Abu-Zahr)

His response highlights a number of issues. Firstly, questions around the content of the '*planned curriculum*' prescribed in his school programme and texts. Abu-Zahr is stating quite clearly that the information he shares with his class is excluded from texts and argues that the children should '*know the truth*'. This failure to legitimise the contributions to knowledge from minority ethnic people, from across the world, results in the systemic privileging of Eurocentric knowledge. The centrality of Whiteness as an instrument of power and privilege ensures that particular types of knowledge continue to remain omitted from our curriculums (Tate & Bagguley, [2017](#)). Lianagye (2020) argues that power, privilege and elitism frame the curriculum through a White Eurocentric/Western perspective lens in academic institutions, which has predicated and reinforced racism in its structures through the exclusion of other world views and narratives. By identifying and investigating this, we will have a better collective understanding of how race is constructed and be better equipped to recognise and challenge racism more effectively within our curricula and beyond.

Abu-Zhar offers a brief insight into his own experience when he responded, 'this stuff was not in the resources we used when I was at school'. This indicates that he also experienced a similar curriculum which placed an emphasis on colonial knowledge (Leonardo, 2016). In his attempt to tell the truth to the young pupils we can see his

resistance to the current context of a Eurocentric curriculum. He applies a more critical lens which seeks to disrupt, challenge and makes visible the invisible racism in existing scholarship and learning and teaching within education. He is reframing the science lesson by sharing the contributions of scientists across the world. prioritises whiteness and does not fully prepare colleagues to consider antiracist practices or the impact of teaching on our diverse students.

Abh-Zhar's counter-narrative helps to resist and interrupt European and western discourses which prioritise whiteness, more formally known as decolonising the curriculum. In education, decolonisation involves acknowledging and critically examining the influence of colonial legacies on education systems, and its various sub-components such as knowledge and the curriculum (Maldonado-Torres, 2007; Liyanage, 2020).

Naila is a British Asian who has been teaching Modern Studies in a secondary school for thirteen years. Like Abu-Zahr, she too questions what she is teaching and the messages this gives out to not just her minority ethnic pupils but her white pupils too:

I made a lot of enemies in my school the day I said that teaching global citizenship is not enough... (laughs out loud) but I don't mind. I said we need to make sure that the history, the right history of Britain, of Europe needs to be taught to the young because ...the wealth of this nation. What made Britain what it is and what made Europe what it is today... places like Africa and India – that's where all the gold, diamonds and precious metals came from and so if the young don't know that what we have and what the slave trade has brought to Scotland then the natives, the young don't know all these things and understand it...showing on the television is not enough, dramatizing it is not enough ...it needs to be a core subject... make sure it appears in exams.

(Naila)

Naila also highlights the significant presence of colonialism in the curriculum and states that conversations around the history of enslavement and empire are absent. Moreover, the show concerns that her pupils are not aware of this. Her comments also about media are important to reflect on. So, when asked about her comment on global citizenship not being enough and television not being enough she remarked:

no... to begin with, it is not examinable...she laughs...that's the time the children come into play and watch programmes on BBC and what they are watching is how to contribute money to people in Bangladesh and Ethiopia or wherever... it is more or less that. You are reinforcing a stereotype that people from these countries are poor and that 'we' (with emphasis) can help ...how do you think that makes the Black and South Asian pupils feel?

Here, Naila is highlighting the fact that subjects like global citizenship are not examined and that there is an absence of critical depth to what the pupils learn as they watch programmes that position a racial hierarchy of how the West can contribute financial resources. This reinforces racial stereotyping. I argue that both Naila and Abu-Zahr regarded their role as teachers to disrupt the stereotypes that lead to inequality as a vehicle to promote social justice, for all the children they teach but in particular, for the minority ethnic pupils.

You have to be careful, very careful, introducing the truth to the Black man who has never previously heard the truth about himself, his own kind, and the white man ... The Black brother is so brainwashed that he may even be repelled when he first hears the truth.

(Malcolm X, *The Autobiography of Malcolm X*, 1965)

Evidence of power, privilege and racial hierarchies can be identified through Naila's narrative. There are many national campaigns like 'Why is My Curriculum White and Decolonising the Curriculum' which seek to dismantle and disrupt the practices within educational establishments from schools to universities. Heleta (2016) argues that UK educational policy fails to have a conceptual overview of how race and racism impacts within school processes and practices. Given the changing demography where pupil diversity is in the increase, it is important to note the lack of progress in terms of ensuring that policies and curriculum are responsive to such diverse needs (Li.et.al, 2015). As such, adopting a culturally responsive pedagogy ensures that both BME staff and young BME people see themselves in the teaching and learning process (Ladson-Billings, 1995, Kohli, 2014).

There has been much debate in recent years around the difference between multi-cultural education and anti-racist education. Peters (2015) argue that multi-cultural education positions minority ethnic communities as exotic and reduces practice to simply celebrating tokenistic cultural festivals. However, anti-racist education is rooted in action as there is an acknowledgment that racism does exist and educators are well placed to actively address this. Using an anti-racist lens helps to make visible the many different power structures which remain largely intact within our school structures through policies, practices and curricula. Moreover, Peters argue that educational settings will continue to reinforce white privilege if educators do not have the racial literacy with which to examine and critically reflect on not just what they teach but how they teach.

Cultivating an understanding and self-awareness about their own positionality in the world and education, and by extension how these impact upon what they teach and how they teach it. They are both attempting to reframe the way they think about curricula with a strong anti-racist consciousness applied to those discussions (Kohli, 2021). Transforming the ways in which every pupil learns, experiences, and then takes those lessons forward into the world, benefitting everyone. CRP explicitly acknowledges and teaches explicitly about racism and anti-racism, both past and present within our curricula and interrogates the pathways and privileges that lead to

certain knowledge and narratives to be amplified or silenced (Ladson-Billings, 2005). Both Abu-Zahr and Naila question whose stories get told and who gets to tell the stories and where is space for the counter-narratives?

Naila also shared that in doing this work she has '*...made a lot of enemies*'. When asked if she could elaborate on this, she responded:

My white colleagues get annoyed and say that I am causing problems and this is the way we have always done things – why change? I want to scream out loud and say “look around you – who are you teaching and what it is doing to them...we need to change and be responsive to the children’s needs. We will always face pushback.

(Naila)

It can be argued that the minority ethnic teachers in this study are challenging the status quo in terms of not only what is being taught but how it is being taught. Deng (2017) argues that '*...teachers are fundamentally curriculum makers – not curriculum deliverers or implementers*'. (p.16)

Priestly and Phillippou (2019) argues that the curriculum is political and presents four broad ideologies or orientations. The first is academic nationalism which includes traditional/liberal forms of knowledge which are content led. Secondly, he refers to social efficiency which involves the preparation of future citizens and learners. The third orientation is humanism focussed on human development and child centered curriculum and lastly, social deconstructivism challenging inequality and social justice. I argue that the minority ethnic teachers in this study demonstrate nuanced understandings of the practices associated with the curriculum – i.e. curriculum making and drawing on their cultural experiences they are skilled in being able to make the curriculum meaningful in their contexts. However, the barriers they face are perhaps linked to their limited agency in this area.

It is well documented that teachers play a large role in the success of their pupils and there are always notable change agents amongst them (Heijden et, al. (2015). Bandura (2001, p.2) states that ‘to be an agent is to intentionally make things happen by one’s actions’. However, teachers are also self-conscious of the complexity that change brings to schools and this will have an impact on how they act accordingly. Sannino (2010) assert that teachers are well placed to resist and advocate for change. However, Eteläpelto et, al. (2013) argue that if teachers are influenced by their personal characteristics and how they see themselves as teachers then more work is needed around teacher agency and how this can be developed at both a classroom and school level. (Beijaard, Meijer, & Verloop, 2004; Kelchtermans, 2009).

Moreover, Vähäsantanen & Eteläpelto, (2011) argue that teachers’ sense of their professional selves influences how they practice agency at work. This is particularly significant as the teachers in this study have shared the challenges they face in constructing their professional identities and as such, this inevitably has an impact on how they practice agency. Hattie (2012) discusses the importance of teachers’ personalities and beliefs and the impact this has on the success of their pupils. He also argues that individual characteristics influence their sense of teacher agency e.g. Bakkenes et al., 2010; Fullan, 2013). This resonates with the case of minority ethnic teachers in this study in how comfortable and confident they feel about their identity as a teacher to influence the pupils they work with.

Heijden et, al. (2015) undertook an exploratory study to obtain insights into what characterises teachers as change agents. Interviews were conducted involving external experts with expertise in curriculum, principals, and teachers from primary schools. There was no reference to any participant being from a minority ethnic background, which is the case for many research studies exploring teacher agency. The analysis revealed that characteristics pertain to lifelong learning (being eager to learn and be reflective), mastery (giving guidance, being accessible, positive,

committed, trustful, and self-assured), entrepreneurship (being innovative and feeling responsible), and collaboration (being collegial). It can be argued that the minority ethnic teachers in this study, they do have the eagerness to learn but the opportunity to explore categories within the mastery characteristics present as barriers. In terms of how they are positioned than the question of whose guidance is valued over others. They are committed but perhaps self-assurance is problematic because of the pushback they experience of colleagues when they attempt to facilitate change.

In terms of collaboration, Heijden et, al. (2015) found that teachers are willing to work collaboratively with their colleagues, particular, those who are committed to becoming agents of change. They also indicate that teacher agency is rooted in action and to lead change effectively, they need to work collaboratively with their colleagues. However, as much as the minority ethnic teachers in this study attempt to collaborate, they are met with hostility from fellow colleagues. The minority ethnic teachers have a sense of agency in their own classroom, but this does not appear to extend to the school level.

An important part of expanding on both personal and professional identities of minority ethnic teachers is the discourse that provokes transformation in their thinking. As such, Slay and Smith (2010) encourage a personal transformation where they become conscious that as professionals, they, too, should be afforded status and respect. They promote the kind of interaction that has the power to confront teachers' ideas about themselves and their profession, through their beliefs, actions, emotions, language and appearances. As such, they go on to experience transformations in the schools where they teach. When the participants were asked what they bring to their teaching, they shared stories of when they stood their ground and commanded respect and did not shy away from discussing controversial issues and started to exercise activism through agency:

'I am confident in pointing out to colleagues that they have overstepped the mark in terms of the Race Equality regulations. People are only vulnerable if

they don't know their rights. I know my rights; I have had a senior role within my teacher union.'

(Abu- Zahr)

"There has been occasions where teachers have said things that are down right out of order. I think it goes on in all workplaces...I think there are hidden prejudices, it's everywhere...and when you are working with children, it's you know, you cannot put up with this! I will challenge my colleagues because if I don't then it can have a negative effect on the young people'

(Kasim)

Both highlight their ability to address any issues around inequality confidently - for Abhu-Zahr, the importance of knowing his rights and for Kasim, his awareness of '*hidden prejudices*'. I interpret the comments made by teachers which in his words are '*down right out of order*' to refer to the daily, subtle discrimination experienced by him.

Safia is a female teacher who has been teaching for over ten years. When asked whether she felt that her cultural and linguistic identity had an impact on her practice, she responded:

When I am in school, I am just a teacher

(Safia)

I asked Safia to explain what being '*just a teacher*' meant for her. She explained:

I teach Maths and that's what I am there for. I don't feel comfortable talking about my culture...this is my workplace and who I am and what I do outside, I see no need to discuss.

It seems clear from Safia's comments that she believes that her professional identity remains separate from her personal identity. Her comment *'I teach Maths and that's what I'm there for'* suggests that she is adopting a technical approach to her teaching – she is only employed to teach a subject. Her subsequent comment *'I don't feel comfortable talking about my culture...this is my workplace'* further reinforces this point. She is clear that her culture has no place at work. Her tone and body language seemed to indicate that this was making her feel anxious. It is important to consider why she doesn't feel *'comfortable'* with her culture and how she views her *'workplace'*. I interpret this to mean that the environment in which she works is white homogenous and monocultural and she appears to have accepted this to be the norm. She clearly does not recognise a place for her own cultural identity to coexist with her white peers and her anxiety perhaps manifests in adopting two separate identities – one for school and one for home (Cummins, 2005; Daniel, 2019).

Safia, is trying to fit in and perhaps drawing from her own school experience, which promoted dominant white cultural values, her cultural identity was not acknowledged. She has learned that there is no place for her personal self to exist. Furthermore, she states *'who I am or what I do outside, I see no need to discuss'*, I interpret this to mean that Safia perhaps she feels it is an invasive question which has no relevance to her, and a question she does not want to acknowledge. Daniel (2019, p.26) argues that ME teachers adopt a survival strategy:

Black faculty members may ascribe to the expectations of docility and silence, and refrain from questioning the existing status or 'rocking the racism board.

Safia appears to have assimilated into the dominant white culture in order to fit in. Using a CRT lens, Safia's comments reflect internalised racism, a concept that explains when minority ethnic people consciously or unconsciously accept a racial hierarchy (Kohli, 2014). Having internalised racism can lead to a lack of self-esteem and this can perhaps help to understand why Safia feels this way. Her experiences in school have perhaps convinced her of the inferiority of her racial community. Kohli (2014) asserts:

If students grow up and become teachers without a space to critically reflect on and heal from their experiences with internalised racism, they can also carry problematic beliefs into classrooms and replicate the cultural alienation students of colour experience in schools.

(p.371)

Moreover, Magaldi and Trub (2018) argues this potentially oppresses minority ethnic teachers' identity and that of the young minority ethnic people they teach. Purwar in talking about bodies out of place and how they are more likely to conform to the majority:

When established institutions open their doors to postcolonial bodies, they have a strong preference for those who have assimilated the 'mother country's legitimate language...They bear the signs of cultural refinement. As an instrument of the governance of 'civility', the acquisition of the imperial/legitimate language is able to take racialised bodies through a passage of rites to becoming honourable human beings (2004, p.112).

Safia may be struggling to comprehend the intimate connection between identity and the self. Thus, it is important to support minority ethnic teachers to acknowledge and better understand internalised racism in schools. It may be that Safia did not have an

opportunity to explore identity construction within her teacher training. Beachamp and Thomas (2009) argue that teacher education programmes seem the most likely place to understand identity and its evolving nature and that opportunities to reflect on how their teacher identity is shaped and redefined should form part of these programmes (Slay and Smith, 2009).

On the other hand, Yasmeen and Shagufta both female teachers, seem to suggest that despite trying hard to keep their ethnicity and culture separate they seem to influence in some shape or form:

I very rarely let my culture or colour come into these things...I'm very professional...

(Yasmeen)

I try my best not to bring my personal identity into the classroom but it does....

(Shagufta)

Yasmeen's word choice '*rarely let*' suggests that she tries hard to separate her personal self from her professional self where she can. She appears to do this because she sees herself as being '*very professional*'. I interpreted this to mean that she considers fitting in to be what is expected of her, and she does not wish to set herself apart from her fellow white colleagues. Interestingly, there also appears to be the view that if you make your culture visible then this is considered to be unprofessional and so therefore perhaps to avoid this, she is ascribing to the expectations of an assimilatory process in which they are silenced and remain docile. Thus the construction of her identity is influenced by the dominant white culture of the school– anything that marks her out to be different is avoided (Purwar, 2004; Beauchamp and Thomas, 2009; Sachs, 2016).

Like Yasmeen, Shagufta also tries her '*best not to bring*' her personal self into the classroom but what sets her apart is that she acknowledges that despite trying to separate her personal identity, '*...it does*' enter the classroom. I interpreted this to mean that she was not referring to her culture or language because drawing from Yasmeen and Safia's experiences, one seems to consciously choose to leave aside their culture. Rather, in this case, Shagufta was making direct reference to her skin colour, as this is something that she cannot choose to change. There appear to be some challenges for Safia, Yasmeen and Shagufta about their understanding of identity with a particular focus on the link between identities, the self and external forces such as life experiences. Not wishing to acknowledge their culture or language could be an attempt by all three teachers to adopt an assimilatory stance in order to be accepted into a respectable position as teacher. It could also be because they have not had minority ethnic teacher role models, so the only experience they have had of teachers are white professionals, and they do not know otherwise.

This resonates with Yasmeen's reference to '*I'm very professional*'. Furthermore, this acceptance of the dominant culture and language carries significance in terms of who is an 'insider' and 'outsider' and Goldberg offers insight here:

Black people are faced with the dilemma that the principal mode of progress and self-elevation open to them is precisely through self-denial, through the effacement, the obliteration, of their blackness. They are predicated, that is upon the possibility of rendering a significant feature of their self-definition invisible, if not altogether effaced. This invisibility, in turn, is affected through the necessity of recognition by whites which is begrudgingly extended only at the cost of the invisibility of blackness.

(Goldberg, 1997, p.185)

This lack of understanding around identity development is further evident from both Yasmeen and Shagufta's responses, again perhaps questioning whether identity construction was explored during their training or subsequent professional development. Arguably, it is important for Initial Teacher Education institutes to ensure that discussions around expectations, aspirations and understandings of what is required in the development of their teacher identities need to be unpacked and understood (Day and Greene, 2018). Where teachers have an awareness of their identities, this leads to a strong sense of agency:

Human beings are active agents who play decisive roles in determining the dynamics of social life and in shaping individual activities.

(Sfard & Prusak, 2005, p.15)

It is not surprising then that they feel their cultural identity bares no relevance to their 'professional lives' and as such, fail to lead a sense of agency within their teaching to transform contexts or reach desired goals (Pillen, Den Brok, and Beijaard, 2013).

Progression to leadership roles - barriers and enablers

Barriers

Unequal treatment – being overlooked and devalued

Despite the benefits that minority ethnic teachers bring into schools, some of the participants discussed the racial hierarchies that exist within schools particularly when it comes to progression in their careers. I found that some of the participants

wavered in their sense of their racial identities. They saw their cultural, religious and linguistic skills as being both enablers and barriers in their teaching careers.

Farhana, as been a Principal Teacher for over 25 years, in one of Scotland's most ethnically diverse schools with a minority ethnic pupil population. She discusses how she is always called upon to engage with minority ethnic parents who have little English and only then does she receive acknowledgement from the HT. Similarly, Zainab makes reference to a further challenge; highlighting her ethnicity and faith which Crenshaw refers to as intersectionality - double discrimination where Zainab's colour and faith intersect and compound (1989).

The HT just picks up the phone and says "have you got two minutes could you come down" – He needs a little bit of help in translating, parents coming in with no English. I mean one day he said "It's amazing having you here" ...but this appreciation is forgotten very quickly.

(Farhana)

It's not just the colour of my skin but it's now my faith...I always get asked to speak about Islam when it's Ramadhan...I don't mind but it shouldn't just be me expected to do this...if I am willing to do additional work then surely this should be recognised?

(Zainab)

Both Farhana and Zainab comments align with aspects of Santoro's (2015) research which investigated the experiences of culturally diverse teachers working in Australian schools. The indigenous teachers reported feelings of being pigeonholed – to connect to the indigenous students and to teach 'culture' to the majority ethnic white students. Their colleagues viewed indigenous teachers as indigenous rather

than teachers and were seen as the cultural expert placing a burden on them. Like Zainab's comment about not just expected to do things related to her ethnicity but an additional burden of speaking about her faith during Ramadan.

Both Farhana and Zainab were asked if this extra work they do is recognised in any way by their leaders in schools. Zainab just laughed out loud and said:

I am just expected to do this...it's as if that is all I am here to do. It is never discussed as part of my professional development. I do raise it though but it is overlooked.

Zainab alludes to the pigeonholing and tokenistic representation that Santoro highlighted in her study of Indigenous teachers (2015). Farhana elaborated a little further on her experience of supporting the diverse communities in the school:

I have been a Principal Teacher for many years teaching in English and as Pastoral care, supporting the cultural and linguistic needs of minority ethnic pupils... They (senior team) are beginning to accept that I'm actually a bit of a bonus being in there (the school) ... an internal post came up for acting Assistant Head and I applied for it. I cited all the additional work that I do in my role and also stressed the cultural diversity work I do across the school. I didn't get the job and when I asked for feedback, I was told that I did not have enough strategic leadership. Well, how else am I supposed to get this if you are not prepared to support me?

(Farhana)

Drawing from a CRT perspective, one of the tools used to understand the power and privilege is interest convergence. Derek Bell (1992), one of the founding scholars of

CRT argued that the rights of minority ethnic people advance only when they converge with the interests of white people. We can see this in Farhana's example of the HT only calling her when he needed to speak to parents who did not communicate in English.

Bell (1992) would argue that Farhana's role in the school is to connect and engage with minority ethnic students and their families which in turn supports their academic success and she should be recognised and valued for this work. The positive test results showcase the success of the HT in leading the school; thus the interests should converge conditionally.

However, Gillborn (2013) argues:

Derek Bell's concept of interest convergence argues that moments of racial progress are won when White powerholders perceive self-interest in accommodating the demands of minoritised groups; such moments are unusual and often short-lived. Presently, we are witnessing the reverse of this process; a period of pronounced interest-divergence, when White powerholders imagine that a direct advantage will accrue from the further exclusion and oppression of Black groups.

(Gillborn, 2013, p.477)

Moreover, Warmington (2021) argues that when minority ethnic teachers, like Farhana, begin to question or disrupt the existing structures, it then becomes clear that the school is more interested in maintaining the status quo of the existing, white structures, than its diverse teachers. As such, Farhana is kept in her place as a PT and any strategic leadership for her, could threaten the very structures of the institution that seeks to privilege the dominant culture. Warmington argues that this is

where interests diverge, leaving minority ethnic teachers to do all things diverse while their white colleagues reap the benefits. This is further evidenced through Yusuf and Mumta's comments:

I spent a lot of time helping and training teachers and then they get promoted – I don't

(Yusuf)

I am invited to the table to improve the diversity quota but then nothing I say is listened too...they just want to do what they always do.

(Mumta)

Kohli (2021) makes reference to the unrecognised labour of minority ethnic teachers otherwise known as 'minority tax and cultural tax':

There are three dimensions of this tax. First it is the uncompensated and unrecognized labor...when it comes to the dealing with, being a representative for, or serving as an expert on issues of race, equity, and diversity. Second, it is the added stress that race...work put on the body, mind and spirit of faculty of color. Third it is the added burden that comes with being a person of color in everyday life- the everyday instances or disrespect and incivility encountered on and off campus'. (xv)

Farhana, Zainab and Yusuf's comments demonstrate how important it is to have a diverse workforce which will help to build stronger relationships with minority ethnic pupils and their families. However, the policies and practices in schools remain largely unchanged (Arshad, 2018; Mohammed, 2020; CRER, 2021). Furthermore, minority ethnic teachers continue to be overlooked, pigeonholed and critiqued when

they are trying to teach in a culturally responsive way. This conflict has a considerable impact on the wellbeing of minority ethnic teachers as they begin to question their place in the profession (Miller, 2019).

A further area where participants identified unequal treatment when seeking progression centred on having to work much harder than their white colleagues. Farhana remarked:

I have to be whiter than white! I worked doubly hard to be a Principal Teacher and have been through many interviews to progress to the next stage as Depute Head Teacher. I don't know what more I can do to demonstrate my skills. I always get told that I am not quite there yet, enrol on this course and that, I have them all...yet nothing.

(Farhana)

The doors just close. I give up...I have been trying for over 30 years and will just bow out soon because I cannot take anymore, not physically nor mentally...clearly my face doesn't fit!

(Adnan)

It's not a glass ceiling, it's a concrete ceiling and it hasn't even chipped... I am a female, women of colour and a Muslim...I stand no chance!

(Ambreen)

For some participants the social networks formed in schools were places they felt they didn't fit in:

I never received a tap on my shoulder ...but I watch my white colleagues who are being coached into promoted posts... (Laughs out loud) I like to call it 'professional grooming'. They go out to the pub on a Friday after school and chat about opportunities and offer support to each other. I don't feel comfortable being in a pub ...I used to go but then I experienced some racism – someone shouted 'terrorist' because of my beard.

(Yusuf)

Mboyo (2017) argues that racism both at an institutional and interpersonal level is one of the main reasons why minority ethnic teachers are underrepresented in school leadership roles and to find some solutions, more nuanced understandings of the nature of this discrimination is required. Ambreen's comment about a 'concrete ceiling' indicates the importance of intersectionality as a key barrier. Crenshaw (1989) discusses this as multiple layers of disadvantage that a person of colour would face.

In 2018, a survey conducted by the Educational Institute of Scotland (EIS), Scotland's largest teaching union, highlighted that 43% minority ethnic teachers feel they had been overlooked for promotion and a staggering 75% felt that promoted posts were difficult to obtain. The report also documented the racism that minority ethnic teachers were reporting: racist or Islamophobic language; racists attitudes from colleagues; invisibility of racial diversity within the curriculum and racist comments from parents (EIS, 2018).

Four years on, the landscape has not changed much despite the Scottish Government's focus on diversifying the workforce. Recent statistics recorded show only 0.4% progress has been made in five years towards boosting the number of minority ethnic teachers in the profession (Scottish Government, 2022). Now sitting at only 1.8%, this falls far short of Scottish Government's 2030 target of a 4% black and minority ethnic teaching workforce and even further behind a true reflection of

the diversity of the Scottish population today (EIS, 2022). Moreover, in terms of leadership roles the statistics are even more concerning with only three minority ethnic head teachers in Scotland. What is even more problematic is where school leaders do not see this an issue. A study conducted by one of the most diverse local education authorities in Scotland, revealed that Headteachers did not see this lack of minority ethnic leadership as an issue (McClung et.al, 2018):

I have no reason to think that promotion is more difficult for teachers from a minority ethnic background.

(Head Teacher, Secondary)

I think they are proportionally represented at each level of the profession.

(Head teacher, Primary)

Miller (2019) reported several factors related to the progression of teachers from minority ethnic backgrounds in England that resonate with the minority ethnic teachers in this study. Race and racism were found to be a factor in terms of stereotyping and this has continued over the last two decades from Earley et al. (2002) stating stereotyping affected the progression of minority ethnic teachers to senior roles. A decade later, Early et al. (2012) reconfirmed this was still the case. Furthermore, Lumby and Coleman (2007), found racial discrimination to be a barrier and again in 2017 this too was evident (Lumby and Coleman, 2017).

Another factor related to the progression was institutional practices where minority ethnic teachers are marginalised and experience indirect racism through policy processes that privilege the dominant culture (Kohli, 2021). Miller (2019) also makes reference to group membership or affiliations, where informal networks, such as the social events in the pub which Yusuf highlighted, exclude some groups. Finally, Religion was also viewed as a barrier to progression, particularly for Muslims (Shah

and Sheikh, 2010). This was certainly the experience that Yusuf and Adnan shared regarding their appearances. Moreover, Iqbal's research (2019) into the experiences of Muslim Pakistani Head teachers also showed where faith and gender intersect, being Muslim and male added a further layer of disadvantage.

Enablers – assimilation, affiliation and allyship

The participants in this study also shared their experiences of trying to secure leadership posts. Shaista is a hijab-wearing Muslim woman and has been teaching for almost sixteen years. She remarked:

I had attended so many interviews to secure a leadership post – I was a Principal teacher but just could not make it to the next rung on the ladder and for me, that was a depute HT post. When I didn't get the job, the feedback was very woolly ...unhelpful nothing really tangible that I could try and address. I wondered if it was because of my hijab. I don't have the look maybe... so, for the next position I applied for, I removed my hijab for the interview. I got the job...I just know it was the material on my head that was the problem.

(Shaista)

Shaista shares something quite profound – the removal of her hijab demonstrates her way of trying to fit in and not set herself apart. Miller (2015) argues that appeasement or adaptation improved the chances of progression. Moreover, he asserts that three key aspects serve as enablers: to look like; share cultural habits/behaviours and lastly to adapt or adjust to the dominant white culture. Another example of communicating to minority ethnic teachers – leave your identity at the school front door.

Many of the participants spoke about their path towards leadership as a lonely journey:

I could see my white colleagues supporting each other – discussing applications and providing mock interviews. I was completely ignored, no one offered to support me. I often wonder what it would be like to have someone who would understand what I am going through...

(Keisha)

I met a teacher who looked like me when I attended a local authority in-service day (development day). I was so excited, and we connected instantly. We still keep in touch, and we support each other regularly especially when we are applying for promoted posts...we pick each other up when we are unsuccessful, which is always expected.

(Pooja)

Mosley (2018) argues that minority ethnic teachers need to figure out and navigate racially inequitable systems in schools and suggests that being part of an affiliated group of like-minded minority ethnic teachers. It helps them to see that they are not alone, and this acknowledgement becomes empowering and contributes to their progression. Moreover, Mosley discusses the Black Teacher Project in the USA which is a professional development programme which helps to sustain Black teachers. They set up support groups such as book clubs, inquiry groups, and drop-in “Rejuvenation Spaces.” They found that racial affinity spaces relieve stress as they collectively try to resist the racism they experience. This group activism helps to decrease the isolation that teachers experience and as such manages to retain those who were thinking of leaving the profession.

Finally, some of the participants discuss how they have been well supported by a white colleague in their school:

I have only been teaching for two years and the PT (Principal Teacher) in my English department has been so supportive. He is constantly trying to look out for opportunities to enhance my leadership skills. I know that he sees me for who I am and what I bring ... he always comes up with some ideas to introduce the pupils to different authors and perspectives...

(Waheed)

I experienced racism from one of the pupils and my colleague overheard. She immediately called it out...asking me if I was okay...this is the first time that someone supported me as normally, I am told that I am too sensitive. She even went a step further and spoke with the Head Teacher and said he needs to address this as a whole school issue...I was so grateful.

(Mumta)

Waheed's response shows how he is being supported by his senior colleague who acknowledges his differences and, in some ways, validates what he brings to teaching by providing opportunities for further professional development. Miller (2016) refers to this as 'White Sanction' where a minority ethnic teacher's skills are recognised and endorsed or legitimised by a white colleague (p.990). This validation is also evident in Mumta's response when her colleague acknowledged and addressed the racist incident. From a CRT perspective, the term 'White sanction' indicates a relationship where the power and gatekeeping lies with the white colleague. Miller acknowledges this but still holds firm that this endorsement is key to enabling agency.

Sue et al. (2019) describe this enabling as allyship:

Allies are individuals who belong to dominant social groups and, through their support of non-dominant groups actively work toward the eradication of prejudicial practices they witness in both their personal and professional lives.

(p.132)

Summary

In this chapter, the analysis has shown that minority ethnic teachers attempt to build positive relationships with the minority ethnic pupils they teach through relatable ties, such as culture, gender, and language and through connecting with minority ethnic pupils' families. The participants also demonstrated how they used their diverse identities and discuss their personal understandings of racism and injustices to disrupt the western euro-centric curriculum in schools and act as advocates for minority ethnic students in their school settings. They discussed how they stand up to the dominant structures that question their place in school and identified both the benefits and barriers to bringing their cultural, religious and linguistic skills into the classroom.

The analysis informed our understanding of minority ethnic teachers working in culturally diverse classrooms and also showed how they had agency to disrupt the status quo of the curriculum with the cultural wealth they bring. Minority ethnic teachers also discussed the limited agency they had in terms of career progression and share the barriers and enablers they experienced as they move to progress in their careers.

Chapter 7

Closing reflections: models for supporting minority ethnic teachers and recommendations

This thesis has provided a case study of the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland. This chapter draws on the research findings to develop conclusions about how minority ethnic teachers negotiate their professional identities and struggle to find a sense of belonging in school settings. It reports on findings that minority ethnic teachers faced additional barriers when attempting to use their cultural and linguistic experiences to inform the curriculum and how they teach. These experiences also affected their opportunities to forge relationships within wider professional networks and subsequently impacted their career progression.

The chapter presents a model for supporting minority ethnic teachers' professional identity, which emerged when the findings from Chapters 4, 5 and 6 were considered together. The chapter then discusses how this model and the research findings more broadly contribute new knowledge that shows how policy and practice have already been influenced by my research as an iterative process of learning about the context for minority ethnic teachers. Finally, I consider how the findings and recommendations drawn from my research can support the identification for future research.

The purpose of this qualitative study was to explore the case of minority ethnic teachers and their experiences within school education in Scotland. The focus groups and semi-structured interviews provided space for them to collectively discuss and unpack the internalised racism they experienced. They also discussed the ways in which they are now working to support the minority ethnic children they teach to prevent racism from manifesting in their pupils. In bringing the thesis

together to produce conclusive findings, I felt compelled to re-read the analysis chapters.

In chapter four, I introduced the findings while simultaneously discussing and analysing what the participants shared. As I began to re-read the thesis, I realised there were some key aspects present within the data. The first analysis chapter focused on the reasons why minority ethnic teachers in this study chose teaching as a career. Two core areas emerged that illuminated i) how minority ethnic teachers find a sense of belonging and ii) the discriminatory challenges experienced by them on a regular and routine basis. This highlighted the cultural factors which influenced their decisions as well as their religion and the strong desire to give back to their communities.

Chapter Four, also established that research participants came into teaching for reasons that would be routinely expected. This did not throw any new light on why minority ethnic teachers become teachers. It is however significant to note that although they all identified commonality in their decisions to become a teacher, all participants felt that they were persistently treated differently. This theme re-emerged in Chapter Five which explored some of the challenges experienced by participants while trying to construct their professional identities. The analysis reflected how minority ethnic teachers negotiated their own racialized identities. While some confidently acknowledged their diverse ethnic identities, others assimilated into the majority dominant culture of their white peers. The minority ethnic teachers in this study also threw light on how they negotiated the racial climates of ITE institutions and schools since they were students and now also in their professional lives as teachers. To support and sustain minority ethnic teachers in the profession, teacher education programmes, schools and local education authorities must acknowledge the systems that continue to marginalise and make school sites hostile places for minority ethnic teachers.

Devising a model for supporting minority ethnic teachers' professional identity

Four aspects of the professional identity construction of minority ethnic teachers

In chapters four, five, and six, the analysis highlighted findings relating to acknowledgement, affirmation, agency and activism. Through discussion, it was shown that these four aspects, when combined, were necessary to support minority ethnic teachers to construct and strengthen their professional identities and enhance the chances for minority ethnic teachers to have a positive experience of being a teacher. By way of illustration and explanation, I decided to call these four elements the 'The Four As Model of minority ethnic teachers professional identity construction'.

Acknowledgement – The aspect of acknowledgement was reflected when participants acknowledged that they did not feel a sense of belonging; and when they acknowledged that they had never realised their experiences of feeling isolated, being invisible and silenced were common to most minority ethnic teachers. Minority ethnic teachers acknowledged that what they were feeling and experiencing in terms of racial discrimination is real and exists. Some of the participants shared that they found discussing their experiences of racism helpful as they often were made to question whether they were overthinking or perhaps being too sensitive. However, CRT helped to focus on their racialized experiences and Kohli (2014) asserts that 'CRT unapologetically identifies the perpetrators and victims of racism' (p.369). This helped the participants in this study to have a language to name and acknowledge their experiences and use their voices to challenge the injustice they experienced. This acknowledgement validated their experiences, and the focus groups provided safe spaces for them to do so.

Affirmation – in chapters 5 and 6 the reflections of minority ethnic teachers illumine how they draw on their cultural, gender, linguistic and religious skills bringing added value to their teaching and the wider school and community. The participants' narratives touch upon the relational ties experienced by them and how they feel connected with their minority ethnic pupils and with their colleagues through informal networks where they meet and affirm experiences.

Agency – Minority ethnic teachers in this study have shown how they are capable of leading transformation by resisting the assimilatory processes and practices in schools that their minority ethnic pupils are subjected to. They also shared how they challenged the deficit framing of their minority ethnic pupils and communities and disrupt the euro-centric, racist curriculum in schools. This self-evaluation and critical reflection supported participants to step outside systemic expectations and allow different practices to emerge. Minority ethnic teachers saw themselves as change agents and discussed how they had insight into the racialized experiences of their minority ethnic pupils and stood as their advocates. Participants also experienced difficulty in gaining promotion in their workplace.

Activism – Participants demonstrated how they were building the capacity to organise for change. Through the lens of CRT, this study reveals the racialized realities of minority ethnic teachers and shows their resilience and strength to challenge inequity and racism within education. Their activism is also demonstrated through their agency to consider teaching strategies that are both culturally relevant and race cognisant. Minority ethnic teachers strengthened their racial literacy, built capacity within their communities and organised as educators and activists to make a difference by challenging the racial injustice in the lives of their minority ethnic pupils.

'The Four As Model of Minority Ethnic Teachers Professional Identity Construction'

Figure 2.

Contribution to new knowledge.

The purpose of this research was to explore the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland. The main aim of the study was to understand how participants develop their professional identities; explore what their expectations of being and becoming a teacher were; identify the enablers and barriers in using their cultural and linguistic skills in the classrooms and consider the extent to which this impacted on their career progression in terms of relationship building and social networks.

Thematic coding was used to identify key themes which were acknowledgement, affirmation, agency and activism. The analysis shows the need to ensure that there are spaces for minority ethnic teachers to talk, to understand and acknowledge their experiences and consider what can be done and how they can collectively take action. Using critical race theory as a theoretical framework provided a lens through which to analyse the data and to gain an empathic grasp of how participants negotiated their professional identities. Focus groups and semi-structured interviews provided participants with a space to share their counter-narratives.

Thus, my research albeit in a small, but significant manner contributes to a new and deeper understanding of the experiences of minority ethnic teachers in negotiating their professional identities. The analysis of participants' responses has enabled me to develop a model that has the potential of creating better processes to address three key areas faced by minority ethnic teachers: acknowledgement of individual/institutional racism; restricted agency and restricted career progression. I will explore these more in-depth in the next section.

Contribution to a Grassroots Movement for Change

During the data collection and analysis phase of my research, as I was researching the participant's perspectives, I became concerned that minority ethnic teachers needed a space to support each other, and should not have to wait for my research to be completed, to act on what was already being clearly articulated by them, which resulted in the development of SAMEE.

I co-founded an organisation called, SAMEE (Scottish Association of Minority Ethnic Educators) where acknowledgement and affirmation were a key focus of its purpose. Throughout my doctoral study, SAMEE has developed into a nationwide organisation led by minority ethnic education professionals. It has a presence across West, East and Central Scotland, with heightened visibility in areas with the highest concentration of Scotland's minority ethnic practitioners and learners in nursery, primary and secondary schools.

SAMEE education professionals provide support to minority ethnic educators and learners through Continued Professional Learning, workshops, seminars, conferences, one-to-one consultations and bespoke mentoring activities. The skillset and knowledge of SAMEE's members through their research in education, race equality, youth policy and lived experiences, encourage a stronger sense of identity and belonging among minority ethnic education professionals and create a stronger cohesion between minority ethnic pupils, parents, educators, school executives and national educational organizations. SAMEE is supported by Education Scotland, the General Teaching Council for Scotland, and other public bodies.

Applying the emerging Four As Model and academic frameworks of professional learning, I decided to develop a Leadership and Mentoring Programme to support many of my fellow minority ethnic teachers who reached out to SAMEE in search of a safe space. It was designed to reframe the discourse encouraging minority ethnic teachers to shift the focus from individual to systemic inequality. It was important to reject community deficits to reclaim the strengths; to share the power they have and feel connected. The programme is endorsed by Education Scotland, which is a Scottish Government executive agency charged with supporting quality and improvement in Scottish education. The programme also has been successful in gaining funding from Scottish Government to support the commitment to diversify the education workforce. The impact of this programme has been significant in supporting the retention of minority ethnic teachers. Many of the participants had been teaching for decades and shared how they were tired of resisting and the racial trauma they endured came at a cost to their physical and emotional wellbeing. The programme offered safe spaces to strengthen their professional identity and to build confidence as activists of equality matters.

Three areas of contribution:

Individual and institutional racism – acknowledgment and affirmation

The first area that this study has contributed to is that there is little to no acknowledgement of the individual and institutional racism that minority ethnic teachers face working in Scottish schools. Analysis has shown that some participants struggled to understand their feelings of isolation and inadequacy as the only minority ethnic teacher in their different schools. They shared their experiences of white colleagues adopting, what they described as a 'colour-blind' approach, denying the existence of racism but their use of counter-narratives helped to affirm and clarify that both overt and covert racial discrimination is a reality for them. The participants highlighted the importance of having safe spaces for them to come together to share their experiences. For many minority ethnic teachers who felt isolated in an all-white school, these spaces offered them a sense of belonging, where they felt part of a community of teachers who faced similar challenges.

This affirmation offered emotional encouragement which helped them to build resilience and confidence in their teacher identity. Education stakeholders should take action to enable critical, honest conversations in this area. It is also important to provide supportive networks for minority ethnic teachers to come together and affirm their cultural, religious and linguistic identities and share ideas on how these contribute to their teaching. As detailed earlier in the chapter, my concern that minority ethnic teachers needed a space to support each other, led to the development of SAMEE.

Minority ethnic teacher agency

The second area where this study contributes to new knowledge is in relation to minority ethnic teacher agency. Whilst there is much research on teacher agency and curriculum making, my literature review showed that minority ethnic teachers

were excluded from research and policy. Yet, this study demonstrates that some minority ethnic teachers draw on their cultural, religious and linguistic experiences to inform their teaching while others are reluctant to do so. Being able to activate their cultural knowledge, skills and experiences here, in this way not only promotes their teacher agency in making decisions about what to teach and how to teach but also supports curriculum making to be responsive and relevant to the needs of children from diverse backgrounds. The participants in this study who articulated a Culturally Responsive Pedagogy (CRP) became agents of change making the 'hidden' curriculum visible by challenging the dominant discourse of 'no problem here' (Davidson et al., 2018). However, the participants who were reluctant to use their cultural and linguistic skills for fear of the impact on their career progression, will require support to help them in strengthening their professional identity and developing their capacity to act, and have agency.

In the summer of 2020, a global response to the killing of George Floyd was led by the resurgence of the Black Lives Matter Movement. Students from across the world were calling for a decolonised curriculum (Liyanage, 2020). They argued that decolonisation requires a fundamental re-evaluation of the existing forms of teaching, learning in education. It was about acknowledging the ways in which our institutions reproduce unequal social structures. Therefore, meaningful engagement with decolonisation required reassessing curricula, attainment and representation concurrently. The Scottish Government has since committed to developing an antiracist curriculum/ decolonised curriculum in education. The findings of this study suggest that for this commitment to be realised, more work is required to support minority ethnic teachers in developing their identities. Where minority ethnic teachers are routinely expected to leave their diverse cultural identities outside of the classroom this raises a question about what it means to have a diverse workforce as discrete from making tokenistic gestures.

More recently, the Race Equality Framework for Scotland 2016-2030 commits to promoting good relations and community cohesion but how this manifest in educational practice is not clear. It states that 'Scotland's educators should be

confident and empowered to promote equality, foster good relations and prevent and deal with racism' (Scottish Government, 2016, p.54). To this end, the goal identified to achieve this aim is for practitioners to develop *intercultural competency*. Policy therefore should reflect critically to ensure culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) is not just limited to minority ethnic teachers but involves all teachers and should include a range of diverse ways of bringing their cultural identities into the classroom. This also leads me to rethink how the Curriculum for Excellence recognises the importance of CRP within everyday practices in a classroom and school setting.

My research of minority ethnic teachers' experiences in Scotland resonates with the need to bring CRP in terms of a range of personal and cultural identities. Rather than be suppressed, CRP should be encouraged in the classroom. This study showed that agency was important not just in terms of teachers' ethnicity but includes religion, sexuality, language, and disability among other protected characteristics.

Moreover, I was commissioned by the Scottish Council of Deans (SCDE) for Initial Teacher Education (ITE) to develop a national anti-racism framework for ITE. This will be launched in spring 2023.

Career progression – activism

Finally, the participants in this study discussed their feelings of being overlooked in terms of their career progression and that some, after many years, were able to acquire Principal Teacher posts whilst others did not. As identified in Chapter six, the phraseology of the glass ceiling metaphor was first coined by feminists in reference to the barriers women face in their career progression. The participants in this study believe that the primary influence on the barriers they faced were aligned to ethnicity which was typically evident in their experiences of marginalisation. One participant articulated that the extent of ethnic disadvantage was not a glass ceiling but rather a 'concrete' ceiling.

Minority ethnic teachers shared how they were excluded from social networks within the schools and local authorities they worked in and this presented a barrier to gaining promotion. They discussed feelings of exclusion despite actively trying to build relationships with their white peers as typical of the racial discrimination they faced. Yet, some participants highlighted the importance of being aware of their rights as a catalyst for becoming active in their trade unions. In doing so, they identified a sense of purpose that enabled them to come together, in a safe and constructive space for developing their professional growth. Working through trade unions, offered a route for personal growth but also helped to build capacity and resilience for bringing change across the wider professional workforce. According to participants, this kind of work identified a need to acknowledge the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers to review and eradicate ethnicity-related barriers to career progression. There is a need to raise awareness of intersectionality as a concrete barrier where minority ethnic teachers may be standing in the path of multiple disadvantages like some of the participants in this study – female, minority ethnic and Muslim.

If we are serious as a profession about challenging racism within contemporary society, we must consider the extent to which our education system is a tool for social change or is complicit in maintaining the status quo. My research has shown that ethnicity remains problematic within the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers in terms of the racism they experience; the agency they are afforded to draw on their lived experiences and cultural skills and the lack of opportunities they have in terms of career progression. More work is needed to realise the potential for our teaching workforce, regardless of ethnicity, to understand racism and how it presents in its multiple forms. However, this study offers hope in the midst of a current review of our education system in Scotland, working with key stakeholders e.g., teacher trade unions and Local Education Authorities to create a fairer more socially just society.

Recommendations

The research has shown that to understand and support minority ethnic teachers in negotiating their professional identities, the Four As Model: Acknowledgement, Affirmation, Agency and Activism, can serve as a tool for systemic change. We need to acknowledge and understand the additional barriers minority ethnic teachers encounter as they navigate their workplace and beyond and integrate with the majority white teaching workforce. It would be useful for education stakeholders to engage in conversation about how this model might be utilised and developed across educational institutions. The following recommendations have emanated from my research in the following key areas:

Practice:

1. The Four As Model should be introduced to Initial Teacher Education (ITE) and Teachers' Continuous Professional Learning (CPL), including leadership qualifications, to ensure that anti-racist practice is embedded within programmes. Consideration of Critical Race Theory and Whiteness studies by pre-service and in-service teachers should also be encouraged.
2. To ensure that teacher educators, teachers, and senior leaders in education are supported to build their racial literacy, a nuanced understanding of race and racism and how it manifests should be promoted.
3. Proactive sponsorship by the Scottish Government, Education Scotland, Trade Unions and Leaders within educational establishments should be offered, to ensure that minority ethnic teachers are able to take advantage of promotion into leadership roles.

Policy:

Where the use of safe words like diversity, intercultural awareness, fairness and equality in institutions and policies can result in the loss of critical reflections around racism and whiteness. Therefore:

1. Policies and frameworks need to acknowledge the voices and lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers and avoid taking a homogenous approach.
2. Explicit references to race and racism should be included to avoid colour-evasiveness.

Research:

This study has revealed that minority ethnic teachers are largely missing from research in areas such as teacher identity, teacher agency and teacher leadership. When reviewing current and past research on social justice leaders there is a tendency to focus on poverty, gender or additional support needs. Therefore:

1. There is a need to explore leadership in educational settings in Scotland that examine racial equity. This research has also shown how minority ethnic teachers' sense of agency is limited as they are questioned about what they teach. As the calls for 'decolonising the curriculum' increase, there is merit in developing a more nuanced understanding of how minority ethnic teachers use their cultural wealth to advocate for social change.
2. Research on how union representatives can be better supported to acknowledge and affirm the racialised experiences of minority ethnic teachers is required.

I end with a closing reflection from one of the participants and this inspired me to rethink the title of this thesis from 'negotiating' to 'celebrating' the professional identities of minority ethnic teachers:

I am celebrating today that I am black. Finally, I have been able to validate my experiences ... Now, I will say this out loud. No, I am not being sensitive and no, it's not just all in my head...please stop! See me and hear me. My agency is about my acknowledgement, to share with my people that it's okay to be black. I want the black children I teach, to feel valued. I want them to feel whole.

(Abayomi)

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Appendices

Appendix A – Consent Form

Negotiating Professional Identities: A Case Study of Minority Ethnic Teachers Experiences.

Consent Form

Participation in Focus Group and Semi-structured Interview - Statement of Consent:

Technique	With whom	Requirement of Participants
Focus group	8 minority ethnic teachers who have gained their teaching qualifications in Scotland and are currently teaching in Scotland.	To participate in focus group where a few questions will be prepared in advance to encourage them to speak about their experiences.
Semi-structured interviews	Up to 8 Participants from focus group x3 will be invited for individual interviews.	The participants will be asked to answer questions prepared in advance about their own personal experiences of teaching.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any questions to my satisfaction.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study within an agreed time limit.
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the project. Yes/No

(PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above project
Signature of Participant	Date

Appendix B

Negotiating Professional Identities:

A Case Study of Minority Ethnic Teachers Experiences.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Introduction

This study is being conducted by Khadija Mohammed, at the University of the West of Scotland, as part of her doctoral studies. Khadija is a Lecturer in the School of Education at the University of the West of Scotland.

Purpose of the study

You are invited to participate in a research study that sets out to investigate how - **How do minority ethnic teachers negotiate their personal and professional identities in the classroom?* There is a plethora of research around teacher identity but little that focuses on the identities of Minority Ethnic teachers. The study seeks to explore the lived experiences of minority ethnic teachers in Scotland to understand the ways in which their teaching and learning experiences draw from a range of cultural and linguistic experiences. (Ladson-Billings, 2011). Arshad (2012) argues that minority ethnic teachers will be able to function as role models and inform the whole school community in supporting diversity.

* For the purposes of this research the term 'minority ethnic' will be used. *Arshad (2005) states that the term 'minority ethnic' is mainly used to denote people who are*

in the minority within a defined population on the grounds of 'race', colour, culture, language or nationality.

The purpose of this study is to answer the following research questions:

- How do minority ethnic teachers construct their professional identity in a profession that does not mirror their ethnic identity?
- How do these teachers bring their own cultural, linguistic and religious identity to the classroom?
- What are their views on the recruitment and retention of minority ethnic teachers?

Participation - What specific techniques will be employed and what exactly is required of participants?

You will be required to take part in one focus group interview followed by an invitation to take part in an individual interview. This will be audio recorded. Participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw within an agreed time limit. The details are below:

Technique	With whom	Requirement of Participants
Focus group x3	8 minority ethnic teachers who have gained their teaching qualifications in Scotland and are currently teaching in Scotland.	To participate in focus group where a few questions will be prepared in advance to encourage a conversation about ME teachers' experiences.

Semi-structured interviews	From the three focus groups, 8 Participants will be invited for individual interviews.	The participants will be asked to answer questions prepared in advance about their own journey/narrative.

Risks and Benefits for the teachers participating in the study:

Participating within this research should help you to reflect more deeply on how you can, make use of your own cultural, linguistic and religious identity in schools which should, hopefully, be of benefit to you, your colleagues, your pupils and your prospective pupils.

Confidentiality:

Any information obtained in connection with this study that can be identified with you will be kept confidential and will be disclosed only with your permission. After a period of time I will destroy all original reports and identifying information that can be linked back to you.

What debriefing, if any, will be given to the participants?

Participants will be invited back to discuss the findings of the study.

How will the outcomes of the study be disseminated?

The outcomes of the study will be disseminated through the PhD dissertation and the possibility of academic papers emanating from it. It will also be referenced in my teaching at the university.

Voluntary nature of the study:

Participation in this research study is voluntary and you may withdraw within an agreed time limit.

Consent

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. If you feel that you do not wish to take part then can I please thank you for taking the time to read the information.

Contacts and questions:

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me:

Khadija Mohammed

Lecturer in Education

University of the West of Scotland

██

Personal details withheld.

████████████████

You may keep a copy of this form for your records.

APPENDIX C

Focus Group Questions

- Why teaching?
- What do you get out of your teaching?
- What do you bring/give to your teaching?
- What difference do you think it makes for minority ethnic children in having minority ethnic teachers?
- Do you think you offer particular support to minority ethnic pupils?
- Does your identity as a minority ethnic teacher impact or make a difference to your teaching?

Appendix D

Semi-structured Interview – Outline

Events and experiences in the personal lives of teachers are intimately linked to the performance of their professional roles. Some researchers (Bhatti, 1999; Kearney, 2003; Cummins, 2000; Arshad, 2012) have noted that teacher identities are not only constructed from the technical and emotional aspects of teaching for example, class management, subject knowledge and their personal lives but also as a result of an interaction between the personal experiences of teachers and the social, cultural and institutional environment in which they function on a daily basis.

Self-image

- Thinking about your identity as a teacher - How would you describe yourself?
- How does your own ethnic identity shape your teacher identity?

Self-Esteem

- Are you able to be yourself in school? If yes, how do you do this?

- What gives you a sense of belonging?
- What kind of relationship do you have with your peers from the ethnic majority?
- Are you treated equally?
- How do you feel about the Judgements made on you from colleagues, parents and other external agencies
- How would you describe your relationship with the pupils?

Job – motivation

- Why choose this career?
- How do you remain committed to your job?
- What unique contribution do you feel that you can make in helping to promote tolerance and support?
- In what ways have you been involved in developing school activities?

Task description

- How do you define your job?
- In what ways do you show your commitment to the job?
- In what ways can your cultural and linguistic experiences be used to inform your practice and support the pupils?
- Have opportunities arisen for you to influence the development of school policy? If answer to the above is yes, then please explain.
- Primary – how confident do you feel about delivering the curriculum?
- Secondary –How confident do you feel about delivering the subject/s that you teach in line with a curriculum for excellence – establishing links with other curricular areas e.g. literacy and wellbeing?

Future perspectives

- What are your expectations for the future development of your jobs?